

**From Knowledge to Narrative: Exploring the
Art and Techniques of Heritage Interpretation
in Indonesia**

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Declaration

This is to certify that this thesis content is my original work to the best of my knowledge, except for explicitly stated otherwise. This thesis has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other university.

Signed

Date : 20 January 2025

Abstract

This thesis investigates how Indonesian tour guides craft and deliver heritage narratives and shows that interpretation is a fundamentally social, co-produced process in which interpretive authority is continually negotiated. Using a qualitative, social-constructivist design, the study draws on semi-structured interviews with 36 guides and trainers across Jakarta, Bandung, and Yogyakarta, alongside document analysis. Findings indicate that competence in interpretation develops less through formal certification than through ongoing collective practice: peer exchange, mentoring, and sustained engagement with communities and sites. Within this social context, authority is not fixed in credentials or scripts; it is performed and redistributed through dialogue with peers, collaborative sourcing and verification of stories, sensitivity to local protocols and permissions, and careful handling of contested or painful histories. The thesis identifies narrative techniques such as clear thematic framing, purposeful sequencing, interactive questioning, and attentive use of sensory cues that enhance understanding, recall, and ethical awareness of provenance and consent. Conceptually, the study positions guides as active cultural mediators whose legitimacy arises from how they assemble, justify, and share knowledge with others on the ground. Practically, it recommends training programmes that institutionalise mentoring, reflective debriefs, and community partnerships alongside ethics and safety, thereby supporting context-sensitive, credible interpretation and more sustainable heritage tourism in Indonesia.

Keywords: heritage interpretation; tour guiding; interpretive authority; narrative; informal learning; authenticity; Indonesia

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

ACCSTP	ASEAN Common Competency Standards for Tourism Professionals
AHD	Authorised Heritage Discourse
AHI	Association for Heritage Interpretation
ANRI	<i>Arsip Nasional Republik Indonesia</i> (National Archives of the Republic of Indonesia)
AR	Augmented Reality
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations,
AWHF	African World Heritage Fund
BNSP	<i>Badan Nasional Sertifikasi Profesi</i> (Professional Certification Board)
CHSE	Cleanliness, Health, Safety, and Environment
COVID-19	Corona Virus Disease 19
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
HPI	<i>Himpunan Pramuwisata Indonesia</i> (The Indonesia Tourist Guides Association)
ICOMOS	International Council on Monuments and Sites
IDR	Indonesian Rupiah
IHS	Indonesian Heritage Society
InterpID	<i>Interpretasi Indonesia</i> – the Indonesian Society for Interpretation
KSPN	<i>Kawasan Strategis Pariwisata Nasional</i> (National Tourism Strategic Area)
LNT	Leave No Trace
LSP	<i>Lembaga Sertifikasi Profesi</i> (Professional Certification Institute)
MNI	<i>Museum Nasional Indonesia</i> (National Museum of Indonesia)
MRA-TP	Mutual Recognition Arrangement on Tourism Professionals
MSMEs	Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises
NAI	National Association for Interpretation
OUV	Outstanding Universal Value
SBCI	School of Business and Creative Industries
SKKNI	<i>Standar Kompetensi Kerja Nasional Indonesia</i> (Indonesian National Work Competency Standard)

SPD	Super Priority Destinations
TPA	Theory of Reasoned Action
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
UK	United Kingdom
UN Tourism	United Nations World Tourism Organization
USD	United States Dollar
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UWS	University of the West of Scotland
VOC	<i>Vereenigde Oostindische Compagnie</i> (Dutch East India Company)
WFTGA	World Federation of Tourist Guide Associations
<i>WFTGA</i>	World Federation of Tourist Guide Associations
WHIPIC	International Centre for the Interpretation and Presentation of World Heritage Sites
WHS	World Heritage Sites
WTTC	World Travel & Tourism Council

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and Thesis Rationale

Tour guides play an essential role in shaping how tourists experience and understand cultural, historical, and natural heritage. They act not only as facilitators of information but also as mediators between visitors and the social and cultural contexts of the places they visit (Ballantyne et al., 2009; Weiler & Kim, 2011). In this sense, guides are more than service providers; they are cultural interpreters, storytellers, and interpreters who contribute directly to tourists' perceptions and experiences. This is particularly significant in Indonesia, a vast archipelagic nation composed of more than 17,000 islands where extraordinary cultural and ecological diversity renders heritage interpretation both complex and essential. Tour guides in Indonesia must navigate and communicate this diversity across linguistic, ethnic, and religious lines, offering tourists not only factual information but also insight into the country's deeply rooted cultural traditions.

As cultural and heritage tourism continues to grow globally, tourists are no longer satisfied with surface-level, information-heavy tours. Instead, they increasingly seek experiences that are immersive, authentic, and emotionally engaging (Richards, 2018). These trends place new demands on guides, who must balance technical knowledge with cultural sensitivity, emotional intelligence, and storytelling capabilities. However, traditional tour guide training programmes in Indonesia and in much of the world continue to prioritise formal education models. These programs typically emphasise competencies such as customer service, language proficiency, safety protocols, and basic site knowledge (Cohen, 1985; Weiler & Black, 2015a). While such training provides a necessary foundation, it often fails to address the deeper interpretative,

adaptive, and relational dimensions of guiding, particularly in culturally plural and dynamic settings like Indonesia (Lugosi & Bray, 2008).

Scholars have increasingly drawn attention to the evolving and multifaceted nature of guiding work, highlighting that guides are not merely passive transmitters of information but rather active meaning-makers and cultural brokers (Ham, 1992; Reisinger & Steiner, 2006; Salazar, 2008). Effective interpretation demands more than technical skill where it requires contextually situated knowledge, emotional awareness, and the ability to mediate between multiple worldviews. Yet many institutional and academic approaches continue to prioritise formal, standardised training frameworks that do not fully account for the situated, experiential, and relational aspects of knowledge acquisition in guiding practice.

Informal learning, which occurs outside structured training settings through daily experience, social interaction, and community engagement, plays a particularly vital role in shaping guides' interpretive capacities. In Indonesia, this form of learning holds even greater importance due to the country's long-standing reliance on non-institutional methods of cultural transmission. Much of Indonesia's heritage is sustained not through textbooks or formal curricula but through oral histories, local rituals, storytelling traditions, and communal practices (Geertz, 1960; Sutanto, 2010). In many communities, especially in rural or indigenous areas, knowledge is passed down informally from elders to younger generations, embedding cultural understanding within daily life. For Indonesian tour guides, these informal mechanisms serve as rich sources of tacit, place-based knowledge that can deeply enrich tourist experiences (Bakker, 2007; Arifin & Kusumah, 2015).

Through informal learning, guides develop the ability to interpret heritage not just as a collection of facts, but as a living, evolving set of practices and meanings. Peer learning, community involvement, and lived experience all contribute to guides' capacity to tailor their narratives to different audiences and respond to unexpected situations in real time (Marsick & Watkins, 2001; Weiler & Black, 2015b). This includes knowing when and how to use culturally grounded metaphors, how to respond sensitively to tourist questions, and how to represent local perspectives in ways that are both respectful and engaging. Such learning processes are rarely visible in formal curricula but are essential to the authenticity and impact of heritage interpretation.

By focusing on both formal and informal learning, this research aligns with calls for a more integrated approach to tour guide training—one that incorporates not only structured, formal instruction but also the flexible, context-driven knowledge that guides develop through lived experience and community connections (Ap & Wong, 2001; Weiler & Black, 2015b). This approach is particularly relevant in heritage tourism, where interpretive depth and cultural authenticity are critical for meaningful visitor engagement. Previous research suggests that tourists increasingly seek immersive, authentic experiences that connect them to local histories, values, and perspectives (Reisinger & Steiner, 2006; Cohen & Cohen, 2012). Thus, understanding and integrating informal learning into the professional development of tour guides could enhance the authenticity of tourist experiences, ultimately contributing to more sustainable and culturally sensitive tourism practices (Ham, 1992; Beck & Cable, 2011).

Despite its importance, informal learning remains underexplored in Indonesian tourism scholarship. Much published work focuses on formal education and certification, tourist satisfaction, and destination infrastructure (Oktadiana and Chon, 2017; Kementerian Ketenagakerjaan RI, 2023; Laia and Listyorini, 2023; Hesna, 2023; Nuryanti, 1996). While these studies offer valuable insights into the structural aspects of tourism development, they largely neglect the everyday, informal learning through which guides cultivate interpretive practices and cultural knowledge. This gap is especially notable given the centrality of community-based ways of knowing in Indonesian heritage contexts, where cultural identity is often transmitted through oral traditions, performance, and relational engagement (Fox, 1988; Fox, 2016; UNESCO, 1998).

This thesis addresses this critical research gap by examining how Indonesian tour guides acquire, apply, and transmit informal knowledge in their work. It investigates the ways in which guides blend formal training with experiential, community-rooted learning to produce rich and meaningful interpretations of heritage. In doing so, the research contributes to a more nuanced understanding of professional learning in tourism, offering insights not only for academic theory but also for policy and practice in guide training and certification.

Ultimately, this study argues for a balanced training paradigm that recognises and integrates both formal and informal learning. While formal education provides structure, consistency, and professional standards, informal learning brings adaptability, authenticity, and cultural depth. This dual approach is particularly necessary in contexts like Indonesia, where diverse and localised knowledge systems play a vital role in sustaining cultural identity and enhancing

visitor experiences. By highlighting the value of informal learning, this research contributes to more inclusive, culturally grounded, and effective models of tour guide development in Indonesia and beyond.

1.2 Thesis Aim and Objectives

This thesis critically examines how tour guides in Indonesia informally acquire and utilise knowledge in the crafting narratives. To achieve the aim, a series of research objectives have been identified to support and direct the study. These objectives are as follows:

- To critically explore the processes through which tour guides in Indonesia acquire and integrate knowledge into their professional practice, focusing on the interplay between formal and informal learning frameworks.
- To analyse the methodologies employed by tour guides in constructing narratives that balance authenticity with audience engagement.
- To investigate the effectiveness and adaptability of interpretive tools and techniques used by tour guides to enhance narrative delivery and foster meaningful connections with diverse tourist demographics.
- To explore the socio-cultural dynamics influencing the narrative strategies of tour guides within the context of global and local heritage discourses.

1.3 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study provide significant insights into how informal learning processes impact knowledge acquisition and narrative construction among Indonesian tour guides. While much of the existing literature on tour guiding focuses on formal training, this study highlights the value of informal learning such as peer learning, community engagement, visitor interactions and lived experiences in enriching guides' interpretive skills and fostering authentic storytelling. By investigating how Indonesian tour guides acquire knowledge beyond structured educational or institutionalised settings, this research contributes to a broader understanding of heritage interpretation within tourism studies, particularly within culturally diverse contexts like Indonesia.

From a scholarly perspective, this study addresses a gap in tourism literature by illustrating the importance of informal learning as a complementary approach to formal training. It demonstrates how social constructivist theory can be applied to tour guiding, showing that

knowledge in this field is dynamically shaped through social interactions and contextual experiences rather than being solely rooted in formal education. This perspective aligns with calls for more integrative training models in tourism that support not only factual knowledge but also cultural sensitivity and adaptability.

This study offers practical recommendations for tourism stakeholders. Integrating informal learning within training frameworks can better equip tour guides to handle the unique cultural and historical landscapes they interpret. Such integration can support the preservation of Indonesia's intangible heritage by encouraging guides to weave local insights, traditional knowledge, and communal values into their narratives. This study's findings advocate a training programme that empowers guides as cultural mediators, ultimately enhancing the visitor experience and supporting heritage tourism development in Indonesia.

1.4 Study Area of the Thesis

As an archipelagic nation with over 17,000 islands, Indonesia represents a cultural and ecological tapestry that uniquely positions it within the global heritage tourism market. The country's rich heritage is not only tied to its tangible assets, such as ancient temples, historical architecture, and UNESCO-listed sites, but also to its diverse intangible cultural heritage, which includes local customs, languages, rituals, folklore, and traditional knowledge systems (UNESCO, 2003). Indonesia's heritage is deeply rooted in its indigenous communities and local traditions, presenting a multi-layered cultural landscape that appeals to tourists seeking authentic, immersive experiences. This rich cultural diversity aligns with global heritage tourism trends, which increasingly emphasise the value of preserving and showcasing local cultures, historical narratives, and community identities (Timothy & Boyd, 2006).

The rise of heritage tourism in Indonesia is closely connected to the country's broader tourism development strategy, which recognises tourism as a key driver of economic growth (OECD, 2024). As a strategic sector, tourism has been prioritised to diversify Indonesia's economy, creating employment and improving local livelihoods, particularly in areas with significant cultural and environmental assets. The Indonesian Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy has championed heritage tourism, particularly in culturally significant regions such as Yogyakarta, Bali, and Jakarta. These regions attract millions of visitors annually, drawn by renowned sites like Borobudur and Prambanan temples—both UNESCO World Heritage Sites—which embody Indonesia's ancient architectural achievements and spiritual heritage.

(Hitchcock, King and Parnwell, 2010). This approach is in line with the global shift in tourism toward experiences that combine leisure with education, where tourists seek both entertainment and meaningful engagement with local cultures (Pine and Gilmore, 1999).

Heritage tourism development in Indonesia has necessitated a professionalised approach to tour guiding, given the critical role guides play as cultural interpreters and ambassadors. In line with ASEAN's tourism competency standards, Indonesia has implemented a certification and formal training programme for tour guides to ensure that they meet quality and service standards in tourism. (ASEAN, 2018). However, these formal training programmes have often been critiqued for their rigid curricula, which focus on factual content delivery, customer service skills, and language proficiency, often at the expense of interpretive depth and cultural authenticity (Cohen, 1985; Ap and Wong, 2001).

Heritage tourism demands more than essential knowledge transfer; it requires guides who can act as “cultural mediators,” offering insights that deepen tourists' engagement with heritage sites by revealing the cultural, historical, and social contexts surrounding them (Salazar, 2008). This expectation aligns with the principles of heritage interpretation, where guides do not merely convey information but engage tourists in a meaningful exploration of place, memory, and identity (Ham, 1992; Beck and Cable, 2011). Scholars argue that for tour guiding to be effective in heritage tourism, it must foster a connection between visitors and the cultural heritage of a destination, a goal that often involves informal learning processes and personal insights that transcend standardised training (Timothy and Boyd, 2006; Reisinger and Steiner, 2008; Weiler and Black, 2015b).

Heritage interpretation is increasingly recognised as a vital component of meaningful tourism experiences in Indonesia. As outlined by Ham (1992), this approach involves communicating deeper meanings and connections, striving to forge an emotional and intellectual bond between tourists and the places they visit. Effective heritage interpretation, as supported by Weiler and Ham (2002) and Beck and Cable (2011), encourages guides to go beyond surface-level descriptions, fostering an environment where tourists can engage deeply with local customs, history, and values. Given Indonesia's rich multicultural backdrop, where diverse cultural symbols, rituals, and stories are interwoven, enhancing interpretative skills can significantly elevate the tourist experience. By prioritising these aspects of heritage interpretation, Indonesia can better position itself as a leader in sustainable and meaningful heritage tourism. This approach will not only satisfy the growing demand for authentic and immersive experiences

among global travellers but also contribute to the preservation of its cultural heritage and the empowerment of local communities.

1.5 Research Approach

This study employed a qualitative research design grounded in a social constructivist paradigm, providing exploratory insights into knowledge acquisition and heritage interpretation. A comprehensive literature review identified significant gaps, particularly regarding the informal learning processes that tour guides use to craft and convey authentic narratives. These gaps informed the research questions and guided the choice of semi-structured interviews as the primary data collection method. A total of 36 interviews were conducted with tour guides, and trainers, across three Indonesian cities—Jakarta, Bandung, and Yogyakarta. All interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim. Additional narrative documents provided by trainers were used to support data triangulation.

The data were analysed using thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's (2021) six-step process. This method was employed to identify patterns, interpret themes, and provide a rich, detailed understanding of the qualitative data. The coded extracts were further examined in relation to the research questions and existing literature. This analysis explored how tour guides integrate informal learning from community engagement, peer interactions, and personal experiences to enhance their interpretive practices.

1.6 Structure of the Thesis

This study is organised into seven chapters, beginning with this introductory chapter. The first chapter provides an overview of the research background and context, establishing the aim and objectives of the study. It also outlines the theoretical foundation and research approach and introduces the case study area.

Chapter two, grounds the study conceptually and is organised into six parts. It first treats heritage as a negotiated field, tracing the shift from object-centred charters to locally interpreted, practice-based understandings. It then shows how destination imaging and the Authorised Heritage Discourse, alongside orientalism/self-orientalism, preconfigure what visitors see and expect. A fuller account of authenticity follows, moving from essentialist tests to procedural/performative judgments relevant to live guiding. The chapter next foregrounds

embodiment and sensory engagement, explaining how attention, affect and memory are shaped through brief, consent-aware cues. Interpretation is then developed as communicative and narrative craft (TORE: thematic, organised, relevant, enjoyable), supported by dialogue and ethical transparency. Finally, it advances social capital and informal learning as the mechanisms that furnish guides with sources, permissions and techniques. Across these sections, the guide is positioned as an active cultural agent and critical mediator who reconciles market logics, institutional frames and community voice, with closing implications for practice.

Chapter three presents the dynamics of heritage tourism in Indonesia and is organised into five sections. It first situates Indonesia's cultural landscape historically, Hindu-Buddhist to Islamic, colonial and post-independence, showing how layered pasts shape today's sites and policies. It then examines how global frameworks amplify visibility while pressuring local meanings, requiring a balance between international criteria and community narratives. The chapter next centres tour guides as cultural interpreters who safeguard nuance, translate situated values and keep local voice present in visitor experience. It further evaluates digital transformation such and argues for blended models where technology extends reach but human mediation secures depth, context and ethics. Finally, it grounds the argument in practice, from mandated guided visits in museums to community-embedded walking tours, to show how interpretation manages flow, education and authenticity on site. Across these sections, the chapter positions Indonesia to integrate global recognition with local agency, with guides as critical mediators of sustainable, credible heritage tourism.

Chapter four outlines the methodological framework guiding this study, beginning with the research's philosophical foundations, particularly its alignment with a social constructivist paradigm. This chapter discusses how this paradigm informs the qualitative approach, which centres on semi-structured interviews and document analysis to investigate knowledge acquisition, heritage interpretation, and informal learning among tour guides. The chapter elaborates on the participants' selection process, data collection methods, and thematic analysis techniques used, including detailed steps to ensure methodological rigour. The chapter also considers ethical considerations and the author's reflexive positioning as both an insider and outsider in the research setting, recognising potential biases and outlining measures to uphold trustworthiness.

Chapter five presents and interprets the findings related to knowledge acquisition and narrative construction in Indonesian tour guiding, focusing on the role of informal learning. It begins with analysing formal training structures, including certification and institutional requirements, which serve as foundational knowledge for guides. The discussion then shifts to the informal learning processes that guide narrative development, encompassing peer interactions, mentorship, and community engagement. Drawing on these findings, the chapter demonstrates how informal learning allows guides to enrich their narratives with culturally resonant, authentic content that reflects local heritage and customs. Each major section presents findings followed by an analysis, highlighting the transformative impact of informal learning in shaping guides as cultural interpreters.

Chapter six examines the complex process of crafting and delivering interpretive narratives in Indonesian tour guides. It begins by exploring the role of informal learning and social constructivist approaches that guide use to shape culturally resonant stories, drawing on their own lived experiences, community engagement, and local knowledge. The chapter highlights the ways guides use these insights to personalise narratives, moving beyond formal training to provide tourists with authentic, culturally embedded experiences. The chapter continues with an in-depth discussion of the interpretive tools and techniques that guides employ to engage tourists.

Chapter seven summarises the key findings from this study on informal learning and narrative construction processes among Indonesian tour guides. The conclusions highlight the significance of informal knowledge—acquired through community engagement, peer networks, and lived experiences—in shaping culturally resonant narratives that go beyond the limitations of formal training. This study contributes to knowledge in heritage interpretation, filling a gap in understanding how informal learning supports authentic, immersive tourist experiences. The chapter also presents practical recommendations, advocating for an integrated approach to tour guide training that combines formal instruction with experiential, community based learning to capture Indonesia’s cultural diversity better. Limitations of the study are discussed, such as sample representation and the researcher’s dual role as both insider and outsider, with suggestions for refining these aspects in future research. Finally, the chapter concludes with reflections on the research journey and the transformative potential of informal learning in empowering tour guides as cultural ambassadors.

CHAPTER 2

CONSTRUCTING HERITAGE NARRATIVES

This chapter provides a critical synthesis of the scholarship that informs the study and locates it within the wider field. It sets out the conceptual grounds on which the thesis proceeds, identifies where prior research is limited, and clarifies the theoretical and methodological framing that underpins the analysis that follows.

The chapter is organised into six sections. First, it considers heritage as a negotiated construct, moving beyond object-centred views to emphasise practice, use, and value in context. Second, it examines how destination imaging and related authorised discourses, including orientalism and self-orientalism, pre-configure what is presented to, and expected by, visitors. Third, it develops a fuller account of authenticity, bringing classical treatments into dialogue with procedural and performative understandings relevant to live guiding. Fourth, it expands the role of sensory engagement, outlining how attention, affect, and memory are shaped by embodied, multi-sensory encounters and by interpretive scaffolds such as maps, then-and-now photographs, and digital aids. Fifth, it treats interpretation as communicative and narrative practice that translates information into meaning through themes, dialogue, and situated ethical judgement. Sixth, it foregrounds social capital and informal learning as the mechanisms through which guides mediate between externally circulated images and locally grounded understandings. The chapter closes by restating the contribution and indicating implications for practice.

2.1 Heritage as a Contested Field

Heritage has shifted from a bounded inventory of valued objects to a set of practices through which communities, professions and institutions make claims on the past. Early international charters codified a material focus and the language of fabric, integrity and expert care, visible

in the Venice Charter and the 1972 World Heritage Convention. Subsequent developments widened what counts. The Burra Charter articulated social and spiritual values alongside historical and aesthetic ones. The Nara Document on Authenticity recognised that criteria such as use, tradition, setting and “spirit and feeling” are interpreted locally. UNESCO’s 2003 Convention further consolidated the move by defining intangible cultural heritage as skills, expressions and knowledge recognised by communities themselves. Together, these shifts mark a turn from essence to procedure and from universal tests to situated judgements.

Comparative research demonstrates that the broadening of what counts as heritage is not a simple East–West contrast but an ongoing hybridisation. The Nara Document helped normalise locally interpreted criteria and the legitimacy of living practices, drawing in part on Asian conservation philosophies that accept material renewal and prioritise continuity of use and tradition (ICOMOS, 1994; Jokilehto, 1999; Munjeri, 2004). Scholarship on Asia documents how doctrines of impermanence and ritual maintenance sit alongside care for fabric, which has, in turn, influenced international thinking about authenticity and value (Winter, 2014; Chapagain, 2016; Sandholz, 2017). At the same time, European and North American practice increasingly recognises community voice, intangible dimensions and contemporary uses as integral to significance rather than as add-ons (Smith and Waterton, 2009; Harrison, 2013). Tourism and conservation now operate within mixed regimes in which tangible and intangible values interdepend. A single place may be safeguarded for its material fabric, its performative life and its social meanings, and those values are negotiated across publics rather than discovered once and for all. Case work on cross-cultural settings makes this visible, for example collaborative arrangements at Angkor, or urban heritage programmes in Singapore, Macau and Tianjin that fold ritual practice and community use into building-focused schemes (Gravari-Barbas and Poulot, 2021; Wong, McKercher and Li, 2016a; Wong, McKercher and Li, 2016b; Gravari-Barbas, Guinand and Lu, 2021).

The historical broadening of heritage, from a fabric-centred charter tradition to locally interpreted criteria and recognition of intangible practice, widens what can count, but it also brings the politics of selection into view. Once authenticity rests on procedures and permissions rather than on intrinsic properties alone, authority is negotiated among institutions, professions and publics with unequal influence. From this vantage point, heritage is best approached as a contested field.

Heritage is widely treated as a negotiated social process rather than a stable stock of valued objects. Meanings are assembled and circulated in practice, they are argued over, and they change as publics and circumstances change. This shift from things to practices is now foundational in critical heritage studies, where heritage is described as something people do rather than something that simply is (Harvey, 2001; Smith, 2006). Once practice is foregrounded, the focus moves from intrinsic properties to the procedures, relations, and settings that sustain particular claims about the past. Those procedures are never neutral, because selection and presentation take place within fields of power that advantage some ways of knowing over others (Harrison, 2013; Waterton and Smith, 2010).

A first site of contestation concerns authorisation. The Authorised Heritage Discourse prioritises expert canons, monumental and architectural forms, and conservationist vocabularies that stabilise certain narratives as common sense while marginalising vernacular histories, lived experience and intangible practice (Smith, 2006). Tunbridge and Ashworth's account of dissonant heritage argues that conflict is structural, since the same places bear incompatible meanings for groups with divergent identities and interests (Tunbridge and Ashworth, 1996). Related work traces how registers, criteria and planning regimes distribute voice and value unevenly across social groups and spatial scales (Graham, Ashworth and Tunbridge, 2000; Pendlebury, 2009). There is no simple consensus. Authors close to policy argue that authorised systems can be widened through participatory processes and revised criteria without sacrificing the benefits expert regimes bring for conservation and legal certainty (Jokilehto, 1999; Labadi, 2013). Critical scholars reply that participation often arrives after evidential styles are set, leaving communities to supply colour rather than grounds (Smith and Waterton, 2009; DeSilvey, 2017).

Representation is a second site of dispute. Postcolonial analyses explain how durable ways of seeing are produced. Orientalism shows the long history through which non-Western peoples and places were arranged as objects of knowledge and as sites of difference and distance (Said, 1978). The tourist gaze extends this to contemporary mobility by showing how routes, sightlines, captions and promotional circuits train audiences to recognise some elements as sights and to overlook others (Urry, 1978; Urry and Larsen, 2011). These frames now interlock with digital platforms. Platform logics and algorithmic ranking tend to reward repeatable shots and templated captions, narrowing what is easily shown and discouraging nuance that travels poorly as quick content (Leaver, Highfield and Abidin, 2020; Abidin, 2016).

Voice and permission form a third line of contestation. Institutional regimes shape who can speak for the past in public and under what conditions. National registers, UNESCO processes and site policies direct resources and attention, often privileging the monumental and tangible over the vernacular and intangible, or consensus stories over contested ones (Labadi, 2013; Meskell, 2018). Many communities also treat permission as part of knowing. Standing to recount a story may depend on role, kinship, season or place; the right to show an image or repeat a song can be conditional. Museum and Indigenous-studies literatures therefore tie credibility to provenance, consent, and scope rather than to access alone (Peers and Brown, 2003; Christen, 2012). This sits in tension with older object-centred approaches that sought authenticity primarily in material fabric or age (Lowenthal, 1998). In practice, authorised systems remain important for protection, yet there is growing recognition that speaking rights and cultural protocols are elements of evidential warrant (Waterton and Smith, 2010; Harrison, 2013).

Comparative research shows that these debates do not reduce to an East–West divide. Hybridisation is common. Asian conservation philosophies that accept renewal and prioritise continuity of use have influenced international thinking, as in the Nara Document on Authenticity, which broadened criteria to include form, function, tradition and spirit alongside material fabric (ICOMOS, 1994; Jokilehto, 1999). European and North American practice has increasingly acknowledged living traditions and community voice in both tangible and intangible domains (Kurin, 2004; Smith and Waterton, 2009). Japan’s Ise Shrine illustrates how periodic rebuilding can coexist with strong claims to authenticity when the criterion is faithful transmission of craft and ritual rather than untouched fabric (Winter, 2014). In China, debates over urban renewal reveal conflicts between branding, legal frameworks, and neighbourhood life, with outcomes that vary by city and by the coalitions assembled (Ren, 2014; Hsing, 2010). In the Middle East and North Africa, UNESCO inscriptions have sometimes amplified national narratives at the expense of minorities, prompting calls for rights-based governance (Meskell, 2018). Across the Pacific, indigenous policy has pressed institutions to accept that consent and restricted circulation may be integral to responsible access (Christen, 2012).

Commodification is another long-running controversy, and it links directly to the wider politics of authorisation and display. Critics argue that market logics flatten complexity, producing “staged authenticity,” “Disneyfication” and “McDonaldisation” that narrow urban pasts to a

few marketable traits and reward spectacle over care (MacCannell, 1999; Hewison, 1987; Bryman, 1999; Ritzer, 2011). Others counter that commodification can add layers of meaning and expand publics when translation is accountable and benefits are shared (Cohen, 1988; Macleod, 2006; Graham, Ashworth and Tunbridge, 2016). In short, the fault line is not the presence of markets per se, but the terms on which selection and explanation are governed.

This dispute flows into the authenticity debate, which crystallises the broader shift from essence to procedure. Essentialist tests such as originality, age, intact fabric that remain important in architectural conservation, yet they cannot settle most public encounters (Lowenthal, 1998; Jokilehto, 1999). Constructivist and experience-centred accounts instead treat authenticity as something produced in interaction: plausibility, care and fit are judged as stories are tethered to a clear theme, supported with visible reasons, and enacted with calibrated affect and dialogue (Bruner, 1994; Wang, 1999; Reisinger and Steiner, 2006). The disagreement, then, concerns anchor points. Some worry that a fully constructivist view detaches practice from material reference (Jokilehto, 1999), others argue that procedural clarity can hold both together by showing provenance and consent alongside material evidence so audiences see how claims are made and under what conditions they may be shared (Silverman, 2011; Waterton and Smith, 2010).

These questions of procedure and benefit are intensified by global governance. UNESCO inscriptions can bring protection and resources, while also reordering national priorities and local economies (Labadi, 2013; Meskell, 2018). Heritage-led city-centre regeneration, for example, may couple preservation gains with displacement and contested calculations of social value (Jones and Varley, 1999; Pendlebury, 2009). In sub-Saharan Africa, community-based projects show how local stewardship and tourism can align under supportive institutions, yet they also reveal fragility when donor priorities shift (Ndoro and Pwiti, 2001; Chirikure and Pwiti, 2008). In Eastern Europe, the politics of remembering twentieth-century violence make heritage a site of open contest among municipal, national and transnational actors (Light and Young, 2010). In each case, the same issue recurs: who sets the terms of recognition, and with what social consequences.

The urban arena condenses these tensions at street level. Gentrification and adaptive reuse are praised for saving fabric and attracting investment, but criticised for sanitising labour histories and displacing residents (Zukin, 2010; Colomb and Novy, 2016). Decisions about industrial heritage encode judgements about class, gender, and work that are rarely neutral (Edwards and

Llurdés i Coit, 1996; Smith, 2006). Dark-heritage studies press the ethical edge: how atrocity sites should be presented, to whom, and with what affective register, so that learning is possible without exploitation. What is contested is not only which artefacts survive but whose pride or suffering can be shown, and what forms of silence enable coexistence (Ashworth and Hartmann, 2005; Logan and Reeves, 2009).

Finally, user-generated platforms assemble alternative archives and circulate counter-stories that can challenge official framings, yet platform logics also reward repeatable visuals and templated captions, entrenching caricatures through repetition (Highfield, 2016; Mkono, 2020). As heritage professionals work with community-produced datasets, vernacular photographs and short-form video—sources that carry their own claims to authenticity—the issue circles back to procedure: warrant, credit and consent must be established explicitly when both evidence and audiences are platformed (Giaccardi, 2012; Ridge, 2014).

Across these threads, what is contested is clear. It is the right to define significance, to speak for the past in public, to set the criteria by which claims are judged, and to distribute the benefits and harms that follow from recognition and use. Proponents of authorised regimes stress conservation efficacy, legal clarity and common standards; critics foreground the politics of categorisation, exclusions embedded in expert languages and the need to treat permission and protocol as part of knowledge. Market-oriented writers point to the capacity of tourism to mobilise resources and sustain sites; opponents warn of simplification, displacement and the erosion of minority claims. Constructivists describe authenticity as emergent in interaction; essentialists worry that this can unmoor practice from material anchors. Regional studies show that resolutions vary with history, governance and local coalitions.

Two consequences follow for the remainder of the chapter. The review concentrates on the mechanisms that organise contestation such as authorisation, perceptual pre-configuration through media and gaze, and voice and permission within institutional and community regimes and then turns to the communicative and ethical craft through which credible accounts are built under those conditions. The working position that carries forward is that authenticity is an outcome of good practice. It appears when claims are well grounded, permission to speak is clear, staging fits place and audience, and people leave with a story they can reasonably tell again (ICOMOS, 1994; Bruner, 1994; Reisinger and Steiner, 2006; Falk and Dierking, 2013).

2.2 Destination Imaging, Authorised Discourses and Market Preconfiguration

Tourism rarely encounters places in a vacuum. Well before arrival, destinations are rendered legible through circulating repertoires of images, slogans and narratives that move across ministries, destination management organisations, travel media and user platforms. Classic work on destination image shows how expectations are built from the interplay of organic sources, induced promotion and autonomous media, sedimenting cues that visitors recognise and operators reproduce (Gartner, 1993; Jenkins, 2003). Place-branding research adds that branding is not only descriptive but constitutive: it selects and repeats attributes until they stabilise as common sense, with investment and policy following suit (Kavaratzis and Ashworth, 2005; Anholt, 2007). In heritage tourism, such branding practices operationalise prior authorisations by converting registers, curatorial scripts and media conventions into routinised visual and narrative assets.

In practice, destination management teams build libraries of approved photos and captions. These libraries concentrate on a small set of familiar scenes such as a temple at sunrise, an artisan at work or a rehearsed ritual, and the same scenes are then reused in brochures, on platforms and on-site panels (Jenkins, 2003; Kavaratzis and Ashworth, 2005). As these cues settle, they pre-allocate attention and compress narrative options for guides. The effect does not rest on falsehoods so much as on ease of reproduction: familiar images are the easiest to stage and the safest to sell (MacCannell, 1999; Urry, 2002). Research on tourism imaginaries shows that these frames are co-produced across agencies, firms, venues and visitors, creating durable storylines that are easy to mobilise and difficult to complicate (Salazar, 2012).

Postcolonial scholarship helps to explain how particular visual and textual regimes take hold. The Authorised Heritage Discourse (AHD) privileges expert canons, monumental forms and a limited range of affect, which then becomes a template for what counts as “heritage” in brochures and on platforms (Smith, 2006). Orientalism offers familiar signs of otherness, while self-orientalism describes local actors leaning into externally recognisable tropes to secure visibility and advantage in the market (Said, 1978; Ooi, 2003; Salazar, 2012; Wei, Qian and Sun, 2018; Kobayashi, Jackson and Sam, 2019). The result is rarely top-down imposition alone. It is a co-production in which certain angles and captions are reinforced because they travel easily and draw approval (Jenkins, 2003; Urry and Larsen, 2011). The tourist gaze remains a concise way to describe how attention is organised within this infrastructure of signs. In current

media circuits, platforms intensify the effect through algorithmic amplification that rewards repeatable images and discourages nuance (Urry, 2002; Mkono, 2020).

Debates on commodification sit within this broader picture. Critics contend that market logics can flatten complexity, producing “staged authenticity” or “bogus history,” and narrowing urban pasts to a few marketable traits (MacCannell, 1999; Hewison, 2023; Kearns and Philo, 1993; Ashworth and Tunbridge, 2000; Gotham, 2007). Others describe “Disneyfication” or “McDonaldisation” when spectacle and standardisation dominate (Choay, 2001; McIntosh and Prentice, 1999; Breathnach, 2006). A parallel strand treats heritage as cultural and economic capital and argues that commodification can add layers of meaning and widen publics when translation is carefully managed (Cohen, 1988; Macleod, 2006; Graham, Ashworth and Tunbridge, 2016). The question is therefore less whether markets are present than the terms on which heritage is selected, staged and explained.

For guides, this becomes a practical problem rather than a binary for or against markets. Branding and AHD narrow what is recognised as real while also expanding audiences. Under these conditions the quality of interpretation is seen in whether familiar images are situated within sourced, situated accounts that visitors can retell with reasons. In that sense, destination imaging and AHD are not background noise but conditions of practice. They shape what will be noticed, what will be asked for and what will count as convincing on site.

Commodification analysis clarifies the stakes. Turning culture into product is not inherently corrosive, yet it is never neutral. Formats trim representations, schedules time performances and narratives are calibrated to price and risk (Cohen, 1988; Greenwood, 1989). The result is a tension between legibility and complexity: operators prefer clear promises, sites prefer managerial simplicity and visitors arrive with pre-formed heuristics. The interpretive task is to work within these constraints without capitulating to them. Research on interpretation points to a workable route. A clear theme disciplines selection so that even when a tour acknowledges the recognisable image, it can reposition that image within a broader line of argument where organisation structures movement from the known to the less familiar; relevance connects the account to visitor repertoires; and enjoyment sustains the attention that understanding requires (Tilden, 1957; Ham, 1992; Beck and Cable, 2011). In short, the aim is not to negate destination scripts but to place them in context so that more than recognition travels.

These preconfigurations matter for interpretation. They set expectations and incentives before any guide speaks. Visitors often arrive with stock photos and ready-made captions already in mind. Under these conditions, the task of interpretation is to acknowledge recognition and then thicken it with situated explanation. Research in interpretation emphasises that meaning does not travel by facts alone; it is organised through theme, sequence, relevance and enjoyment, with carefully chosen media used sparingly to mark turns in the argument (Tilden, 1957; Ham, 2016; Beck and Cable, 2011). Small, well-placed techniques can reposition familiar views without shaming audiences for what they do not know: an aligned then-and-now image that makes regulation or repair visible; a different vantage point that swaps foreground and background; a short tactile or auditory cue that opens a story about labour, authority or etiquette. Such moves work when they are tied to a clear theme and when ethical limits are named, especially where material is sacred, sensitive or contested.

The literature cautions against treating authorised and market frames as uniform. They are patterned yet porous, and practitioners often work in the seams. Studies show local actors juxtaposing promoted vistas with alternative sightlines, annotating emblematic objects with lineages of labour and conflict, or pairing expected rituals with accounts of regulation and change (Salazar, 2012; Weiler and Black, 2015). At the same time, authorisation proceeds through images, labels and lists that confer status and order attention, from national registers to UNESCO inscriptions. These instruments support conservation and access, yet they also create hierarchies that privilege monumental over vernacular, tangible over intangible, and consensual over contested pasts (Smith, 2006). Authorised scripts then travel into brochures and briefings and become the easiest narratives to reproduce, while unrati ed or difficult stories demand additional grounds that policy and branding do not always recognise.

These conditions shape what is feasible on site. Where market logics and authorisation align, interpretive scripts tend to calcify. Where they diverge, guides face the practical problem of reconciling visitor expectations with local claims to meaning. Progress typically depends on resources that live guiding can mobilise: access to elders and archives, peer-tested stories, permission to address sensitive topics and practice environments in which techniques can be tried and refined. Such resources make it possible to widen the interpretive field without overstating certainty, and to attach multiple, defensible grounds to accounts that sit outside the promotional template.

Several strands of research identify techniques that help reposition meaning within market constraints. Visual scaffolds such as then-and-now photographs, annotated maps, archival images and simple diagrams place circulating images in historical and social context and make continuities and breaks explicit (Falk and Dierking, 2013). Dialogic methods draw out the assumptions visitors bring and allow small-scale negotiation of meaning. Carefully chosen questions and analogies connect prior images to situated detail without shaming audiences (Beck and Cable, 2011). Sensory affordances, tied to a clear theme and used with consent and cultural care, focus attention and support encoding so that unfamiliar claims are more likely to be remembered (Falk and Dierking, 2013). Ethical calibration runs through these practices. Where material is sacred, sensitive or contested, responsible interpretation may slow the pace, bracket topics or refuse certain forms of access. In such moments, protocols form part of meaning-making rather than an external limit.

The literature suggests that authorised and market frames are neither uniform nor total. They are patterned yet porous, and practitioners often work in the seams (Smith, 2006; Salazar, 2012). Guides may juxtapose a promoted vista with an alternative vantage point that reorders foreground and background, annotate a celebrated object with lineages of labour, conflict or migration, or pair an expected ritual with accounts of regulation and recent change (Edensor, 2001; Weiler and Black, 2015). Such manoeuvres do not dissolve power, but they thicken the interpretive field with plural warrants (Waterton and Smith, 2010; Harrison, 2013). They also rely on resources that frequently sit outside formal curricula such as access to elders and archives, peer-tested stories, permissions to address difficult topics, and a practised sense of when consent is needed and when refusal is appropriate—resources that are social as much as textual and that circulate unevenly (Kirshenblatt-Gimblett, 1998; Weiler and Black, 2015). This uneven circulation is taken up later when informal learning and social capital are theorised as the mechanism that sustains interpretive authority.

In this view, destination imaging and authorised discourse are conditions of practice, not background noise. They set expectations, allocate attention and shape incentives before any encounter. The task of interpretation is to work with these conditions by applying Ham's TORE principles—thematic, organised, relevant and enjoyable—to move audiences from recognition to understanding, while using dialogue and consent-aware sensory cues to support attention and memory (Ham, 1992; Ham, 2016; Beck and Cable, 2011; Falk and Dierking, 2013). The next sections examine the craft principles that enable this work and the informal learning

networks through which knowledge and permission circulate. The empirical chapters then show these moves in practice as guides acknowledge stock images, test audience assumptions and reframe encounters with warranted, situated narratives.

2.3 Interpretation as Communicative and Narrative Practice

Interpretation is treated here as a communicative craft that turns information into meaning for particular audiences in particular settings. The genealogy is well known. Enos Mills (1920) framed interpretation in early nature guiding as more than explanation; Tilden (2007) consolidated that position by insisting that interpretation “relate” material to visitors’ experience and that its aim is provocation rather than instruction (Tilden, 2007; Brochu and Merriman, 2015).

Ham gives this tradition an operational centre. Effective interpretation is thematic, organised, relevant and enjoyable (TORE). The theme is a defensible message rather than a topic. It states what the encounter is about and what claim is being advanced, and it functions as a criterion for inclusion and exclusion. In practice a working theme reduces the temptation to list interesting facts and instead selects a few elements that carry the line of reasoning. Studies of programme planning and field delivery repeatedly find that a clear thematic statement improves focus for both interpreter and audience (Ham, 1992; Ham, 2016; Beck and Cable, 2011). Evaluations of themed programmes in protected areas and historic sites report higher comprehension, recall, and application than topic-led talks because visitors can locate each detail within an explicit claim (Tarlton and Ward, 2006; Powell and Ham, 2008).

Organisation then sequences material so that the argument is followable. Common routes include moving from the familiar to the less familiar, from part to whole, or from a concrete case to the general idea it illustrates. Organisation also covers pacing and the timing of brief aids, so that small “turns” in the narrative are marked and the group is kept together cognitively (Ham, 1992; Beck and Cable, 2011). Field applications show that simple, signposted structures—problem–evidence–implication, or now–then–now—improve question quality and recall, especially with mixed-age groups (Tarlton and Ward, 2006). In invasive-species communication at Cumberland Island, a thematically structured sequence that moved from a familiar plant to ecological impact to visitor action produced better understanding than unstructured fact lists while avoiding alarmism (Sharp et al., 2012).

Relevance links the theme to visitor repertoires and motives. It is created through short checks, analogy, example and contrast rather than assumed a priori. Analogy maps unfamiliar material onto existing schemas; contrast unsettles an expectation and opens space for reframing; brief prompts surface what people already think they know so that discrepancies can be worked with rather than ignored (Tilden, 1957; Beck and Cable, 2011; Ham, 2016). Applied studies echo this. Thematic guiding in Sarawak National Parks used quick audience checks and locally grounded analogies to connect conservation messages to everyday practices, producing measurable shifts in intention and self-reported understanding (Amin, Chan and Omar, 2014). Visitor-studies syntheses similarly show that when new information is explicitly tied to prior knowledge, encoding and later retrieval improve (Falk and Dierking, 2013; Bitgood, 2013).

Enjoyment names the conditions that sustain attention without displacing meaning. It covers clarity of voice, variety in delivery, appropriate opportunities to participate and emotional salience that serves the theme (Beck and Cable, 2011; Falk and Dierking, 2013). Enjoyment is not a separate goal but a resource for cognition: moments that are affectively marked are more likely to be remembered, provided they are tethered to the claim being advanced. Programme evaluations report that brief, well-timed inserts—a single image, a short handling of a replica, a concise story with a point—raise engagement and aid recall more effectively than long diversions or entertainment that is detached from the argument (Falk and Dierking, 2013; Bitgood, 2013).

On this view, planning is less an inventory of facts and more the disciplined choice of the few elements that drive the theme forward, arranged in a sequence that visitors can follow, connected to what they already know, and delivered in a way that keeps attention steady. Case work from historic sites and parks shows that programmes which make the TORE elements explicit in planning templates and briefing sheets produce more consistent visitor outcomes than ad-hoc talks, while giving interpreters room to adapt in delivery (Clark et al., 2011; Sharp et al., 2012; Amin, Chan and Omar, 2014). The approach is not without limits—strong themes can be over-narrow, and enjoyment can slide into display—but the balance of evidence suggests that TORE provides a reliable spine for live interpretation when it is coupled with dialogic checks and ethical clarity about sources, permissions and limits (Ham, 2016; Beck and Cable, 2011; Weiler and Black, 2015).

Audience research adds a dialogic inflection to this craft. Visitors do not arrive as blank recipients; they bring expectations formed by prior experience, promotion, and media, which

shape what is noticed and valued (Falk and Dierking, 2013; Packer and Ballantyne, 2016). Dialogic interpretation works with those starting points through quick checks, prompts, and follow-up questions that surface assumptions and open small negotiations of meaning between guide and audience (Ham, 2016; Weiler and Black, 2015). Such exchanges act as framing devices: they surface visitors' existing preferences and repertoires and align the programme's theme so that new claims connect to what people already know (Pekarik et al., 2014). Participatory techniques—brief voting, object handling with guided questions, or inviting alternative readings—serve the same purpose by distributing voice while keeping the line of reasoning visible (Simon, 2010). The effect is pragmatic: dialogue does not replace structure; it tests where the audience is, connects new claims to prior frames, and increases the chance that the account will be understood and later retold (Falk and Dierking, 2013).

A storyline with a clear arc, a steady point of view and explicit reasons for belief helps audiences make sense of sequence and cause, and it gives them a form they can later retell. In tourism, performances unfold within scripts, roles and regulated spaces, yet there is room for improvisation inside those constraints; guides work with this latitude to pace scenes, manage turns and keep a group together (Edensor, 2001). Practically, narrative work involves framing a question, staging a series of small reveals and returning to the theme at each step. Short, situated readings of material culture or the built environment can anchor a claim when they name the features being read and the limits of generalisation. Tool marks, joints or repairs can support an account of technique or chronology when the interpreter also states what remains uncertain or contested (Prown, 1982; Beck and Cable, 2011).

Building on this scaffolding, certain devices move the story. Analogy maps unfamiliar material onto existing schemas so the new claim has somewhere to land; contrast unsettles an expectation and opens space for a reframe when a familiar view is incomplete or misleading (Ham, 1992; Ham, 2016). Signposting keeps the thread visible. Simple markers such as “first look closely,” “now step back” and “notice how this changes the picture” indicate where the group is in the argument and why a detail matters. Brief vignettes can make a process visible without drifting into anecdote when they end with a sentence that ties the episode back to the theme.

A consistent narrative voice signals stance and responsibility, especially where topics are sensitive. Clear handling of time links present surfaces to prior decisions and future consequences, for example a now–then–now sequence that moves from an observed feature to

its origin and back to current regulation or use. Audience research aligns with this practice, showing that people follow and remember more when temporal and causal relations are explicit and when moments of emotion serve the argument rather than replace it (Beck and Cable, 2011; Falk and Dierking, 2013).

Credibility is maintained by keeping evidence visible inside the story. Stating what is being inferred from what prevents narrative from sliding into performance. Naming the source of an image, the scope of a testimony or the reason for a limit keeps trust with the guide rather than with charisma alone (Beck and Cable, 2011; Silverman, 2011). On this view, analogy, contrast, close looking and careful sequencing are not decorative rhetoric. They are working tools for thinking with an audience so that recognition becomes understanding and the account can be carried forward in retellings (Tilden, 1957; Ham, 2016).

With these narrative devices in place, two guardrails follow. First, media should support rather than dominate. Visuals and other aids are most effective when brief, legible and tied to a sentence that states the point; long slideshows or frequent device-switching fragment attention (Beck and Cable, 2011; Falk and Dierking, 2013). Second, credibility depends on plain ethical grounding. Where knowledge is sensitive or contested, audiences trust accounts that make sources visible, acknowledge uncertainty and explain limits or refusals (Smith, 2006; Silverman, 2011; Weiler and Black, 2015). On site, provenance, consent and scope matter as much as the number of facts recalled.

Outcomes are often assessed through satisfaction, yet satisfaction is a weak indicator of interpretive quality. Visitor studies link clear themes, structured progression and emotionally salient cues to stronger encoding and later recall, as well as selective intentions such as revisiting or recommending with reasons (Falk and Dierking, 2013; Bitgood, 2013). If interpretation is judged by what it enables, then reasoned recall and valued retellings are closer to purpose than momentary liking.

Digital media complicate the craft without displacing it. Building on the thematic spine, they extend what can be shown when access is restricted or when change over time must be made visible quickly. A twenty-second clip of a tool in use, a still that aligns with the current view, or a simple AR overlay that sketches a vanished roofline can help audiences connect a surface to process, regulation or labour, provided the theme has been stated and the point is voiced before and after the insert (Falk and Dierking, 2013; tom Dieck and Jung, 2017). This

sequencing aligns with findings on signalling and brevity in learning research, where concise visuals paired with a clear sentence aid encoding and later recall (Paivio, 1986; Mayer, 2009).

Devices create a second performance that can compete with the shared field of focus. Long clips, dense screens or frequent switching encourage spectatorship rather than interpretation and can depress comprehension in mixed groups (Bitgood, 2013; Falk and Dierking, 2013). In platformed contexts they may also steer visitors toward capture and repetition, reinforcing the tourist gaze's preference for recognisable angles over situated explanation (Urry and Larsen, 2011; Mkono, 2020). A practical response is parsimony and placement. One insert per major turn is usually enough; it should be legible at a glance, visible to the whole group and positioned so that eyes return to the site rather than to the screen.

In bright light, wind or crowded spaces, an analogue aid such as a printed then-and-now card can keep the group together and reduce handling time, while still marking a step in the argument (Falk and Dierking, 2013; Bitgood, 2013). This sits comfortably with TORE. The theme selects which image matters, organisation decides when it appears, relevance is made by linking the image to what visitors already know, and enjoyment is the steady attention that follows clear pacing rather than a stream of effects.

In many heritage settings, images, songs and performances are governed by rules of access and by community consent. Recording and circulation are not neutral acts, because they can move knowledge beyond its intended scope (Smith, 2006; Christen, 2012). Responsible use therefore includes securing permission, stating provenance and limits, and explaining refusals plainly when they apply. A brief explanation that ties the limit to the theme tends to increase credibility because it shows how knowledge is being made public, not only what is being asserted (Silverman, 2011; Weiler and Black, 2015).

Not all visitors can see a small screen in strong light, hear an audio cue, or scan a code with limited data. Museum studies report that accessible, low-bandwidth options—large-print cards, captions, tactile surrogates—serve mixed groups well when they are integrated into the same thematic sequence rather than offered as add-ons (Parry, 2007; Falk and Dierking, 2013). Overall, the literature positions digital media as helpers, not centrepieces. They work when they carry the theme forward, are brief and well timed, return attention to the site, and make sources and permissions visible. When they dominate, they fragment the encounter and feed

repetition; when subordinated to the narrative and to protocol, they make complexity graspable in the moment and more likely to be remembered (Ham, 2016; Falk and Dierking, 2013).

Having outlined TORE and the role of dialogue, the focus now turns to how stories are built and justified in delivery, since the order of scenes, the voice that binds them, and the reasons offered for belief shape what visitors later carry away (Ham, 2016; Silverman, 2011). Narrative is not an embellishment but the medium through which interpretive craft travels. A storyline with a clear arc, a consistent voice and visible grounds for belief helps audiences follow causal and temporal relations and gives them a version they can retell (Bruner, 1991; Ham, 2016). In practice, narrative performs the same work as TORE by selecting, ordering and connecting material so that meaning, rather than detail, drives the encounter (Tilden, 1957; Beck and Cable, 2011).

Evidence on visitor learning shows why this matters. Theme-led, well-signposted stories support reflective processing and stronger sense-making, a pattern Moscardo describes as greater mindfulness during visits (Moscardo, 1996). Simple cues that guide attention and invite short checks of understanding help audiences reorganise prior assumptions rather than stack new facts on top of them (Falk and Dierking, 2013; Bitgood, 2013). When scenes are tethered to a single claim that is stated plainly, recall improves and retellings are more likely to include reasons rather than slogans.

Heritage practice reaches similar conclusions when stories are framed from local perspectives. People-centred guidance recommends naming why a place matters in community terms and showing present use and care alongside the past (Court and Wijesuriya, 2015). Comparative studies report higher appreciation and more pro-social intentions when tours foreground community voice, stewardship and contemporary relevance as part of the plot, not an add-on (Liu and Lin, 2021). A locally grounded theme disciplines selection, while short dialogic moments help listeners connect community reasons to their own repertoires (Ham, 2016; Simon, 2010).

Work on guided tours also links narrative framing to perceived quality. Coherent sequencing, a steady voice and explicit linking of scenes to a central idea are associated with clearer understanding of place and higher judgements of guide performance (Ap and Wong, 2001). Emotion contributes to this effect when it supports a stated claim that can be repeated; affect

tied to explanation enhances retention more reliably than feeling on its own (Packer and Ballantyne, 2011; Falk and Dierking, 2013).

Narrative construction carries ethical weight as well. Incorporating local testimony and acknowledging limits makes the grounds of knowledge visible and reduces the risk of exoticism or overreach, concerns noted in postcolonial heritage work (Smith, 2006; Waterton and Smith, 2010; Silverman, 2011). Brief, plain attribution of sources, scope and consent signals how knowledge is being made public and supports trust. Where a limit applies, a short explanation tied to the theme often strengthens the account because it clarifies responsibility and care.

Taken as a whole, the literature points to a practical claim. Narrative is the vehicle through which TORE operates. A locally grounded theme, clear ordering, purposeful dialogue and calibrated affect help visitors re-sort what they thought they knew and leave with a story they can justify in their own words. This orientation prepares the ground for media used as short inserts that signal a turn in the argument and then step back, and for the ethical and procedural concerns developed in the sections that follow (Ham, 2016; Falk and Dierking, 2013; Court and Wijesuriya, 2015)

Interpretation is the disciplined arrangement of ideas, evidence and moments that helps visitors make sense of place and retell it with reasons. TORE provides the organising logic, narrative and dialogue carry the movement, and ethical transparency with light-touch media sustains trust and attention (Ham, 2016; Beck and Cable, 2011; Falk and Dierking, 2013; Smith, 2006; Weiler and Black, 2015). Quality is visible when visitors can later explain what changed and why, not only that they enjoyed themselves.

2.4 Tour Guide as Active Cultural Agent and Critical Mediator

The previous section has established the rigorous intellectual components that anchor this study. However, the main power of this theoretical architecture is contingent upon defining the agent who synthesises and operationalises these concepts. This study rejects the reductionist view of the guide as a passive, information-delivering conduit, advancing instead a robust theoretical claim that the guide's function is defined by an indispensable and complex dual theoretical role: that of the active cultural agent and the critical mediator. This positioning is not merely descriptive, it constitutes the primary mechanism through which the guide manages

the endemic crises of representation, authenticity, and sustainability within the heritage sector. Defining this comprehensive role is crucial, as it establishes the guide as the intellectual engine of the conceptual alignment that follows.

The guide's communicative role has its conceptual genesis in the principles of heritage interpretation, most notably articulated by Tilden (1977), who posited that effective interpretation is an educational activity aiming at the revelation of meanings and relationships rather than the mere conveyance of factual data. Tilden's framework provided the necessary foundation for viewing the guide as an interpreter. However, as critical tourism scholarship developed, particularly following the rise of mass tourism and post-colonial critique, this technical model proved theoretically insufficient. Early studies often suffered from an epistemic oversight, where they treated the guide as a neutral transmitter of information, failing to account for their inherent professional agency and situated power to influence the visitor's perception (Adams, 2012).

This theoretical gap demanded the rigorous integration of social constructivism and narrative theory to achieve the necessary analytical depth. Drawing upon Urry's (1990) seminal work on tourist gaze, contemporary scholars recognised that the tourist experience is not a static encounter with a fixed reality, but is actively negotiated and shaped in situ. This reconceptualisation positions the guide as an active cultural agent which is a strategic professional who utilises communicative tools to structure, and frequently control, the visitor's perceptual reality.

The guide's active agency is primarily executed through the strategic deployment of narrative construction. The interpretive function is not a simple repetition of an authorised script but a highly selective and intellectual process. As articulated by Salazar (2005; 2012), whose extensive research on guides in developing contexts established the significance of their subjective position, the guide is constantly engaged in a cognitive process of "imagining the other," predicting visitor expectations and constructing narratives designed to fulfil, challenge, or manipulate these expectations. This cognitive labour demonstrates that the guide is an editor and an orchestrator, strategically framing information and applying the interpretive principles of provocation and relevance to achieve a desired narrative reality (Ham, 1992). This requires utilising a blend of verifiable data and local, often tacit, knowledge to weave a cohesive story.

The necessity of this active management is empirically supported by the work of Adams (2012), whose research in Southeast Asia illuminated the concept of gaze management. Adams illustrates how guides employ tactical narratives to mediate and soften the inherent cultural shock associated with encountering poverty or profound social difference, thereby actively shaping the way tourists perceive and react to the local environment. This strategic intervention reveals that the guide's active role is defined by intellectual and rhetorical work, transforming static cultural content into dynamic, engaging, and ethically managed experience. The shift from passive "speaker" to active "shaper" establishes the guide's essential role as the communicative engine of the entire framework.

While the guide's interpretive function defines their communicative methodology, the second, more ethically complex role that the critical mediator, addresses the guide's relationship with power, ethics, and conflict. The guide operates as a cultural broker positioned at the confluence of competing socio-economic, political, and epistemic interests (Cohen, 1985; Holloway & Wallin, 2017). This role is one of critical intervention—the active management and resolution of fundamental contradictions that threaten the integrity of the heritage resource.

The most profound and historically challenging tension managed by the mediator is the endemic contradiction within the heritage and tourism system where the struggle between the ethical demand for preservation and the economic necessity of commodification. Critical tourism scholarship, particularly the scrutiny of staged authenticity (MacCannell, 1999), poses a direct challenge to the guide's ethical position, often viewing them as tacitly complicit in the systematic reduction of culture to a marketable commodity. The role of the critical Mediator exists precisely to negotiate this tension, rejecting the notion of authenticity as a fixed object to be consumed. Instead, the guide demonstrates that authenticity is a dynamic, fragile state to be actively constructed and ethically managed in situ where a process inherently requiring negotiation (Salazar, 2012).

This mediation relies critically on the guide's capacity to function as a cultural gatekeeper, a concept extensively analysed by scholars such as Hitchcock (2001; 2007) in his research on Indonesian and Southeast Asian tourism. Hitchcock's work illuminates how guides actively regulate the flow of information and access, strategically filtering potentially harmful or culturally sensitive material to protect local communities from excessive intrusion or misrepresentation. This ethical gatekeeping function is the practical manifestation of the mediator's ethical responsibility. The guide anchors this practice by prioritising narratives

grounded in community-vetted knowledge. The reliance on social capital (section 2.3) moves beyond simple networking; it functions as a critical mediation tool that provides the ethical authorisation necessary to narrate a culture (Black, 2010). By demonstrating commitment to local trust, the guide safeguards the narrative against the market's reductionist demands. The guide's professional authority, therefore, is rooted not solely in technical expertise, but in their capacity for ethical negotiation and their commitment to local interests.

Furthermore, the mediator is responsible for resolving the historical epistemic and post-colonial gap between the local community's complex identity and the often-ethnocentric expectations and assumptions of the global visitor (Wang, 2000). The mediator translates local norms, values, and nuanced intangible heritage, often filtering them through a framework that anticipates and manages the post-colonial gaze. This is a powerful act of cultural translation where the guide actively combats the reductionist tendencies of tourism marketing by presenting a complex, multifaceted reality. The guide strategically frames narratives (the active agent's skill) to cultivate empathy and ethical responsibility, effectively transforming the visitor from a passive consumer into an engaged steward of the site. This mediation of attitude and ethics is a critical social intervention that directly supports long-term preservation goals by building a global constituency for local heritage. The synthesis of Salazar's (2012) work on representation and Hitchcock's (2007) observations on gatekeeping demonstrates that the guide in this region is not a neutral party but an indispensable cultural manager of power relations.

Having established the guide as the dynamic engine of the process and the indispensable agent of cultural interpretation, the subsequent section must now delineate the specific inputs that fuel this agency, focusing explicitly on the resources and learning pathways upon which this central actor relies.

2.5 Knowledge Systems as Mechanism: Informal Learning and Social Capital

If interpretation is enacted rather than transmitted, the review must explain how interpretive craft circulates and why the licence to tell difficult stories is uneven. Studies of professional learning show that much competence is tacit, situated and acquired through participation in work communities more than through classroom instruction (Polanyi, 1966; Lave and Wenger, 1991; Eraut, 2000). In heritage and tourism settings this appears as iterative trial, mentoring, peer clinics and the exchange of tested stories and examples. Workplace and service-learning research describes these processes as informal and incidental, embedded in routine activity and

social relations, and often decisive for performance in visitor-facing roles (Marsick and Watkins, 1990; Billett, 2001; Airey and Tribe, 2000; Baum, 2008).

Social capital provides the analytic bridge between individual craft and the settings in which it develops. Following Bourdieu (1986), Coleman (1988) and Putnam (2000), it is taken here as the resources embedded in social relations that enable coordinated action. Putnam's distinction between bonding and bridging ties, along with later work on linking ties, helps specify how different networks work: bonding ties sustain trust and obligation within close circles, bridging ties connect practitioners to new information and perspectives, and linking ties open channels to institutions with formal authority (Putnam, 2000; Szreter and Woolcock, 2004). Portes (1998) clarifies that social capital has causes and effects, which matters for interpretation because networks both generate knowledge and distribute opportunities unevenly. In heritage tourism, these relations underpin participation and preservation by moving stories, provenance and practical help through communities as well as across organisations (Murzyn-Kupisz and Działek, 2013; Moscardo et al., 2017).

At community scale, the literature shows how these ties shape participation, resilience and the tenor of narratives. In Aboriginal cultural tourism, for example, social capital mediates between perceived benefits and willingness to engage, with trust within the group and confidence in partners predicting sustained involvement (Hsieh, Tsai and Chen, 2017). Rural studies report that when bonding ties dominate and wider links weaken, engagement contracts to family units and collective identity erodes, reducing capacity to host visitors and to refresh stories (Borlido and Coromina, 2018). Where bridging and linking ties are stronger, communities mobilise resources more readily, attract investment and innovate through partnerships that retain local voice while meeting visitor needs (McGehee et al., 2009; Macbeth, Carson and Northcote, 2004). In heritage settings, this configuration affects what visitors hear: dense local bonds protect care and continuity, while outward-looking ties connect guides to archives, curators and peer expertise that deepen interpretation and open room for contested histories.

Research to date leaves several gaps. Much of the social-capital literature in heritage tourism concentrates on community mobilisation and destination governance, with less attention to how individual guides draw on networks to build repertoires, secure permissions, or handle contested material. Empirical coverage is also uneven. Studies are weighted toward Europe, North America and Australasia, while contexts marked by multilingual practice, plural authority and uneven institutional reach, in Southeast Asia, for example, there are

comparatively under-represented (Mura and Tavakoli, 2014). Finally, outcomes are often inferred at the project level rather than examined in delivery. We know that trust and collaboration aid participation, yet we know less about how particular ties shape what visitors actually hear, what they later recall, and how they act. These gaps justify closer attention to the micro-mechanisms through which bonding, bridging and linking ties furnish guides with sources, consent and narrative techniques, and to the conditions that make such resources usable on site.

The present study addresses these gaps by examining how Indonesian guides mobilise networks of trust and reciprocity to deepen understanding of culturally significant material and to make that knowledge publicly usable. The focus is on the interactions among guides, communities and institutions that support exchange and mutual learning, and on how those interactions supply provenance, consent and technique for narrative construction. In doing so, the study extends accounts of informal learning in tourism by specifying how social capital shapes the development and maintenance of guiding repertoires in culturally diverse settings.

Social capital provides an analytic vocabulary for how learning is organised and how authority is constructed. Bonding ties build trust and shared norms within close circles and support obligation, quick help and reputation protection (Coleman, 1988; Putnam, 2000). Bridging ties reach across groups and bring new information and perspectives, linking guides to archives, scholars and expert peers they would not otherwise meet (Granovetter, 1973; Burt, 1992). Linking ties connect practitioners to institutions with formal decision-making power, including museums, site managers, certification bodies and heritage offices (Szreter and Woolcock, 2004). In practice these relations move more than content. They move provenance, reasons and permission to speak, which is crucial where material is sensitive, sacred or contested (Waterton and Smith, 2010; Weiler and Black, 2015; Silverman, 2011). Credibility on site rests less on possession of facts than on showing grounds, for example, citing a recognised source, naming the person or community that authorised the account, or explaining a refusal in clear protocol terms.

These dynamics also explain unevenness. Bonding ties can harden into enclaves that protect quality but limit novelty and access, sometimes excluding women, younger guides or linguistic minorities from mentorship and story banks (Portes, 1998). Bridging ties may be thin or transactional, yielding access without depth; without bonding trust, sensitive material is unlikely to be shared. Linking ties broaden recognition, yet heavy dependence can align

practice with managerial scripts and marginalise contested voices (Bourdieu, 1986; Harrison, 2013). Practitioners positioned at structural holes who connect otherwise separate circles often gain privileged access to diverse sources and can translate between institutional and community grounds for belief (Burt, 1992; Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). Where such positions are scarce, repertoires narrow and delivery gravitates to safe, repeatable narratives.

Practice circulates not only through conversation but also through concrete materials. Annotated scripts, image folders that record provenance, and story banks that note who told a story, when it was told, and under what conditions, act as evidence trails. They show provenance, consent and scope, which helps standardise delivery, lowers preparation time and lets knowledge move across organisations (Brown and Duguid, 2001; Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). Peer debriefs and small clinics play a similar role. Guides unpack difficult moments together—fielding a challenge, explaining a refusal, negotiating a boundary and turn them into techniques others can use. These settings are also where sponsorship often happens. A senior guide may open access to an archive, introduce an elder, or endorse a sensitive analogy once a novice has shown sound judgement. In that way, learning is linked directly to permission and to credibility on site.

Two evaluative implications follow. First, breadth of repertoire is likely to track the expansiveness of the learning environment and the diversity of bridging and linking ties, while ethical reliability depends on bonding trust that supports rehearsal and correction (Fuller and Unwin, 2003; Putnam, 2000; Szreter and Woolcock, 2004). Second, programmes that add content without improving access to mentors, archives and institutional partners have limited effect. Interventions that cultivate sponsorship, record provenance and normalise protocol-based refusals are more likely to strengthen interpretive authority than additional facts alone (Weiler and Black, 2015; Silverman, 2011).

The mechanism explained above implies a specific account of how guide knowledge is formed. Formal programmes establish shared vocabulary, ethics and procedural baselines, while much of the situated competence required for live delivery develops through participation in work settings—observing, co-performing and debriefing with experienced peers (Lave and Wenger, 1991; Eraut, 2000; Billett, 2001). In heritage contexts this learning is bound up with negotiated access, provenance checks and protocol, so it is as much relational and ethical as it is informational. The next subsection therefore examines knowledge acquisition in two streams—

formal instruction and informal workplace learning—and shows how social capital conditions each stream's reach and effect.

2.4.1 Tour Guides Knowledge Acquisition

Scholarship on professional learning, material culture and heritage practice converges on a simple claim. Guiding competence grows through a blend of formal preparation and situated participation in work communities. Courses and certification establish shared terminology, ethics and risk management. Much of what enables guides to deliver credible and responsive narratives is tacit, context bound and learned in practice through repeated participation, observation and dialogue with peers and elders (Polanyi, 1966; Lave and Wenger, 1991; Eraut, 2000; Airey and Tribe, 2000). Tourism education recognises the value of formal programmes yet shows that transfer into live situations is mediated by local cultures of practice, organisational routines and site-specific constraints, which helps to explain variation among graduates of similar curricula (Airey and Tribe, 2000; Weiler and Black, 2015).

Accounts of tacit knowledge help to specify why formal preparation has limits. Skilled performance depends on reading weak cues in real time and on timely judgement about pacing, stance, example selection and the handling of protocol and refusal (Polanyi, 1966; Schön, 1983). Situated learning research adds that such judgement develops through participation in communities of practice. Newcomers move from peripheral roles to fuller participation as they absorb norms, tools and repertoires that define competent work in a setting (Lave and Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1998). In early career stages, much learning is informal and incidental, triggered by the demands of real tasks and supported by brief exchanges, observation and feedback rather than by scheduled classes (Eraut, 2000; Billett, 2001).

Heritage and museum studies complement this view by tying credibility to process. Public claims acquire weight when chains of custody are visible, framing is transparent and uncertainty is acknowledged, not simply when objects are impressive. For guiding, acquisition of knowledge therefore includes building access to attributable sources, learning the scope and limits of testimonies, and developing language that can state a limit without closing down learning (Dudley, 2012; Harrison, 2013; DeSilvey, 2017).

Social capital offers a useful vocabulary for how such learning moves. Bonding ties sustain trust and continuity within guiding circles and lower the cost of asking naive questions or testing a story in a safe setting. Bridging ties connect practitioners to diverse sources such as archives, producers, community historians and expert peers. Linking ties open channels to curators, site managers and regulators and help practitioners to secure permissions or understand rules that govern access (Putnam, 2000; Szreter and Woolcock, 2004). These ties circulate techniques, sources and attributions, and they also circulate permissions and the language for limits. In this sense, social capital acts as a conduit that converts knowledge into admissible public narrative. The same framework helps to explain why guides with similar formal credentials differ in confidence and nuance when handling sensitive topics. Networks vary in reach and reciprocity and so do the sets of permissions and attributions that practitioners can call upon.

Everyday sociality is a central vehicle for this circulation. Informal gatherings with peers and elders function as reciprocal learning environments where alternative readings are tried, boundaries are rehearsed and phrases that make a refusal intelligible are refined. Mentoring and route shadowing support similar ends. Novices see how experienced guides time a turn in the narrative, frame an uncertainty or explain a protocol, and they learn which archives are reliable, who in the community is comfortable with attribution and which professionals will answer a quick query. Partnerships with museums and makers widen the pool of attributable images and examples and provide an evidence base that travels well in public settings. These features mirror what communities-of-practice research describes and align with heritage documentation work on the importance of provenance and clear crediting for public trust (Wenger, 1998; Harrison, 2013; Silverman, 2011).

Shared artefacts act as teaching devices as much as records. Route cards and annotated image banks present worked examples of how to stage a claim, when to insert a cue and how to word an attribution. Story banks that note source, date and conditions of use model the language of consent and scope. Because these materials circulate across teams, novices rehearse credible phrasing before they meet a live dilemma and can see what counts as adequate provenance in the group. Peer debriefs and clinics extend this pedagogy by turning difficult episodes into case notes that can be tried by others. Sponsorship often follows such clinics when a senior practitioner opens an archive, introduces an elder or authorises a delicate analogy once

readiness is evident, which links learning directly to permission and public credibility (Brown and Duguid, 2001; Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995; Harrison, 2013; Silverman, 2011).

Barriers to acquisition arise when networks tilt toward enclosure or thin brokerage. Dense bonding can safeguard quality yet restrict entry to mentorship and story banks, particularly for women, younger guides or linguistic minorities (Portes, 1998). Pure bridging can yield contact without depth, which limits access to sensitive knowledge that depends on trust. Heavy reliance on linking ties may secure recognition but pull practice toward managerial scripts that exclude contested voices (Bourdieu, 1986; Harrison, 2013). The most fertile positions are those that bridge otherwise separate circles and translate between institutional and community warrants. Practitioners in such positions accumulate diverse examples and a wider set of attributions and permissions, which supports richer and more careful narrative work (Burt, 1992; Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998).

These dynamics also clarify unevenness. Bonding ties protect quality yet can become enclaves that limit novelty and exclude women, younger guides or linguistic minorities from mentorship and story banks (Portes, 1998). Bridging ties can be thin or transactional, yielding access without depth; without bonding trust, sensitive material is unlikely to be shared. Linking ties broaden recognition yet heavy dependence can encourage compliance with managerial scripts and discourage contested voices (Bourdieu, 1986; Harrison, 2013). Configuration matters. Practitioners who bridge otherwise separate circles often gain privileged access to diverse sources and translate between institutional and community warrants (Burt, 1992; Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). Where such positions are scarce, practice collapses toward safe repetition.

Formal systems still matter, but the literature is clear about their scope. Training and certification set a common floor for ethics, visitor care and safety, and can widen links to institutions and resources. They rarely capture the tacit repertoire required for live guiding, and transfer into practice is strongly shaped by local conditions (Airey and Tribe, 2000; Baum, 2008; Eraut, 2000). When rubrics privilege standard recall they stabilise quality but also narrow autonomy or lock practice to scripts. Strong bridging and linking ties help recover plurality by bringing in new sources, fresh analogies and community-grounded justification (Weiler and Black, 2015; Smith, 2006). Institutions can tilt the balance by recognising informal learning through mentoring and peer clinics and by assessing judgement as well as knowledge. Approaches that value reflective debriefs, observed practice and feedback from communities

tend to widen repertoires rather than freeze them (Fuller and Unwin, 2003; Weiler and Black, 2015).

Examples illustrate the complementarity rather than the sufficiency of formal routes. Well-known certifications such as the UK Blue Badge or Australia's EcoGuide raise a baseline of competence, codify safety and legal standards and sharpen delivery skills, yet graduates still rely on local networks to source attributable images, learn protocol and refine storylines for mixed audiences (Black and Ham, 2005; Institute of Tourist Guiding, 2023; Weiler and Black, 2015). Similar patterns appear in national programmes in Indonesia and Japan, where formal modules on culture and language are necessary but not sufficient for handling community expectations, contested histories and protocol in live encounters (HPI, 2015; Yamada and Skibins, 2020).

Across this work, interpretative authority is treated as situational. Title and credential help, but credibility is earned at delivery when provenance is visible, permissions are clear and scope and uncertainty are stated. This position follows constructivist readings of authenticity and museum practice that tie credibility to process and disclosure rather than to essence or volume of access (Bruner, 1994; Reisinger and Steiner, 2006; Silverman, 2011). It also sits with postcolonial concerns where permission is part of knowing and where some knowledge is restricted by role, season or place. In those contexts, consent and attribution form part of the claim because they locate the speaker within relations of responsibility (Smith, 2006; Smith, 2012; Christen, 2012).

Tourism education seldom treats permission as part of knowing, although indigenous and museum studies make this explicit. Assessment in guiding still tends to privilege recall and delivery mechanics over procedural judgement about attribution, consent and refusal, despite calls for stronger links between research and training (Weiler and Black, 2015). Social-capital studies often document collaboration but underplay asymmetries of access around knowledge sovereignty. Communities-of-practice theory explains how newcomers learn, yet says little about how communities retire scripts that have become ethically or analytically weak. Heritage studies document the importance of provenance and consent, but provide fewer accounts of how these commitments hold under time pressure and mixed audiences.

The implication is straightforward. Formal instruction lays a floor of shared language and ethical expectation. Informal participation builds repertoires that are responsive to place and

audience. Social capital carries the permissions and attributions that render those repertoires usable in public. Knowledge acquisition is therefore inseparable from the social organisation of authority. This explains why similar facts lead to different narratives and why some practitioners can handle difficult material with care while others remain within narrow promotional frames.

2.5 Embodiment and Sensory Engagement

This section extends the craft account in 2.3 by treating embodiment and the senses as routine parts of interpretive work. Visitor studies and environmental psychology show that attention, feeling and memory arise from what people do with their bodies in places, not from words alone (Falk and Dierking, 2013; Tuan, 1977). Museum and heritage research adds that small, well-judged sensory cues can anchor an argument in experience when those cues are tied to a clear theme and handled with care (Classen and Howes, 2006; Pink, 2009). On this review, sensory engagement is a practical means to focus attention, help understanding and support later recall. It is not decoration and it is not a show.

A consistent finding across the literature is that pairing a verbal claim with a simple, relevant cue improves learning. Dual coding theory proposes that people store information in verbal and nonverbal systems, so a short cue that fits the message can create two routes for later recall (Paivio, 1986). Multimedia learning research reaches a similar conclusion and points to conditions for success. The cue should be brief, uncluttered and obviously connected to the message, and it should be placed where it marks a turn in the story rather than interrupting it (Mayer, 2009). Museum studies echo this with evidence that simple images, short object touches and concise map inserts help visitors keep track of ideas over time, provided the facilitator names the link back to the theme (Falk and Dierking, 2013; Bitgood, 2013). When these conditions hold, audiences are more likely to remember the claim and the reason for it, not only the novelty of the moment.

In live guiding this translates into small practices that support the TORE spine. The theme selects which cues matter. Organisation decides when to use them so that they mark a step in the argument. Relevance links each cue to what the audience already knows. Enjoyment keeps attention steady without diverting it from meaning (Ham, 2016; Beck and Cable, 2011). A period photograph held where the present view aligns helps audiences grasp change (Falk and Dierking, 2013; Mayer, 2009). An annotated map before a complex object story gives bearings

that make the next step easier to follow (Falk and Dierking, 2013). A brief tactile check of a building stone prepares listeners to hear about material, source and labour (Pallasmaa, 2005; Prown, 1982). Each act is short, placed and tied to a sentence that states the point, so the claim feels reasonable and memorable rather than being buried under extra stimuli (Mayer, 2009).

Embodiment involves more than sight. Work in architecture, anthropology and sensory studies shows that sound, temperature, texture and smell shape mood and attention, and that these states in turn govern what people notice and how long they stay with an idea (Pallasmaa, 2005; Howes, 2005; Pink, 2009). Heritage research has pushed beyond the visual gaze by showing how understanding often turns on small bodily adjustments such as pausing, touching, listening and breathing in a place, through which visitors orient themselves and attach meaning (Edensor, 2001; Tuan, 1977). In practice this means using cues that already exist on site and tying them clearly to the theme.

Food offers a direct route to place because taste and smell bind experience to memory and social meaning. Short, well-framed tastings help visitors connect landscapes, labour and identity when provenance and technique are made explicit rather than left implied (Sutton, 2001; Richards, 2002; Timothy and Ron, 2013; Ellis et al., 2018). A clove in the hand, a sip of palm sugar syrup or a bite of fermented cassava can anchor a concise account of trade routes, seasonal work and household skill. Naming producers and methods strengthens authenticity claims and allocates credit to communities as well as venues (Bessière, 1998; Sims, 2009). These inserts should be small and consent-aware. Allergies, dietary rules and fasting days require checks and an opt-out, and where ritual foods are involved explanation may replace tasting. When a limit is stated and linked back to the theme, refusal clarifies rather than obstructs (Smith, 2006; Silverman, 2011; Waterton and Smith, 2010).

Traditional instruments work in a similar way when they make a claim audible instead of turning into a show. Brief guided listening to a live phrase or a short recorded clip draws attention to structure and role and links sound to social order, space and etiquette (Small, 1998; Schippers, 2010). Safe touch with replicas or robust instruments gives a bodily handle on craft. Feeling string tension, mallet weight or a drum membrane prepares a concise account of tuning systems, materials, apprenticeship and repair (Grant, 2014; Schippers and Grant, 2016). Some instruments and repertoires are restricted by gender, lineage or ritual status. Good practice confirms who may play, what may be demonstrated and where, and explains a limit when one

applies. A simple statement that “today we listen rather than play because this melody belongs to ceremony” models respect and strengthens credibility (Smith, 2006; Silverman, 2011).

Across senses the same craft rules hold. Fit matters, so the cue must carry the theme rather than compete with it. Timing matters, so the cue should mark a turn in the story and then return the group to a shared line of thought. A few seconds spent listening for a sound mark such as a call to prayer or harbour horn can open discussion of regulation, labour rhythms or the management of sacred time when the guide then states the point and moves on (Schafer, 1994; Falk and Dierking, 2013). Stepping into shade before discussing courtyard design or irrigation helps bodies register the claim before it is named (Tuan, 1977; Pallasmaa, 2005). Pairing a verbal claim with a simple sensory act gives two routes for recall, which explains why these brief, theme-tethered inserts travel beyond the visit as reasoned retellings rather than as loose impressions (Paivio, 1986; Mayer, 2009; Falk and Dierking, 2013).

Digital media can help when used with restraint. Tablets, small projectors, and short clips are useful when access is restricted or when change over time must be shown quickly (Tallon and Walker, 2008; Parry, 2007). The same conditions apply as for any cue. Inserts should be brief, easy to read and tied to the point at hand. A twenty-second clip of a tool in use can be enough; a single high-contrast image can stand in for a long explanation of a vanished view (Mayer, 2009; Falk and Dierking, 2013). Long slideshows, dense text, background music over speech and frequent switching between devices fragment attention and weaken the shared field of focus (Bitgood, 2013; Mayer, 2009). Short, well-timed pieces work best when they mark a turn in the narrative and then step back.

Mobile media are most effective when they support situated understanding: simple overlays, then-and-now sliders, and geo-anchored prompts help visitors link what they see to a process or a timeline, provided the prompt is short and clearly signposted (Hsi, 2003; Kuflik et al., 2011). Captions should do conceptual work rather than repeat what is obvious, and should prioritise legibility, plain language and translation where needed. Accessibility matters: subtitles on clips, alt-text for stills and volume control for outdoor use improve inclusion without slowing the group (Tallon and Walker, 2008).

Curation and ethics are part of craft. Images and clips should carry provenance and permission, especially where people, sacred places or community knowledge are involved (Smith, 2006; Silverman, 2011). Avoid filming new scenes without consent. Where protocol restricts

recording, explain the limit and use a diagram or an approved still instead. Practicalities also count: glare, battery life, network drop-outs and speaker bleed can derail a group. Offline files, high-contrast visuals and a single device under the guide's control reduce failure points (Parry, 2007). In sum, media support the narrative when they carry the theme forward, clarify one step and then get out of the way.

Dialogue remains central. Sensory work succeeds when it is woven into a short exchange that checks assumptions and names what the cue is doing. A guide can ask what visitors already think they are seeing, then use a cue to confirm or unsettle that expectation. A question about direction on a map, a query about what sounds are local and what are introduced, or a quick comparison between two textures, can make prior frames visible and open space for reinterpretation. Dialogue also helps to keep enjoyment in the service of meaning. A light moment has value when it lowers barriers and refreshes attention, provided it returns quickly to the theme and does not reduce serious material to entertainment (Beck and Cable, 2011; Weiler and Black, 2015).

Ethics sits close to practice because some cues touch ritual, grief or restricted knowledge. In many communities permission is part of knowing. Knowing a fact is not the same as having standing to say it in public, and rights to speak may depend on role, kinship, season and place (Smith, 2006; Smith, 2012; Christen, 2012). Responsible practice checks who may speak, what may be shown or played, where this is appropriate and how it should be framed. Photography and recording require the same care. Limits should be explained simply and linked to the theme so that refusal becomes clarifying rather than obstructive. When audiences understand why something cannot be shown, and how that decision respects people and place, trust increases and the ethical line of the work becomes visible (Silverman, 2011; Waterton and Smith, 2010). These judgements are learned in practice and are upheld as much by social sanction as by institutional rule. Section 2.4 shows how informal learning and social capital supply the permission and provenance that make such decisions credible.

Failure modes are common and avoidable. Sensory inserts fail when they are frequent, long, loosely connected to the theme or chosen for novelty. They also fail when a group is asked to handle sensitive material without preparation, or when an effect is staged without consent. The literature suggests a few safeguards. Use few cues, and choose them for their explanatory power rather than their visual appeal. Place each cue at a turn in the narrative, and keep it short. Say out loud what the cue is doing. If a limit applies, explain it in plain terms. If a member of

the group raises a challenge, slow the pace and restate the theme before moving on. These habits keep the field of attention shared and prevent the slide into display (Falk and Dierking, 2013; Bitgood, 2013; Beck and Cable, 2011).

Evaluation should match purpose. If sensory work is meant to help people grasp and remember a reasoned claim, then outcomes should track recall and retelling rather than satisfaction alone. Visitor studies link clear themes, structured sequences and salient cues to improved encoding and later retrieval, and to selective behavioural intentions such as a decision to revisit, recommend or care for a place with reasons, not slogans (Falk and Dierking, 2013; Bitgood, 2013). Simple checks can be built into practice. A guide can ask a small group to explain what changed here and why, or to place a period image in the right position on a map, or to compare two materials and say what follows from the difference. These are not tests in a formal sense. They are small opportunities to rehearse the account, which makes later recall more likely.

Sensory engagement interacts directly with authorised discourse and destination imaging because many visitors arrive primed by circulating pictures and captions. Destination branding and media produce repeatable “views” and storylines that guide what people expect to see and how they evaluate it (Echtner and Ritchie, 1991; Jenkins, 2003; Urry and Larsen, 2011). These expectations are not neutral. They crystallise the authorised heritage discourse and postcolonial imaginaries by centring certain objects, angles and moods while leaving labour, regulation and conflict out of frame (Smith, 2006; Said, 1978; Salazar, 2012). Sensory techniques give interpreters small, practical ways to work with those frames and then re-contextualise them.

A simple change of vantage point can interrupt a stock view structured by the “tourist gaze” and bring neglected elements into the foreground—back-of-house labour, repair, drainage, or ritual boundaries—so that audiences notice relationships that the iconic angle hides (Urry, 2002; Edensor, 2001). Then-and-now pairings function similarly: a single aligned image turns a promotional vista into a short history of regulation, enclosure or migration, correcting the impression of timelessness often produced by branding (Jenkins, 2003; Morgan, Pritchard and Pride, 2011). Sound and quiet have parallel effects. A brief listen for a sound mark—the call to prayer, harbour horns, market bells—can locate visitors in a social and regulatory field that the photo does not show (Schafer, 1994), while a moment of quiet next to a crowded shot underscores how rules, consent and timing shape access and conduct (Silverman, 2011; Smith, 2006). These sensory techniques support the craft outlined in 2.3 and, when used with consent,

help audiences carry a reasoned account. Their relation to authenticity claims is taken up in section 2.6

This is where the craft in 2.3 and the mechanism in 2.4 meet practice. Theme and organisation shape which sensory inserts to use and when, so that each cue marks a turn in the reasoning rather than becoming a distraction (Ham, 2016). Informal learning and social capital supply the provenance, consent and examples—archival photos with credits, approved audio clips, storylines agreed with community partners—that make re-framing credible (Weiler and Black, 2015; Szreter and Woolcock, 2004). When the insert is brief, well-timed and explained, audiences leave not only with a vivid moment but with a retellable line: what was pictured, what was missing, and why that matters.

A practical implication from attention research is that people fatigue quickly under unvarying cues and retain little when cues are absent. Attention in informal settings rises with novelty, then drifts unless there is a purposeful change in activity or focus (Bitgood, 2013; Falk and Dierking, 2013). Cognitive load studies point to the same middle course: segment the narrative into short, meaningful units and avoid extraneous material that competes with the message (Mayer, 2009; Harp and Mayer, 1998). In practice this means punctuating a tour with a few brief moments that carry weight. A workable rule is that each major section of the story warrants one cue that marks the turn, lasts no more than half a minute, and is followed by a clear sentence that states what the cue was for. Between these points, voice, pacing, eye contact and small gestures carry the work. Short resets—silence, a change of stance, a shift in vantage point—can restore attention without adding more media (Serrell, 1998; Bitgood, 2013). This approach matches accounts of performance in tourism that emphasise improvisation within structure rather than free display (Edensor, 2001) and aligns with craft advice that warns against “seductive details” that are entertaining but irrelevant (Harp and Mayer, 1998). The guide’s task is to help audiences do something thoughtful with what they encounter. Sensory engagement, used sparingly and with consent, is one of the tools that makes that possible.

This section therefore contributes three clarifications to the literature. First, it treats sensory engagement as part of interpretation rather than as an optional add-on, and ties it directly to outcomes that matter, namely reasoned recall and valued retellings. Second, it states the mechanism by which small cues work, which is the pairing of verbal and nonverbal traces and the careful placement of inserts within a narrative. Third, it locates ethical judgement inside practice and shows why permission and provenance are not external constraints but parts of the

knowledge that guides require. Later chapters return to these points in cases where short, consent aware cues help audiences move from recognition to understanding. In those cases, visitors do not only enjoy a moment. They leave with a story that they can tell again, and with reasons that make sense to them.

2.6 Authenticity as an Effect of Practice and Negotiation

This section takes a clear position. In live guiding, authenticity is not a hidden property inside objects, it is something produced in practice when claims are well grounded, staged with care and judged credible in context. Traditional frameworks still shape the field. Material or object-centred approaches tie authenticity to fabric, age and provenance, and they continue to inform conservation and museum decisions (Lowenthal, 1998; Jokilehto, 1999). Tourism's front stage and back stage warning reminds us that polished displays often hide the work behind them (MacCannell, 1999). Experience-centred accounts explain why visitors value moments that feel real, even with replicas or reconstructions (Cohen, 1979; Wang, 1999). These views give us standards, cautions and motives, but on their own they do not explain how authenticity is achieved in a live encounter.

A well-established line of scholarship examines how authenticity is produced. From Bruner (1994) and Kirshenblatt-Gimblett (1998) to Reisinger and Steiner (2006), the argument is that authenticity is negotiated in context, brought into being through selection and framing, and ultimately a judgement rather than a measurable essence. For guiding, the practical test is clear, to make reasons visible and stage them so they land with this audience, in this place.

Authenticity in live guiding is achieved when reasons are visible, delivery fits the setting, ethical care is evident, and the audience can carry the account forward. Making reasons visible goes beyond name-checking a source. It means showing where a claim comes from—an archival photograph with date and credit, a permit or plan, an attributed testimony with scope and consent—and being explicit about uncertainty or disagreement (Smith, 2006; Christen, 2012; Silverman, 2011). These gestures signal that knowledge is being made responsibly rather than recited.

Fitting the staging to place and people turns reasons into something followable. Pacing, vantage point and media should lower cognitive load and mark genuine steps in the argument. A precise then-and-now alignment before a complex explanation, a pause in shade before discussing

microclimates and work rhythms, or one high-contrast still instead of a slideshow are small choices that make the next sentence easier to grasp (Ham, 2016; Mayer, 2009; Falk and Dierking, 2013).

Care for people and materials is part of the claim, not an add-on. Where knowledge is sacred, sensitive or owned collectively, permission is part of knowing. Responsible guiding checks who may speak, what may be shown or played, and where, and gives a brief reason when a limit applies. Explaining that a melody belongs to ceremony, or that a food should not be tasted outside a festival, signals respect and often increases trust because visitors can see the ethics that sit inside the account (Smith, 2012; Waterton and Smith, 2010; Silverman, 2011).

Finally, connection makes a claim carryable. Short questions, quick predictions and one-sentence justifications help visitors surface assumptions and revise them in light of evidence. Analogy and contrast do similar work such as mapping a spice trade monopoly to a modern trademark regime, or feeling limestone against andesite before a line on quarry, transport and labour. These compact exchanges convert attention into understanding and understanding into a retellable story (Beck and Cable, 2011; Ham, 2016; Leinhardt, Crowley and Knutson, 2002).

When visible grounds, apt staging, evident care and live connection come together, participants commonly describe the encounter as “real,” even when the material is modest or unsettles a familiar image. This accords with studies showing that clear themes, simple well-placed cues and dialogic checks yield stronger comprehension and recall than spectacle or volume alone (Ham, 2016; Falk and Dierking, 2013; Weiler and Black, 2015).

Postcolonial critique clarifies how these tourist gaze frames take hold. The AHD privileges expert knowledge and professional canons, and a narrow band of affect, which then sets the template for what counts as “heritage” in brochures and on platforms (Smith, 2006). Orientalism supplies recognisable signs of otherness, while self-orientalism adapts those signs to anticipated demand so they remain legible to visitors and to the market (Said, 1978; Salazar, 2012). The result is rarely a simple top-down script. It is a co-production among DMOs, platforms, venues and tourists, in which certain angles, captions and performances are reinforced because they travel easily and attract approval (Jenkins, 2003; Urry and Larsen, 2011). In such conditions the label “authentic” often attaches to the familiar rather than to the best-grounded account.

Live interpretation guiding operates inside these constraints yet can widen the field of what is sayable. The leverage point is warranted re-contextualisation. Guides can accept recognition as a starting point and then locate the familiar image within narratives of work, regulation, repair, migration or protocol that are supported by sources and permissions. In practice this uses small, consent-aware inserts from 2.5, but the authenticity work happens when reasons are surfaced, limits are named and provenance is visible. A familiar temple vista becomes a story about seismic retrofitting and ritual boundaries once a dated plan or approved photograph is shown and the rule for where one may stand is explained. A market scene becomes a claim about seasonality and labour when a brief tasting is tied to producers and methods rather than to generic “local flavour”. These shifts do not dismantle the image; they provincialise it, placing it as one view among others with clear grounds (Bruner, 1994; Reisinger and Steiner, 2006).

This reframing has two consequences for authenticity. First, it displaces the test from recognition to procedure. What counts as “real” in the encounter is not the repetition of a trope but the clarity of sources, permissions and reasons, which aligns with the Nara argument that criteria are plural and locally interpreted (ICOMOS, 1994; Jokilehto, 1999). Second, it repositions visitors as co-judges rather than spectators. Short questions and one-sentence justifications invite them to compare the circulating image with situated evidence and to endorse a better account. When that happens, the feeling of realness is attached to a claim that can be retold, not only to a moment that photographed well (Ham, 2016; Falk and Dierking, 2013).

The language of authentication helps to describe what is going on. Cohen and Cohen (2012) distinguish cool authentication, which comes from experts, documents and institutions, from hot authentication, which comes from performance and community uptake in the moment. Guiding usually needs both. A dated plan or credited photograph is cool authentication. A clear, protocol-aware refusal that audiences understand, or a brief participatory act that reveals technique, is hot authentication. The two reinforce each other when a guide can show how they know and why a limit applies.

Scholars increasingly treat authenticity as procedural rather than intrinsic. The question shifts from whether an object is authentic to whether the process that produced a claim is credible—who was consulted, which sources were mobilised, what protocols governed access, and how disagreement was handled. This orientation is consistent with the Nara Document, which

broadens admissible criteria to include form, use, tradition and spirit as locally interpreted, not material fabric alone (ICOMOS, 1994; Jokilehto, 1999). Work in indigenous and museum studies advances the same point by showing that permission and provenance are part of knowing, shaping both the legitimacy and the ethics of public narration (Smith, 2006; Smith, 2012; Christen, 2012).

Scholarship in material culture, museum and heritage studies treats credibility as a function of how evidence is assembled and delimited, rather than of any single evidential type (Harrison, 2013; Dudley, 2012). Three streams recur and are often combined. Material traces can be read in situ to warrant claims about technique or chronology, for example tool marks, joins, weathering and repair (Prown, 1982; Beck and Cable, 2011). Documented sources stabilise statements about change and regulation by fixing time and authorship, for example dated photographs, plans and permits. Situated testimony contributes social and ethical knowledge that archives may not hold, provided scope, attribution and consent are explicit (Silverman, 2011; Weiler and Black, 2015). Across these streams, calls for transparency and reflexivity suggest that naming limits and uncertainties typically strengthens the warrant, since it clarifies where disagreement lies and what cannot be shown (Harrison, 2013; DeSilvey, 2017)

Ethics forms part of the evidential basis. Permission, provenance and scope help to determine what counts as a credible public claim alongside the material record. Heritage and museum scholarship shows that who may speak, where the speaking occurs, and how a topic is framed shape the quality of knowledge as much as the evidence itself (Smith, 2006; Smith, 2012; Harrison, 2013; Dudley, 2012). Work on knowledge sovereignty reaches the same conclusion, treating consent and attribution as elements of the claim because they position the speaker within relations of authority and responsibility (Christen, 2012). Visitor-focused studies report that transparency about sources, limits and uncertainty tends to increase trust, since audiences can see how knowledge has been assembled rather than only what is asserted (Silverman, 2011; DeSilvey, 2017).

Seen through this lens, long-running debates are reframed. Rather than opposing a pure backstage to a front stage, scholarship treats authenticity as emerging when the work of staging is made legible, for example which rules, repairs and protocols organise visibility in a given place, and when limits are stated rather than left implicit (Kirshenblatt-Gimblett, 1998; Smith, 2006; Harrison, 2013). The same framing moderates the tension between affect and argument. Felt connection is valuable, yet it rarely endures without visible warrant; signalling sources,

permissions and uncertainties turns feeling into a justified account that can be retold (Bruner, 1994; Wang, 1999; Ham, 2016; Falk and Dierking, 2013). Therefore, simply giving audiences more access does not automatically make something more “authentic.” Authenticity comes from sound procedure, not sheer volume of access.

This section has synthesised work on authenticity across heritage, tourism and museum studies. The literature shows that recognition is pre-shaped by branding, the tourist gaze and authorised discourse, while authenticity is produced in practice when sources, permissions and limits are made visible and delivery fits place and audience. It also indicates that credibility is tied to procedure rather than to volume of access, a position consistent with plural, locally interpreted criteria.

2.7 Synthesis Theoretical Framework and Summary of Chapter 2

The chapter establishes a conceptual architecture where the work of interpretive tour guide which is positioned as the dynamic, central mechanism for achieving authenticity. This alignment is fundamentally procedural, illustrating how the core activity must negotiate challenging external constraints by leveraging specific internal resources. The concepts cohere into a holistic model that explains the ethical and practical complexities of constructing credible heritage narratives. Figure 2.1 illustrates the flow from external constraints through supporting mechanisms to the desired outcome of authenticity.

Figure 1.1 Constructing Narrative Authenticity

Source: Author's own elaboration.

The four core concepts align across four distinct stages: External Context and Constraints, Core Process, Supporting Mechanisms and Resources, and the Desired Outcome that detail the necessary conditions and actions for successful heritage interpretation.

I. Establishing the Context and Constraint

The process begins by defining the complex environment in which heritage work takes place. This environment is characterized by two key, interdependent concepts that act as necessary constraints on the interpreter:

1. **Heritage as a Contested Field:** This concept serves as the overarching frame, acknowledging that heritage is not a static collection of objects but a dynamic, political, and social process. Value is assigned through negotiation, often involving unequal power dynamics among institutions, experts, and the public. This inherently contested nature demands that any interpretive act be ethical, accountable, and transparent. It means the interpreter cannot rely on a single, authoritative truth but must navigate a plurality of viewpoints. This contestability directly necessitates the need for a procedural authenticity.

2. Destination Imaging & AHD: These are the pre-configured expectations that emerge from the contested field. Destination imaging involves the market-driven branding, media representations, and the 'tourist gaze' (including Orientalism or Self-Orientalism) that pre-shape what visitors *expect* to see and what they will accept as "authentic" on site. AHDs simplify, generalize, and often romanticize the heritage, creating a pressure toward "safe" or essentialist narratives. The core challenge for the interpreter is to acknowledge and manage these existing images while enriching them with locally grounded, situated explanation.

II. The Core Activity: Interpretation as Mediation

The constraints from Section I define the vital role of the central concept:

3. Interpretation (Communicative & Narrative Practice): This is the core process—the active, intentional craft of translating information into meaning through themes, dialogue, and ethical judgment, governed by the TORE Principles (Thematic, Organized, Relevant, Enjoyable). Interpretation acts as the mediating force. It takes the simplified, pre-configured images from Destination Imaging and, using its thematic and organizational structure, thicken them with nuance drawn from the complexities of the Contested Field. However, to do this successfully, interpretation must be powered by the two essential internal resources.

III. Supporting Mechanisms and Resources

The credibility and effectiveness of Interpretation depend entirely on two complementary resources that supply the necessary warrant and technique:

4. Social Capital & Informal Learning: This is the enabling mechanism that sustains the interpreter's ethical practice. It represents the crucial resources (trust, information, professional consent) embedded in the guide's social and professional networks (bonding, bridging, and linking ties). Social capital is vital because it provides the Warrant (access to archival sources, peer consensus) and the Licence (institutional and community permission) needed to tell complex, challenging, or non-authorised stories. This mechanism ensures that the narrative produced by Interpretation is well-grounded, defensible, and has the necessary ethical backing to resist pressure from simplistic Destination Imaging.

5. Sensory Engagement: This is the tactical toolkit that provides the technique for powerful delivery. This concept focuses on how embodied, multi-sensory encounters and interpretive scaffolds (like objects, then-and-now photos, or digital aids) are used strategically during interpretation. Its role is to focus audience attention, deepen affective connection, and improve memory encoding of the thematic material. It supports the narrative of Interpretation by making abstract concepts tangible and emotionally resonant, ensuring the message is effectively received and remembered.

IV. The Desired Outcome

The successful, ethical execution of the core activity, supported by its mechanisms, results in the thesis's ultimate objective:

6. Authenticity: This is the procedural outcome, reframed from an intrinsic quality (is the place "truly old"?) to an emergent product of defensible practice. Authenticity is achieved when Interpretation succeeds in making its sources, permissions, and uncertainties visible to the audience. This demonstration of sound procedure—showing how the knowledge was assembled which is what generates credibility. It means that the narrative, even if it incorporates elements of staging or performance, is deemed authentic because its underlying warrant, secured through social capital, is transparently communicated to an audience whose expectations were initially shaped by Destination Imaging. The successful alignment of all five preceding concepts is the engine that generates this form of high-warrant, procedural authenticity.

CHAPTER 3

THE DYNAMICS OF HERITAGE TOURISM

IN INDONESIA

Heritage tourism in Indonesia occupies a critical juncture where international recognition increasingly intersects with locally embedded identities. As one of the most culturally diverse nations, Indonesia's heritage comprises multiple layers of history, tradition, and belief systems. Recent designations, particularly UNESCO World Heritage Sites (WHS) status, have drawn global attention to these cultural assets, generating opportunities for increased visibility, funding, and visitor flows. At the same time, these frameworks also pose challenges. The application of global standards can unintentionally simplify complex cultural narratives, privileging forms of representation that align with international expectations but may not fully capture local realities.

This chapter takes a closer look at these dynamics, exploring how international frameworks shape the way Indonesian heritage is preserved and presented. It considers both the benefits and the compromises involved—particularly for local communities who may find their voices sidelined in the name of global visibility.

A central focus of this discussion is the role of tour guides, who serve as key cultural interpreters on the ground. Their work goes beyond reciting historical facts; they actively shape how visitors understand and connect with heritage sites. By adjusting their narratives to suit different audiences and staying grounded in local perspectives, they help ensure that the cultural, spiritual, and community meanings of these sites are not lost in translation.

The chapter also considers how technology is transforming heritage tourism. Tools like virtual exhibitions, mobile apps, and augmented reality are increasingly used to engage younger, tech-

savvy visitors. These innovations can make heritage more accessible and exciting—but they also raise questions about what might be lost in the process. The chapter argues for a thoughtful blend of digital tools and human-led interpretation, showing how the two can work together to deepen engagement without sacrificing authenticity or cultural richness.

3.1 Historical Evolution of Tourism in Indonesia

Indonesia is strategically positioned within Southeast Asia, spanning more than 1.9 million square kilometres. The archipelago stretches across three time zones and connects the Pacific and Indian Oceans. Recognised as the world’s largest archipelagic nation, Indonesia comprises over 17,000 islands, approximately 6,000 of which are inhabited, while the rest remain uninhabited or serve as biodiversity reserves (Statistics Indonesia, 2023).

With a population of around 275 million, Indonesia ranks as the fourth most populous country globally, following China, India, and the United States (World Bank, 2021). The nation’s cultural richness is equally remarkable, with over 1,300 ethnic groups spread across 38 provinces, each contributing distinct traditions, languages, and cultural practices groups (Ananta, Nurvidya Arifin and Sairi Hasbullah, 2018).

Figure 3.1 Map of Indonesia

Source: Adobe Stock, 2024

This geographic and cultural diversity has made Indonesia a historical crossroads of influence. Starting from the seventh century, the region, historically known as Nusantara—meaning "the archipelago"—came under the influence of Hindu and Buddhist kingdoms. These kingdoms profoundly shaped the region's cultural and architectural legacy, with the eighth-century Borobudur Buddhist shrine and the ninth-century Prambanan Hindu temple complex standing as two of the most iconic testaments to this era. Both structures, now UNESCO WHS, reflect the intricate artistry, spiritual depth, and advanced engineering of the Hindu-Buddhist period, serving as enduring symbols of Indonesia's pre-Islamic heritage (Miksic, 2017; Jordaan, 2019).

The rise of Islam in Indonesia began in the 13th century, catalysed by extensive trade networks and cultural exchanges with India and the broader Islamic world. Muslim merchants from Gujarat, as well as traders from Persia and the Middle East, introduced Islamic teachings through their interactions with local communities in coastal trading hubs. The adoption of Islam was further accelerated by Sufi missionaries, who played a critical role in blending Islamic teachings with local cultural and spiritual practices. Their syncretic approach incorporated elements of pre-Islamic animist, Hindu, and Buddhist traditions into Islamic rituals, enabling a smoother cultural transition. For example, *wayang kulit* (shadow puppetry) and *gamelan* music, deeply rooted in Hindu-Buddhist traditions, were adapted to include Islamic narratives, fostering resonance with local populations (Azra, 2004).

By the 15th century, major Islamic sultanates had emerged in key trading centres such as Aceh in Sumatra, Demak in Java, and Ternate and Tidore in the Maluku Islands. These sultanates gradually supplanted Hindu-Buddhist kingdoms like Srivijaya and Majapahit, which had long dominated Indonesia's political and cultural landscape. The Majapahit Empire, one of the last great Hindu-Buddhist powers, declined in the late 15th century due to internal conflicts, the rise of Islamic trading powers, and economic shifts favouring coastal Islamic states. By the early 16th century, the Sultanate of Demak had established itself as a dominant Islamic polity, promoting the construction of mosques and Islamic schools while diminishing the influence of Hindu-Buddhist institutions (Ricklefs, 2012).

The Islamisation of Java's interior, traditionally the heartland of Hindu-Buddhist civilisation, was facilitated through a combination of political consolidation, economic power, and religious adaptation. Rulers like those of Demak extended their influence by replacing Hindu-Buddhist

governance structures with Islamic administrations. This transition led to the gradual disuse of Hindu-Buddhist monuments such as Borobudur and Prambanan, which fell into neglect until their rediscovery and preservation during the colonial period (Miksic, 2011).

Despite the dominance of Islam, Hindu-Buddhist traditions persisted in certain regions. Bali, for instance, became a stronghold of Hindu practices following the fall of Majapahit, while communities in Java and Sumatra retained elements of pre-Islamic spirituality. Today, the cultural legacy of the Hindu-Buddhist era remains integral to Indonesian identity, as reflected in the preservation and reverence of monumental sites like Borobudur and Prambanan, which continue to attract global recognition and scholarly interest as UNESCO WHS (Munoz, 2006). Colonial history in Indonesia began in earnest in the early 17th century with the arrival of the Dutch, who gradually established control over the archipelago and consolidated their rule through the *Vereenigde Oostindische Compagnie* (Dutch East India Company/VOC). A brief interruption occurred between 1811 and 1816, when the British, under the leadership of Sir Thomas Stamford Raffles, administered Java. During this period, Raffles contributed significantly to the documentation of Indonesia's history and culture, notably rediscovering and initiating early preservation efforts for the Borobudur temple complex, which had long fallen into neglect (Drake, 2005).

The colonial era marked the early development of tourism in Indonesia, with the Dutch administration promoting the archipelago as an exotic destination to attract European travellers. By the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Bali became a central focus of these efforts, celebrated for its breathtaking landscapes, unique cultural traditions, and spiritual heritage. The Dutch administration actively cultivated Bali's image as a "paradise," a narrative designed to captivate Western imaginations—a portrayal that continues to shape the island's global reputation today (Picard, 1996; Vickers, 2012).

To institutionalise and expand tourism, the Dutch established the Royal Paket Navigation Company, which spearheaded the development of infrastructure, including Bali's first hotel in 1928. Recognising the economic potential of cultural tourism, the Dutch government implemented measures to preserve and promote Bali's cultural heritage, positioning it as a cornerstone of its tourism strategy (Silver, 2007). This colonial-era foundation laid the groundwork for the modern tourism industry in Bali, merging cultural preservation with commercial interests.

To support tourism, the Dutch developed infrastructure such as transportation networks and accommodations, facilitating travel to the island. These efforts established Bali as the “jewel” of Indonesia’s tourism industry, attracting European visitors captivated by its perceived harmony of natural beauty and cultural depth (Vickers, 2012). However, this development also commodified Balinese culture, reframing traditional practices as performances tailored for tourist consumption. Scholars such as Picard (1996) and Hitchcock, King and Parnwell (2010) have critically examined this phenomenon, highlighting the tensions between cultural preservation and commercialisation.

The colonial-era promotion of Bali laid the groundwork for its enduring status as a cultural tourism hub. The Dutch portrayal of Bali as a harmonious and spiritual destination intertwined its natural beauty with its cultural richness, creating a dual identity that continues to define its appeal in modern tourism narratives (Adams, 1997; Hitchcock, 2001). During the colonial period, Bali emerged as the focal point of tourism, establishing essential infrastructure and narratives that influenced Indonesia’s wider tourism landscape.

However, the approach to tourism in the colonial era often exploited local resources, focusing predominantly on the economic benefits for the colonisers while neglecting the conservation of local cultures and traditions. In Bali specifically, the development of the tourism sector was closely linked to the island's domination by the Dutch, who created state-run enterprises to oversee tourism infrastructure (Silver, 2007). This approach commodified Balinese culture, transforming traditional practices into spectacles tailored for tourist consumption. While this boosted Bali's appeal as a destination, it also raised significant concerns about the erosion of Balinese identity and heritage. These colonial-era dynamics have left a lasting legacy, continuing to influence contemporary debates about sustainable tourism. Today, efforts to balance economic growth with cultural preservation draw on lessons from this history, emphasising the need to protect local identities while fostering tourism that benefits local communities (Warren and Wardana, 2018).

Following Indonesia's independence in 1945, the nation’s tourism sector began to evolve as part of broader efforts to position itself as a modern and independent state. Early initiatives under President Sukarno (1945–1967) focused on rebuilding the nation’s tourism infrastructure using war reparations and international loans. Sukarno’s administration established Natour, a

state-owned company, to build hotels and promote tourism as a symbol of Indonesia's newfound sovereignty (Silver, 2007).

In the 1980s, tourism gained renewed importance as Indonesia sought to diversify its economy. The global decline in oil prices in 1986, coupled with economic stagnation, prompted the government to reduce its dependence on oil exports and focus on alternative sources of revenue (Sugiyarto et al., 2003). Recognising tourism as a key driver of economic growth and foreign exchange, the government prioritised investments in infrastructure and marketing to position Indonesia as a tourist-friendly destination (Judisseno, 2015).

Under President Suharto (1967–1998), tourism underwent a significant transformation. Suharto shifted the focus from state-run tourism enterprises to privatisation, enabling the private corporate sector to capitalise on the industry's potential. Bali, in particular, became a focal point of this transformation, emerging as a global tourist hotspot and a key contributor to the national economy. By the early 1990s, the tourism sector, led by Bali, had become Indonesia's third-largest source of foreign exchange, following oil and agricultural products (Silver, 2007). Suharto's approach leveraged tourism not only as an economic driver but also as a platform for promoting nationalism and showcasing Indonesia's cultural diversity on the world stage.

To stimulate growth, the government introduced a series of reforms to strengthen the tourism industry. These included allowing 100% foreign ownership in tourism-related businesses, offering tax holidays, simplifying licensing procedures for hotels and other facilities, and permitting foreign professionals to work in the sector (Hill, 1997). Such policies were part of broader economic liberalisation efforts aimed at attracting foreign investment and enhancing Indonesia's global competitiveness (Resosudarmo and Kuncoro, 2006). By creating an investor-friendly environment, these reforms successfully expanded tourism infrastructure and services, setting the stage for measurable growth.

A key outcome of these reforms was the resurgence of Bali as a premier tourist destination in the 1980s. Bali began attracting millions of visitors worldwide, solidifying its position as the crown jewel of Indonesia's tourism industry (Pickel-Chevalier and Ketut, 2016). Targeted government initiatives, such as infrastructure development and global promotion campaigns, further bolstered Bali's international appeal. By 1990, tourism had become Indonesia's fourthlargest source of foreign exchange earnings, surpassing traditional commodities like rubber and coffee (Hitchcock, King and Parnwell (2010).

At the heart of Bali's success is the philosophy of *Tri Hita Karana*, which emphasises harmony between humans, nature, and the spiritual realm (Pitana, 2010). This principle not only guides Bali's cultural and environmental management but also underpins its tourism strategies, ensuring a delicate balance between economic growth, cultural preservation, and ecological sustainability. Bali's approach exemplifies integrating traditional values with modern tourism development, solidifying its status as a leading global destination. Hitchcock (2001) further emphasises that the heritage and philosophy of Bali are deeply embedded in the lives of the Balinese people. Rather than being merely a constructed image for external audiences, this authenticity reflects the intrinsic values and identity of the island, rooted in its high culture and spiritual practices.

Data from *Tempo.co* (2023) indicate that international arrivals at Bali's I Gusti Ngurah Rai Airport accounted for 45% of Indonesia's total inbound tourism, underscoring the island's central role in the nation's tourism framework. Beyond its economic contributions, Bali also functions as a cultural ambassador, representing Indonesia's integration of natural beauty and rich heritage to the global community. This distinctive visitor experience underscores Bali's importance in national efforts to promote sustainable and culturally meaningful tourism (Dewi, Rahayu and Wibisana, 2023).

Following Bali's success as a global tourism hub, other regions in Indonesia began to open up for tourism, diversifying the nation's offerings and reducing the over-reliance on Bali as the primary destination. Provinces such as Central Java and Yogyakarta, known for their rich cultural and historical heritage, gained prominence with attractions like the Borobudur and Prambanan temples. Similarly, areas such as Sumatra, with its Lake Toba and East Nusa Tenggara, and Komodo National Park, capitalised on their unique natural and cultural assets to attract international and domestic visitors. These efforts were part of a broader strategy to showcase the diversity of Indonesia's tourism potential, spanning cultural, natural, and adventure tourism (Sumaco and Richardson, 2008).

To support this diversification, the government launched the "Visit Indonesia Year" campaign in 1991, which aimed to promote Indonesia as a multifaceted tourism destination. This campaign, described as a turning point in Indonesia's tourism marketing, highlighted the country's cultural richness and ecological wonders to global audiences (Schansman, 1991). It

marked Indonesia's first major effort to unify its tourism branding under a national framework, targeting international visitors while encouraging domestic travel (Hall, 1994). The campaign successfully increased international tourist arrivals, attracting over 2.5 million visitors in its inaugural year, a significant milestone for Indonesia's tourism industry (Hall and Page, 2012). During this time, Indonesia's tourism industry had been experiencing steady growth, driven by increased international interest and the popularity of tour packages. Tour operators played a pivotal role in this expansion, offering all-inclusive packages that catered to tourists seeking convenience and structured itineraries. Destinations like Bali and Yogyakarta benefitted significantly from these packages, which bundled transportation, accommodation, and guided experiences to iconic sites.

The Asian financial crisis of 1997-1998 marked a significant turning point for Indonesia's tourism sector. The sharp economic downturn led to a steep decline in international arrivals as consumer spending contracted, and perceptions of instability deterred travellers. Small tourism enterprises, particularly in regions like Yogyakarta, struggled to adapt to the sudden drop in demand, with many relying heavily on domestic tourism and discounted tour packages to survive (Prabawa, 2010). Hotels, local homestays, and guesthouses in Bali adapted by focusing on domestic travellers, offering affordable experiences to maintain operations during this challenging period. Despite these hardships, segments of the industry displayed resilience, with tour operators restructuring their offerings to appeal to budget-conscious travellers and leveraging Indonesia's devalued currency to attract regional tourists from neighbouring countries like Malaysia and Singapore (Lew, 1999).

The crisis highlighted vulnerabilities in Indonesia's tourism sector, particularly its overreliance on international markets. This prompted a strategic shift in tourism policies, prioritising diversification and sustainability. Reforms included the deregulation and liberalisation of the airline sector, allowing the entry of low-cost carriers like Lion Air, Adam Air, and Citylink, which significantly boosted domestic tourism by making air travel more affordable and accessible (McCawley, 2015). Parallel to airline reforms, investments in infrastructure—such as upgrading airports in Bali and Jakarta and improving road and port networks—enabled better connectivity to emerging destinations like Lombok, Yogyakarta, and Sumatra, diversifying the tourism landscape beyond Bali (Hampton and Clifton, 2016).

By the early 2000s, these initiatives, coupled with a global economic recovery, spurred the growth of domestic and regional tourism. The government launched campaigns such as "Visit Indonesia Year 2008," building on the success of earlier efforts in 1991. This campaign was pivotal in drawing international tourists while motivating Indonesians to explore their own country. Additionally, regional partnerships within ASEAN, including visa-free agreements, enhanced connectivity with neighbouring countries like Malaysia, Singapore, and Thailand (Nasution, 2002).

Complementing these strategies, Indonesia emphasises its geoparks (Yuliawati, Pribadi and Hadian, 2016; Hutabarat, 2023) and heritage sites (Diarta, 2017; Pradana, Iban and Setyastama, 2020), many of which are recognised by UNESCO. These sites underscore the country's commitment to preserving its natural and cultural heritage while promoting environmental sustainability. Destinations such as Komodo National Park and Borobudur Temple serve as models of sustainable tourism, balancing conservation with economic benefits for local communities (Miksic, 2017; Hidyarko et al., 2021; Candra, Maulida and Zamahsari, 2023).

Adding to the diversity of its tourism attractions, *Desa wisata* (tourism villages) have become a cornerstone of sustainable tourism and rural development in Indonesia (Dewi, 2013; Nugraha and Agustina, 2021). These villages integrate local culture, natural assets, and tourism activities to offer immersive experiences that showcase traditional lifestyles, crafts, and agriculture. This model empowers local communities by creating economic opportunities and fostering sociocultural resilience. Recognised as a priority programme by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, *Desa wisata* decentralises tourism from traditional hotspots like Bali, focusing on community-based initiatives. Villages like Panglipuran in Bali and Nglanggeran in Yogyakarta highlight the success of this approach, with Panglipuran celebrated for its environmental sustainability and Nglanggeran for its eco-tourism and geopark activities (Dewi, 2013; Nugraha and Agustina, 2021).

The rise of halal tourism further exemplifies Indonesia's adaptability in catering to niche markets. This segment appeals to Muslim travellers' needs by aligning services with Islamic principles, strengthening Indonesia's position as a global halal tourism destination. With dedicated halal-certified accommodations, restaurants, and attractions, this sector has continued to grow, reflecting the influence of Indonesia's majority-Muslim population on tourism development (Sumaryadi *et al.*, 2020; Widodo *et al.*, 2022). Marine tourism remains a cornerstone of Indonesia's tourism sector. Iconic destinations like Raja Ampat, Bali, and the

Gili Islands continue to attract millions of visitors annually, not only for leisure but also as hubs for sport tourism. Activities such as diving, surfing, and snorkelling are major draws, reinforcing Indonesia's status as a global leader in marine tourism. These ventures have also been key drivers of regional development, empowering local communities through job creation and promoting sustainable practices in marine conservation (Kinseng et al., 2018; Prasetyo, Filep and Carr, 2023).

The economic growth in Asia during the 2000s, particularly in Southeast Asia, served as a catalyst for expanding tourism markets, with Indonesia positioned as a key beneficiary. This growth, coupled with rapid advancements in digital technology, reshaped the tourism landscape by democratising travel and making it more accessible to a diverse demographic of travellers. Online travel agencies (OTAs) such as Agoda, Traveloka, and international platforms like Expedia revolutionized the way trips were planned and booked. By offering streamlined access to flight tickets, accommodations, and activity bookings, these platforms simplified the travel experience, enhancing convenience and cost-efficiency for users (Chua, Chiu and Chiu, 2020; Tavor, 2024).

Parallel to the rise of OTAs, sharing economy platforms such as Airbnb and Uber further transformed the tourism sector by providing flexible and affordable alternatives to traditional accommodation and transportation services. Airbnb enabled travellers to explore destinations beyond major hotels and urban areas, fostering cultural exchanges and broadening the tourism map. Similarly, Uber's entry into the transportation market disrupted conventional taxi services, offering tourists on-demand and cost-effective mobility. These platforms particularly appealed to millennial and Gen Z travellers, whose preferences align with the flexibility and customisability that these digital tools provide (Patria, Khrisnamurti and Rahtomo, 2020).

In Indonesia, the adoption of region-specific platforms such as Grab and Gojek has been transformative, especially in improving local mobility and accessibility for domestic and regional tourists. These ride-hailing services provide critical last-mile connectivity to destinations across Indonesia's vast archipelago, which is otherwise challenging to navigate. Beyond basic transportation, Gojek and Grab have diversified their products to include food delivery, logistics, and digital payment solutions, further enriching the travel experience for both domestic and international visitors (Chalermpong, 2024). Their impact has been particularly pronounced in urban centres and emerging destinations, where improved mobility has allowed tourists to explore lesser-known attractions, boosting local economies.

The integration of these technological platforms has not only enhanced the efficiency of the tourism sector but also contributed to its sustainability. By reducing barriers to entry, OTAs and sharing economy platforms have enabled small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to participate in the tourism value chain. Local homestays, guesthouses, and independent transportation providers can now reach a global audience, levelling the playing field for rural and urban tourism entrepreneurs (Sigala, 2022).

The economic benefits of these platforms are substantial. By increasing the volume of independent and flexible travel, they stimulate spending across multiple sectors, including accommodations, food and beverage, and local attractions. Moreover, their integration into the broader tourism ecosystem aligns with the preferences of modern travellers, who increasingly prioritise personalised experiences, convenience, and value for money. As a result, these technological advancements have not only expanded the scale of tourism but also contributed to regional economic growth and social inclusion, reinforcing Indonesia's position as a global tourism hub.

By the late 2010s, tourism had firmly established itself as one of Indonesia's primary economic sectors, contributing significantly to GDP, foreign exchange revenues, and employment. In 2019, the sector generated approximately USD 20.6 billion in foreign exchange revenue, making it the second-largest contributor to non-oil-and-gas exports (Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, 2020). Tourism also accounted for 5.7% of GDP and supported over 13 million jobs across industries.

However, the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 disrupted this thriving sector, leading to unprecedented challenges. International travel restrictions caused a dramatic decline in foreign arrivals, with numbers dropping to fewer than 5 million in 2020 compared to over 16 million in 2019 (Kemenparekraf, 2021). The resulting revenue losses had a widespread impact, affecting both large corporations and, more acutely, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). In tourism-dependent regions like Bali, SMEs faced significant hardships, as many businesses relied heavily on international visitors for their survival.

Amid these challenges, domestic tourism emerged as a stabilising force. Campaigns like "Explore Indonesia" and "Wonderful Indonesia" encouraged Indonesians to travel within the country, boosting local economies (Rozanah and Ishqila, 2024). Domestic travel surged, generating over 734 million trips in 2022 (Statistics Indonesia, 2023). Government incentives,

such as subsidies for domestic flights and discounts on accommodations, further supported the sector, mitigating the revenue gap caused by the absence of international visitors.

Infrastructure improvements supported during this period, with enhanced road networks, port facilities, and affordable accommodations in emerging destinations like Labuan Bajo, Lombok, and Borobudur, providing alternatives to traditional hotspots like Bali and Jakarta. E-tourism platforms further facilitated virtual tours and contactless transactions, catering to safety-conscious travellers.

Central to these efforts was the implementation of CHSE (Cleanliness, Health, Safety, and Environment) certifications, a government initiative aimed at rebuilding traveller confidence during the COVID-19 pandemic (Tandilino and Rero, 2022). CHSE certifications ensure tourism businesses adhere to global health and safety standards, covering accommodations, restaurants, tourist attractions, and transportation services. By standardising rigorous hygiene, sanitation, and environmental protocols, the programme addressed immediate health concerns while committing to long-term improvements in tourism quality and safety. The certifications had a significant impact. They reassured tourists, making safety a decisive factor in travel decisions, and supported businesses, particularly SMEs, by providing tools to adapt to the new normal. Moreover, the initiative bolstered Indonesia's global image as a safe and reliable destination, aiding the recovery of international tourism. Bali, as a leading destination, became a focal point of the CHSE initiative. By mid-2021, over 1,000 establishments had received certifications, boosting traveller confidence and driving a gradual increase in domestic tourism during the second half of the year (Yuliono, Sudiarta and Mananda, 2022).

Building on the resilience demonstrated during the pandemic, Indonesia's tourism strategies have become instrumental in driving recovery and ensuring long-term growth. Central to these efforts are the National Tourism Strategic Area (*Kawasan Strategis Pariwisata Nasional* - KSPN) programme and the Super Priority Destinations (SPD) initiative, which were designed to revitalise the industry while promoting sustainability. The KSPN programme, formalised under Government Regulation No. 50 of 2011, focuses on improving infrastructure, accessibility, and marketing in designated tourism areas. Meanwhile, the SPD initiative, established through Presidential Regulation No. 18 of 2020, accelerates development in five key destinations: Lake Toba, Borobudur, Mandalika, Labuan Bajo, and Likupang. These destinations, selected for their unique cultural and natural attractions, aim to diversify

Indonesia's tourism offerings and reduce the nation's reliance on Bali by fostering the creation of "New Balis." Furthermore, the initiative highlights the importance of community involvement and supports Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), ensuring that the economic benefits of tourism are equitably distributed.

These strategic programmes have positioned Indonesia to leverage its diverse cultural and natural heritage as key drivers of tourism development. The focus on destinations such as Borobudur and Lake Toba highlights Indonesia's commitment to integrating heritage preservation with economic growth. For instance, Borobudur, a UNESCO World Heritage Site, not only serves as a cultural symbol but also attracts millions of tourists annually, contributing significantly to local and national economies. Meanwhile, Lake Toba, the world's largest volcanic lake, is being developed with sustainable practices to ensure its environmental integrity while fostering local community engagement.

This emphasis on leveraging heritage as a cornerstone of tourism aligns with Indonesia's broader strategy to establish itself as a global leader in cultural and heritage tourism. With over 1,300 ethnic groups, each contributing distinct traditions, languages, and practices, Indonesia's rich historical and cultural tapestry provides a unique competitive advantage. Iconic sites like Prambanan and Borobudur, along with intangible heritage such as traditional dance, music, and craftsmanship, are central to the nation's efforts to attract both domestic and international visitors. These initiatives not only boost economic growth but also play a crucial role in preserving and promoting Indonesia's heritage for future generations.

By 2023, Indonesia's tourism sector showed remarkable resilience. International arrivals rebounded to approximately 11.68 million, while domestic tourism generated employment and revitalised small businesses. Domestic tourism's critical role was underscored by its contribution of IDR 1,008 trillion to the economy in 2022, equivalent to 4.8% of national economic output, and projections suggest its annual contribution will reach IDR 1,828 trillion by 2034 (WTTC, 2023).

3.2 Exploring Indonesia's Heritage Tourism

Heritage tourism plays a crucial role in Indonesia's cultural and economic landscape, capitalising on the country's rich historical narratives, diverse ecosystems, and cultural variety. Home to over 300 ethnic groups and thousands of islands, Indonesia boasts an array of cultural

and natural heritage sites, from ancient temples and vibrant traditions to biodiverse environments. These elements not only foster national pride but also serve as strategic assets for tourism development.

Significant sites like the UNESCO-listed Borobudur and Prambanan temples draw millions of visitors each year, acting as major cultural landmarks and economic drivers. Similarly, natural and urban heritage sites, including Komodo National Park and Jakarta's Kota Tua, enhance Indonesia's appeal to a broad spectrum of tourists by blending ecological uniqueness with cultural richness. These areas are pivotal in promoting national identity and international cultural connections, while urban revitalization efforts in places like Bandung's Braga Street showcase how heritage tourism can drive economic revitalization by merging cultural preservation with development.

Additionally, community-driven tourism initiatives in rural locales like Tana Toraja highlight the potential for local traditions to bolster the economy and preserve cultural heritage. Such initiatives exemplify the integration of heritage into Indonesia's economic strategy, involving complex policymaking and balancing of interests among various stakeholders, including local communities and international organizations. This section delves into the intricate dynamics of heritage tourism in Indonesia, emphasising the interplay between local, national, and global influences.

3.2.1 Cultural and Philosophical Dimensions of Heritage in Indonesia

Heritage in Indonesia, akin to that of broader Southeast Asia, encapsulates a dynamic interplay of cultural, historical, social, and spiritual dimensions, reflecting a region shaped by centuries of interaction between local traditions and external influences (Hitchcock, King, and Parnwell, 2010). Contrasting with the static interpretations prevalent in Western discourse, which predominantly emphasise preservation, Southeast Asian heritage is characterised by its holistic and evolving nature, deeply embedded in communal practices and socio-political realities. Graham (2002) and Howard (2003) argue that heritage should not be perceived as a static legacy but rather as a dynamic resource that is continuously renegotiated to align with contemporary needs and aspirations.

As mentioned in Chapter 2, these philosophies and worldviews of Southeast Asian cultures have been deeply shaped by Hindu and Buddhist traditions, particularly before the 16th century, when traders and visitors from India introduced these spiritual frameworks. These traditions emphasise principles such as impermanence, interconnectedness, and the holistic integration of the natural and spiritual realms, which continue to underpin the region's cultural attitudes and heritage practices (Daniels, 1998). Mackee (2009) highlights how these philosophies, especially the Buddhist concepts of dependent origination and impermanence, have influenced approaches to conserving cultural heritage, positioning it as a dynamic rather than static legacy. Similarly, Shimizu (2023) notes that Southeast Asian societies adopted these ideas to understand the interconnectedness of people, nature, and the divine, fostering a worldview that prioritises balance and harmony.

This philosophical foundation has significantly influenced how Southeast Asian cultures manage and interpret their heritage. (MacKee, 2013) points out that traditional conservation practices often integrate these principles, ensuring that heritage remains relevant to contemporary communities while honouring its spiritual essence. By prioritising holistic and dynamic approaches, Southeast Asia presents a unique model of heritage management that emphasises continuity, relevance, and the deep interconnection between people, culture, and the environment.

In Indonesia, the connection between heritage and cultural identity is prominently reflected through both linguistic and cultural frameworks. The Indonesian concept of heritage is profoundly shaped by the philosophy encapsulated in the Arabic word *waris* (meaning heir), which denotes a localised understanding of heritage as a communal legacy transmitted across generations. In contrast to the Western emphasis on preserving physical artifacts, the Southeast Asian approach to heritage is more fluid and inclusive, prioritizing the transmission of practices, beliefs, and identities. This perspective views heritage not merely as a static inheritance from the past but as a living, evolving entity that embodies cultural, historical, and spiritual values. Consequently, this dynamic view ensures that heritage remains relevant across generations, adapting to ongoing cultural and societal shifts while preserving its fundamental essence.

A key challenge in interpreting heritage across cultures lies in the official terminology used within Southeast Asian nations. These terms often do not align strictly with Western notions of heritage, even though dictionaries may translate them as such. Hitchcock, King, and Parnwell

(2011) observe that these linguistic nuances reflect broader differences in how heritage is understood and valued, underscoring the contextual specificity of the concept in Southeast Asia. Illustrating this dynamic perspective is evident in practices like Balinese Hinduism. The *Tri Hita Karana* philosophy exemplifies this interconnectedness, emphasising harmony among people, nature, and the spiritual realm. This principle guides the communal irrigation system known as *subak*, where water temples serve both agricultural and spiritual purposes. This integration of environmental stewardship and cultural rituals highlights a dynamic relationship between heritage and the natural world, reflecting the region's emphasis on adaptability and interdependence (MacKee, 2009; Daniels, 1998).

The transmission of practices, beliefs, and identities is another hallmark of Southeast Asian heritage. Indonesia's *wayang* (shadow puppet) tradition, rooted in Hindu-Buddhist epics like the *Mahabharata* and *Ramayana*, has been adapted to incorporate local stories and contemporary issues, ensuring its relevance across generations. Unlike the static preservation of puppets as artefacts, the *wayang* tradition thrives as a performative and educational practice, embodying the fluid and living nature of heritage (Koentjaraningrat, 1985; Reid, 2019).

Unlike the Western focus on material artefacts, *Warisan* reflects the Southeast Asian perspective of heritage as a living and evolving legacy. This inclusive framing ensures that cultural practices, beliefs, and identities remain integral to heritage management, further illustrating the contextual specificity of how heritage is valued in the region (Hitchcock, King and Parnwell, 2010). For instance, the UNESCO recognition of *Batik* as an intangible cultural heritage underscores its role beyond textile art, serving as a medium for transmitting identity, regional pride, and intergenerational knowledge.

Furthermore, the philosophical approach to heritage aligns with the cultural ethos of community-centred practices, where communal identity serves as the cornerstone of societal organisation. This perspective distinguishes itself from the individualism prioritised in Western traditions, emphasising that individuals are inherently part of larger social units, such as families, communities, and the state. Actions and decisions are guided by collective responsibility and the maintenance of social harmony, which take precedence over individual rights and autonomy (Inoguchi and Newman, 1997). This communitarian ethos, deeply embedded in Asian cultures, fosters social cohesion and stability by prioritising collective welfare over personal interests. Core values such as self-discipline, sacrifice for the greater

good, and respect for familial and societal bonds underpin this framework, shaping social behaviour, governance, and economic practices.

In Southeast Asia, the emphasis on communal identity is deeply rooted in local traditions that prioritise mutual cooperation. A notable example is Indonesia's concept of “*gotong royong*”, which translates to "working together." As a cornerstone of Indonesian social philosophy, *gotong royong* embodies the idea that collective effort yields shared benefits. Rooted in the communal ethos of traditional village life, it emphasises cooperation, solidarity, and shared responsibility within communities, reflecting broader Southeast Asian cultural values that favour communal identity over individualism (Geertz, 1969; Bowen, 2003).

Historically, *gotong royong* involved voluntary community efforts to accomplish tasks such as harvesting crops, constructing homes, or organising communal events. This practice was not motivated by monetary exchange but by reciprocity, fostering bonds of trust and interdependence among community members (Koentjaraningrat, 1985). Its enduring relevance illustrates how traditional mutual support and cooperation values continue to shape social and cultural life in Indonesia and the broader Southeast Asian region.

3.2.2 Balancing Local Values and Global Recognition

Although Indonesia's approach to heritage is fluid, inclusive, and deeply rooted in communal traditions, it faces significant challenges in achieving global recognition, particularly within frameworks such as UNESCO's Outstanding Universal Value (OUV) criteria. For countries like Indonesia, UNESCO recognition serves as a global acknowledgement of cultural and natural wealth, boosting international standing while enhancing tourism potential. The process of attaining UNESCO World Heritage status is a deeply political and competitive endeavour that reflects the intersection of international prestige, national governance, and local realities.

Transforming vibrant, dynamic local places into fixed heritage sites is rarely a neutral process. It is shaped by political calculations, collaboration, conflict, and co-optation (Adams, 2003). Nationally, government priorities shape heritage policies to align with economic and cultural objectives, framing heritage as both a resource and a symbol of national identity. Locally, diverse stakeholders—including community members, activists, and private interests—often contest these designations, leading to tensions over resource allocation, cultural representation, and community involvement (Kausar and Gunawan, 2018).

To better understand the scope and significance of Indonesia's globally recognised heritage, it is essential to examine its UNESCO World Heritage sites. These sites not only reflect the nation's rich cultural and natural diversity but also highlight the complexities of balancing global recognition with local values and sustainable management.

Table 3.1 UNESCO World Heritage Sites in Indonesia

Site Name	Category	Year of Tentative List Inclusion	Key Features
Komodo National Park	Inscribed	1991	Known for Komodo dragons, marine biodiversity, and coral reefs.
Borobudur Temple Compounds	Inscribed	1991	A Buddhist temple complex and one of the largest in the world.
Prambanan Temple Compounds	Inscribed	1991	A Hindu temple complex, renowned for its stunning architecture and cultural significance.
Sangiran Early Man Site	Inscribed	1996	Significant archaeological site for understanding early human evolution.
Ujung Kulon National Park	Inscribed	1991	Home to the endangered Javan rhinoceros and diverse ecosystems.
Taman Nasional Lorentz	Inscribed	1999	One of the largest protected areas in Southeast Asia, rich in biodiversity and cultural significance.
Toba Caldera	Tentative (2015)	2015	Largest volcanic lake in the world, significant for geological and cultural studies.
Cultural Landscape of Bali	Tentative (2012)	2012	Recognises the traditional Subak irrigation system and cultural landscapes in Bali.
Lorentz National Park	Tentative (2004)	2004	Biodiverse park, home to rare species, and culturally significant for local indigenous groups.
Banda Islands	Tentative (2019)	2019	Historical spice trade centre with rich marine biodiversity.
Bukit Duabelas National Park	Tentative (2017)	2017	Important for the indigenous Suku Anak Dalam community and rainforest ecosystems.
Merapi Volcano	Tentative (2004)	2004	An active volcano with geological and cultural importance.
Belitung Island	Tentative (2014)	2014	Known for its unique ecosystem and historical mining industry.

Raja Ampat Islands	Tentative (2015)	2015	Marine biodiversity hotspot with pristine coral reefs.
Wakatobi National Park	Tentative (2014)	2014	Marine conservation area with rich coral reefs and marine life.
Spice Route of Indonesia	Tentative (2018)	2018	Historical trade route for spices with cultural landmarks across several Indonesian islands.
Raja Ampat Islands	Tentative (2020)	2020	Recognised for marine biodiversity and pristine coral reefs.
The Spice Islands of Ternate & Tidore	Tentative (2020)	2020	Famous for their role in the global spice trade and local cultural significance.
The Cultural Landscape of Toraja	Tentative (2020)	2020	Known for unique burial rites and traditional Toraja architecture.

Source: UNESCO, 2023

Beyond its recognised WHS, Indonesia is actively pursuing the inscription of additional locations on UNESCO’s tentative list. This initiative underscores the country’s commitment to preserving its diverse cultural and natural heritage while expanding its portfolio of globally recognised attractions. These proposed sites highlight Indonesia’s dedication to showcasing the richness of its history, ecosystems, and traditions, further solidifying its status as a premier destination for tourism.

Table 3.2 UNESCO Tentative Sites World Heritage Sites in Indonesia

Site Name	Category	Year of Inscription	Description
Komodo National Park	Natural	1991	Home to the endangered Komodo dragon, featuring diverse ecosystems, marine biodiversity, and coral reefs.
Borobudur Temple Compounds	Cultural	1991	A monumental Buddhist temple complex, the largest in the world, showcasing intricate carvings and spiritual significance.
Prambanan Temple Compounds	Cultural	1991	A 9th-century Hindu temple complex, famous for its towering structures and sculptural reliefs depicting Hindu mythology.
Sangiran Early Man Site	Cultural	1996	An archaeological site offering evidence of early human evolution, significant for the discovery of prehistoric fossils.

Ujung Kulon National Park	Natural	1991	A UNESCO biosphere reserve, home to the critically endangered Javan rhinoceros and various ecosystems.
Taman Nasional Lorentz	Natural	1999	A vast, biodiverse park, known for its ecological significance, ranging from glaciers to tropical rainforests.
Cultural Landscape of Bali	Cultural	2012	Recognises Bali's Subak system, a traditional irrigation technique that shapes the island's agricultural and cultural landscapes.
Toba Caldera	Natural	2021	The world's largest volcanic lake is significant for its geological and cultural importance and biodiversity.
Gunung Leuser National Park	Natural	2004	Part of the Tropical Rainforest Heritage of Sumatra, known for its biodiversity and being a habitat for orangutans.
Krakatau	Natural	1991	The site of one of the world's most famous volcanic eruptions features the still-active Krakatau volcano and its surrounding islands.
Sunda Strait	Natural	1991	The region surrounding the Sunda Strait is significant for volcanic activities and marine biodiversity.

Source: UNESCO, 2023

At the international level, UNESCO recognition serves as a crucial marker of geopolitical status, compelling nations to vie for places on the WHS list. This pursuit is not merely about enhancing a nation's global image; it demonstrates a commitment to cultural and environmental stewardship. However, these designations are deeply intertwined with geopolitical strategies and domestic agendas, underscoring that heritage recognition is far from a neutral acknowledgement of cultural or natural significance.

In Indonesia, UNESCO recognition functions as both a catalyst for tourism and a symbol of national leadership in heritage conservation. It elevates Indonesia's cultural profile on the global stage while contributing to economic development through increased visitor flows. However, such recognition often demands alignment with dominant historical narratives that serve state objectives, which can sideline alternative or local perspectives (Graham & Howard, 2008). This makes UNESCO designation not just a cultural milestone, but also a political tool that reflects the state's aspiration for international legitimacy and soft power.

The case of Jakarta's Kota Tua exemplifies these tensions. Between 2015 and 2018, efforts to restore the area's colonial-era architecture faced numerous challenges, including inadequate funding, fragmented governance, and conflicting stakeholder priorities. While the central government pursued UNESCO compliance to bolster Indonesia's international standing, local actors were more concerned with reconciling heritage preservation with community needs and livelihoods (Nugteren, 2020). This case illustrates how global frameworks, when translated into local contexts, may create dissonance between national aspirations and on-the-ground realities.

Understanding this dynamic is important because it reveals that heritage governance is not a neutral or technocratic endeavour. Rather, it is embedded in complex power relations between international bodies, the state, and local stakeholders. The Kota Tua case underscores a central argument of this thesis: that heritage recognition—especially in postcolonial contexts—is often shaped by geopolitical ambition and top-down planning, which can lead to disjointed or contested outcomes at the community level. By highlighting this tension, the paragraph contributes to a more critical understanding of how global heritage politics operate in practice.

The contestation of World Heritage designations in Indonesia mirrors broader global trends in heritage management. As Hitchcock, King, and Parnwell (2010) discuss, marketing heritage sites as unique tourism destinations frequently leads to the creation of "cultural otherness," which reinforces national identities but can sideline the very communities whose traditions sustain these sites. This tension highlights a significant challenge in managing global heritage where the strategies designed to attract international tourists may clash with the preservation of authentic cultural expressions.

Moreover, heritage practices in Indonesia, like those in many Southeast Asian countries, often respond to external influences, balancing local authenticity with the demands of global recognition (Hampton and Clifton, 2016). The pursuit of UNESCO designation underscores national ambitions to enhance cultural prestige and spur economic growth. However, these objectives sometimes conflict with local community realities. For example, Adams (2010) points out how Tana Toraja's funeral ceremonies, originally rooted in Torajan cosmology, have been transformed into cultural spectacles for tourists, raising concerns about the authenticity and sustainability of such practices.

Furthermore, sites such as Borobudur and Prambanan—both designated as UNESCO World Heritage Sites—are often subject to reinterpretation processes that align their meanings with

international heritage discourses. These “international narratives” refer to globally accepted frameworks promoted by institutions like UNESCO, which tend to prioritise universal values such as architectural grandeur, historical continuity, or artistic achievement over more locally rooted meanings. To meet the expectations of these frameworks, national authorities often adapt the presentation and interpretation of heritage sites to emphasise attributes that resonate with global audiences, such as aesthetic appeal or tourism potential. This process is driven by the desire to secure and maintain global recognition, attract international tourism, and assert cultural legitimacy on the world stage.

However, such adaptations can marginalise or obscure the indigenous or spiritual significance of these sites. In the case of Borobudur, while UNESCO celebrates the monument as a masterpiece of Buddhist architecture and an example of world heritage, this framing tends to overshadow its ongoing spiritual importance to Buddhist communities, both local and international. The Indonesian government reinforces this shift by promoting Borobudur primarily as a cultural and economic asset—emphasising its role in attracting tourists rather than its function as a sacred site. This secular framing, aligned with UNESCO’s non-religious approach to heritage classification, risks erasing the living, spiritual dimensions of the monument (Salazar, 2010).

Such re-framings illustrate a broader concern in critical heritage studies: global recognition often comes with implicit expectations to conform to dominant narratives that may not fully reflect local values or lived experiences. As a result, the spiritual or community-based meanings of heritage sites may be diluted in favour of more “marketable” or “internationally legible” interpretations.

Similarly, Bali’s Subak irrigation system, recognised as a model of sustainable land management, underscores another dimension of this tension. While its designation by UNESCO celebrates the system's environmental sustainability, the local spiritual and communal aspects that are pivotal to its operation are often underrepresented in official narratives. This oversight exemplifies how the international acclaim of a heritage site can simplify its rich, multifaceted cultural significance into a single dimension focused on practical utility rather than cultural depth (Timothy, 2017).

This secular framing by UNESCO and the consequent promotion tactics by local authorities illustrate a critical tension between the preservation of a site’s intrinsic spiritual value and the

economic incentives of tourism. Such dynamics reveal the complex interplay between preserving authentic cultural expressions and meeting international heritage criteria, often at the expense of the very elements that constitute the essence of these historical sites.

Achieving a balance between preserving local cultural identities and adapting to global influences remains a critical and complex challenge (King, 2020; Goh, 2022). The recontextualization of heritage sites often results in the displacement and gentrification of local communities, underscoring the need for ongoing negotiations and reinterpretations to align with UNESCO's criteria. These criteria frequently emphasise global appeal and prioritise the aesthetic and monumental aspects of heritage, often at the expense of local historical and cultural significance (Yusuf, 2008; Timothy, 2017).

The pressure to meet international benchmarks commonly prioritises tourism and economic benefits, leading to socio-political tensions. This dynamic is evident at Borobudur, where tourism-driven development has led to gentrification, displacing long-standing residents and altering the site's cultural fabric (Salazar, 2012; Sandholz, 2017). A similar situation has occurred in Jakarta's Kota Tua, where efforts to comply with UNESCO standards have favoured aesthetic and commercial redevelopment over the well-being of local residents and businesses. This strategy has significantly eroded Kota Tua's authentic character, transforming it into a landscape designed predominantly for tourism (Nugteren, 2020).

Additionally, the revitalisation of Braga Street in Bandung highlights the adverse effects of prioritising tourism over community needs. Restoration projects aimed at preserving the street's architectural character and boosting tourism have resulted in increased property values and commercialisation, displacing longstanding businesses and residents. This pattern echoes the developments observed in Kota Tua and Borobudur, marginalising the lived experiences of local communities and reshaping Braga into a space tailored for external consumption (Soewarno, Hidjaz and Virdianti, 2018). These transformations illustrate the inherent tensions in heritage revitalisation, where the drive for global recognition and economic returns often compromises local identity and agency (Sakina, 2020).

Continuing with this theme, Indonesia's approach to preserving its colonial heritage further demonstrates the complex interplay between historical preservation and modern demands. The case of Sawahlunto, a former coal mining town now listed as a UNESCO World Heritage site, highlights these dynamics vividly. Celebrated for its historical mining heritage, Sawahlunto is

being transformed into a hub for education and tourism. However, crafting a historical narrative that neither romanticises the colonial past nor overlooks the impact of mining on local communities presents significant challenges, underscoring the delicate balance required in heritage management (Syafri et al., 2020).

In the Ngadha and Manggarai regions of Flores, heritage preservation efforts have transformed colonial legacies into tools of empowerment. Sudarmadi (2014) details how local communities revitalise traditional architecture and cultural practices while critically addressing colonial exploitation. These efforts not only reclaim historical agency but also enhance economic opportunities through cultural tourism, offering a model for integrating heritage preservation with community empowerment.

Similarly, in Banda Aceh, the approach to heritage post-disaster reflects unique challenges in reconciling local heritage definitions with global standards, the post-tsunami reconstruction in Banda Aceh illustrates the tensions between local definitions of heritage and the AHD. The local community and government, despite initial resistance from conservation authorities, now redefine tsunami-related sites like the Tsunami Museum and Kapal Apung as heritage landmarks. These sites are recognised for their significant historical narratives, embodying a critical local history that does not necessarily align with traditional global heritage criteria (Dewi et al., 2019).

This negotiation process between local and global heritage discourses highlights a dynamic interplay that influences how heritage is ultimately recognised and preserved. It underscores the ongoing dialogue necessary to ensure that local histories are integrated into the broader narrative of world heritage, not overshadowed by global standards. This engagement between local relevance and international heritage frameworks is crucial for a balanced and respectful preservation of cultural identity.

Amid these challenges, some initiatives have successfully aligned global frameworks with local realities in Indonesia. Communities are actively reclaiming and redefining their heritage in response to these changes. These activities resist cultural homogenisation and underscore the importance of local agency in preserving cultural diversity. For example, in Lasem, community-led initiatives have been pivotal in preserving the authenticity of Chinese-Javanese heritage, demonstrating a dynamic model of engagement (Wulandari & Baiquni, 2024; Graham and Howard, 2008). These efforts focus on leveraging the community's unique cultural assets to

foster economic empowerment and resilience through heritage tourism. The community employs a social resilience strategy encompassing coping, adaptive, and transformative capacities, which collectively enhance the management and tourism potential of their heritage sites. For instance, the coping capacity involves using local resources and social networks to maintain the integrity of ancient Chinese houses, transforming them into active tourism sites. The adaptive capacity has led to the development of robust networks with local and external stakeholders, enhancing Lasem's visibility and appealing to a broader audience. Finally, the transformative capacity involves diversifying economic activities and integrating technological advancements for marketing, ensuring that heritage practices are both preserved and relevant in today's tourism market.

Moreover, Picard's observation (2008) of Bali's local communities highlights their proactive reclamation of temple ceremony narratives, an effort crucial for preserving cultural authenticity and resilience. These communities have reintegrated traditional elements that had been marginalized, potentially due to commercialization pressures. Such reclamation is vital in maintaining the spiritual and cultural integrity of these ceremonies, countering the dilution of Bali's cultural expressions by tourism demands. This process empowers local communities, allowing them to assert control over their cultural representation and ensuring their traditions remain true to their original significance. Moreover, by reinforcing these practices, Bali's communities help sustain their cultural heritage for future generations, balancing the development of tourism with cultural preservation. Picard's research underscores the crucial role of local agency in the global heritage landscape, illustrating how communities can maintain cultural authenticity while engaging with international tourists. This ongoing effort not only preserves traditional practices but also enriches the cultural experience for visitors, ensuring heritage sites and practices retain their intended meanings and benefits for the local community.

Adding depth to these examples, the transformation of Kotagede in Yogyakarta post the 2006 earthquake highlights how local communities can redefine their heritage narrative, integrating contemporary challenges into their cultural storytelling. This proactive approach not only created new economic opportunities but also enhanced the site's appeal as a unique tourism destination, aligning with the potential for local narratives to gain broader recognition. The community-driven tourism has developed heritage walks that offer packages allowing tourists to experience the real life and living heritage of Yogyakarta (Rosilawati, Mulawarman and Mulyantari, 2019).

This community-based approach not only revitalizes the local economy but also reinforces the authenticity of the heritage experience. Tourists are given a unique opportunity to engage directly with the history and culture of Kotagede through guided walks that explore ancient sites, local crafts, and daily community activities. This direct interaction fosters a deeper understanding and appreciation of the local culture, which is often overshadowed by more prominent tourist destinations (Rindasih, Izzudin and Baiquni, 2022).

These examples from Lasem, Bali, and Kotagede illustrate the powerful potential of local narratives to bridge with global recognition. By integrating local knowledge and practices into heritage management, these communities not only protect their cultural legacy but also transform it into a living, evolving testament to their history and identity. This approach challenges conventional heritage management practices and highlights the importance of community-driven initiatives in the global heritage landscape.

Thus, the concerted efforts in these regions showcase how Indonesia's heritage sites can serve as dynamic spaces where cultural authenticity is preserved while actively engaging with the challenges and opportunities of the global heritage landscape. These initiatives ensure that heritage management remains inclusive and representative of the nation's rich cultural tapestry, effectively marrying local engagement with global appeal.

Figure 3.2 illustrates the multi-scalar dynamics of UNESCO heritage recognition in Indonesia, highlighting tensions between international frameworks, national strategies, and local community realities. Case examples such as Kota Tua, Borobudur, Subak, and Lasem demonstrate how global recognition both empowers and marginalises local heritage practices.

Figure 3.2 Tensions in UNESCO Heritage Recognition in Indonesia

Source: Author's own elaboration.

3.2.3 Tour Guides as Interpreters of Indonesia's Heritage

Tour guides are integral to mediating the influence of global heritage standards, particularly those advanced by international organisations such as UNESCO (Salazar, 2005, 2007; Weiler & Ham, 2015). They play a pivotal role in safeguarding the authenticity and cultural significance of Indonesian heritage tourism amid the pressures of standardised global narratives (Reisinger & Steiner, 2006; Feldman, 2016). Rather than functioning as passive conveyors of information, tour guides actively negotiate between externally imposed heritage frameworks and locally embedded meanings, thereby helping to ensure that Indonesia's diverse cultural narratives are not diluted or overshadowed by universalising interpretations (Salazar, 2005, 2007).

Situated at the forefront of cultural interpretation, tour guides shape how heritage is perceived and understood by both domestic and international audiences (Weiler & Ham, 2015). Their role extends beyond entertainment or factual explanation; they operate as cultural translators and storytellers, constructing narratives that reflect official histories while also incorporating local identities, values, and lived experiences (Reisinger & Steiner, 2006; Feldman, 2016). In this way, they contribute to the preservation of intangible heritage and community voice, positioning themselves as critical actors in resisting the homogenising tendencies of global heritage tourism (Salazar, 2007; Feldman, 2016). By countering the potential oversimplifications imposed by international heritage frameworks, they enrich the visitor experience with deeper cultural meanings and local significance (Salazar, 2006). This function

is particularly important in contexts where global recognition risks flattening cultural diversity and obscuring the unique meanings embedded in each heritage site across Indonesia (Salazar, 2005, 2007).

The significance of this role is underscored by the dynamic and evolving narratives embedded within Indonesia's heritage, richly woven with myths, folklore, and storytelling traditions. These stories are not static but are complex reflections of the diverse cultural and historical influences that shape each site. For instance, in Tana Toraja, guides utilise local wisdom to enrich their storytelling, weaving narratives that underscore values such as kinship, respect for ancestors, and harmony with nature (Kausar & Gunawan, 2018). Such narratives embody the concept of "Pluriversality," as described by Graham and Howard (2008), where multiple meanings and interpretations continually intersect and are reshaped with each act of recognition and retelling (Lowenthal, 2005). This dynamic storytelling approach ensures that heritage interpretation not only respects but also revitalises the intrinsic cultural values of each location, providing a counterbalance to the universalising tendencies of global heritage criteria.

This interactive dynamic is notably visible in guided tours, where the narratives crafted by tour guides are not merely recitations of historical facts but are deeply influenced by the guides' perspectives, the dynamic interactions with tourists, and the broader sociocultural milieu. Indonesia's heritage sites, with their rich cultural diversity, extensive folklore, religious pluralism, and myriad myths, offer fertile ground for such rich, layered storytelling. These elements contribute profoundly to the personal and communal meanings attributed to these sites, often providing spiritual or mystical interpretations that stand apart from more sanitised, official narratives. This weaving of folklore, historical events, and contemporary realities can, however, lead to what Ashworth and Tunbridge (2000) describe as "heritage dissonance," where the narratives presented are more aligned with visitor expectations than with the authentic perspectives of local communities.

For instance, The Borobudur and Prambanan temple complexes, set within Indonesia's context as the world's largest Muslim-majority nation, exemplify the intricate intersections between religion, heritage, and tourism. These sites not only represent monumental achievements in Buddhist and Hindu architecture but also embody Indonesia's pluralistic religious heritage, shaped by centuries of cultural exchange. Historical shifts, including the repurposing of religious sites, the suppression or adaptation of certain practices under colonial rule, and post-

colonial nation-building policies, have layered these monuments with complex meanings (Timothy & Olsen, 2006).

In the realm of religious tourism, sacred sites are often repositioned as heritage attractions, leading to what Shackley (2001) terms the “commodification of the sacred.” While such framing can broaden accessibility and global visibility, it can also result in the dilution or alteration of traditional narratives to fit the expectations of diverse international audiences (Collins-Kreiner, 2010). In the case of Borobudur and Prambanan, the drive to render them accessible and marketable within global tourism circuits risks oversimplifying their spiritual significance—aligning them more closely with secular heritage discourses and packaging them as easily consumable cultural products (Olsen, 2013). Such processes raise critical questions about how religious meaning is preserved, transformed, or sidelined in the pursuit of international recognition and economic gain.

A poignant illustration of local folklore influencing heritage interpretation can be seen at the Prambanan temple complex. Research by Salazar (2012) highlights how the central Shiva shrine, traditionally housing a statue of the Hindu goddess Durga, is locally identified as *Loro Jonggrang*, a princess from Javanese folklore turned to stone. This narrative coexistence within the same space exemplifies the contentious interplay between global heritage standards and entrenched local traditions, underscoring the challenges and complexities of maintaining cultural authenticity amidst international recognition.

The importance of these multilayered narratives is critical in preserving the authenticity of Indonesia’s heritage sites while also adapting to the evolving demands of tourism and shifting societal expectations. They operate as cultural brokers (Reisinger & Steiner, 2006) and mediators (Feldman, 2016), bridging the gap between the official narratives promoted by institutions such as UNESCO and the lived cultural experiences of local communities (Salazar, 2005, 2007). They must adeptly navigate the delicate balance between engaging visitors and maintaining cultural integrity, crafting stories that not only entertain and educate but also resonate deeply, honouring the richness of Indonesian traditions and fostering meaningful connections with a diverse audience.

The increasing popularity of walking tours and thematic tours in Indonesia, particularly in museums and around heritage sites, mirrors a growing demand for immersive, personalised experiences that delve into lesser-known aspects of history. These tours are typically led by

individuals with rich backgrounds in history, tourism, and culture, or those deeply passionate about these fields. They guide participants along less conventional paths, such as museum basements or historic neighbourhoods overlooked by conventional tourism. Such explorations offer profound insights into the area's cultural heritage, fostering a deeper appreciation of Indonesia's diverse cultural and historical contexts. These engagements not only enhance visitor involvement but also support sustainable tourism and cultural preservation, helping to maintain heritage sites as active, living reflections of Indonesia's historical and cultural richness (Agustiani & Agoes, 2021).

These tours provide a more nuanced understanding of Indonesia's diverse cultural and historical contexts, enhancing learning through engaging and personalised narratives that delve into the depths of local heritage. As described by Ham (2002), such immersive experiences not only increase engagement but also foster an emotional connection with the past, allowing visitors to feel a more personal link to the cultural narratives being presented. These interactive tours empower participants, turning them into active contributors to the interpretative process rather than mere observers. Furthermore, these experiences support local communities by bringing attention and economic benefits to often-overlooked areas, promoting sustainable tourism and broader cultural preservation efforts. For instance, Rosilawati et al 's (2019) research highlights how walking tours in Kotagede engage participants with the wider community, involving them in activities like learning to play musical instrument like *gamelan* or how to play shadow puppet *wayang*, visiting inhabited homes around the area, and exploring local markets. These interactions enrich the visitors' experiences and provide economic benefits to the local community, ensuring that heritage sites continue to be vibrant, living representations of Indonesia's rich historical and cultural fabric. By participating in these tours, audiences gain a more comprehensive view of Indonesia's heritage, challenging preconceived notions and encouraging a deeper appreciation for its cultural diversity and historical complexity. This holistic approach not only educates but also inspires a greater commitment to preserving the rich cultural diversity of the region.

Walking tours further enhance engagement by focusing on specific topics, such as colonial heritage, traditional crafts, or culinary histories. For example, in Jakarta's Old Town, walking tours explore the legacy of the VOC, while in Bandung, tours along Braga Street narrate the evolution of colonial-era commerce into modern-day cultural hubs (Sakina, 2020). These tours are often interactive, encouraging participants to use multiple senses such as tasting local

cuisine or listening to oral histories—to foster a lasting connection with the material. Studies in cognitive psychology suggest that sensory engagement enhances memory retention, making thematic tours particularly impactful for learning and cultural appreciation (Timothy, 2014). Additionally, walking tour guides often engage in continuous learning to develop new themes interpretation and expand their knowledge base (Brochu and Merriman, 2015). While many operate independently, informal networks and regular meetups allow guides to share insights, ensuring their narratives remain relevant and compelling. These practices exemplify the adaptability and creativity of Indonesian tour guides in responding to evolving tourist expectations.

The tension between traditional guided tours and digital alternatives is particularly pronounced when engaging younger tourists, who often prefer interactive digital experiences due to shorter attention spans. This demographic shift necessitates a re-evaluation of methods used by guides to deliver content. Integrating digital tools, such as augmented reality (AR) and virtual exhibitions, has proven effective in enhancing interactivity and retaining the attention of younger visitors (Hassan, 2022). For example, *Museum Nasional Indonesia* (National Museum of Indonesia) has embraced digital innovations like virtual exhibitions, including "Nusantara Jewelry 2021," which utilise 3D models, narration, and multimedia elements to enrich engagement and expand accessibility to Indonesia's cultural heritage (National Museum of Indonesia, 2022). Additionally, the museum's "*Ruang Imersifa*" exhibit employs video mapping technology to create an interactive, 360-degree journey through key periods of Indonesian history, demonstrating how digital tools can complement traditional storytelling to meet diverse visitor expectations.

Despite these technological advancements, the role of tour guides as cultural intermediaries remains indispensable. Guides provide a personal connection and interpretive depth that digital platforms alone cannot replicate, particularly in culturally complex sites. For instance, in Bali's Subak system, recognised by UNESCO for its cultural and ecological significance, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) enhance water management but cannot convey the spiritual and communal values integral to the system. Subak embodies a unique blend of sustainability, spiritual traditions, and collective governance, and guides ensure that these multidimensional aspects are not overshadowed by reductionist global narratives (Timothy, 2014; Achmadi et al., 2023). Similarly, in museums, guides complement digital tools by offering nuanced interpretations and fostering emotional connections, ensuring that visitors engage meaningfully with Indonesia's cultural and historical contexts (Salazar, 2011).

The digital transformation has also reshaped broader engagement with heritage sites. Social media platforms and travel blogs offer visually engaging content that directs tourists to "hidden gems" and helps optimise their itineraries (Patria, Khrisnamurti and Rahtomo, 2020). Museums and heritage sites increasingly adopt digital platforms, such as virtual tours and storytelling apps, to reach global audiences and make heritage more accessible. However, Indonesia's communal culture and emphasis on human connection underscore the irreplaceable role of guides. These guides deliver context-rich narratives tailored to diverse audiences, transcending the limitations of digital tools by blending education with entertainment to create immersive and personalised experiences. This adaptability is especially critical for educational tours, where guides align their storytelling with academic curricula to balance engagement and learning.

Unlike the standardised information provided by digital platforms, guides offer dynamic, interactive experiences that foster deeper emotional and intellectual connections with heritage. Their ability to respond in real-time to visitor questions and interests adds authenticity, ensuring their continued relevance in Indonesia's heritage tourism landscape (Brochu and Merriman, 2012). By integrating suitable digital technologies into their practice, guides can further enrich the heritage experience while maintaining their indispensable role as cultural intermediaries.

In museum settings and busy heritage sites, the role of tour guides is particularly critical for managing large groups, especially during peak tourist seasons. This management is not just about crowd control but also about enhancing the educational value of the visit. For instance, the Ullen Sentalu Museum in Yogyakarta mandates guided tours to manage visitor flow and safeguard its collections effectively. This policy ensures that each visitor not only adheres to the necessary protocols to protect delicate artefacts but also engages deeply with the rich narratives that these collections offer (Septadinusastra and Kurnia Sari, 2023).

Guided tours in such settings ensure that visitors receive a structured and comprehensive narrative tailored to highlight the significance of exhibits in a coherent and engaging manner. This approach is vital because it helps maintain the integrity of the museum experience, ensuring that visitors leave with a greater understanding and appreciation of the cultural and historical contexts of the exhibits. Moreover, guides are trained to handle varied audience questions and interests, providing detailed explanations that might not be possible through selfguided tours or digital interfaces (Urquhart, 2022).

Furthermore, the presence of guides helps to evenly distribute the visitor load throughout the museum, preventing overcrowding in particular areas, which can lead to accelerated wear and tear on exhibits. This strategic management is essential for the preservation of the collections and the quality of the visitor experience.

Additionally, in settings like the Ullen Sentalu Museum, where the cultural heritage is deeply intertwined with the identity of the Yogyakarta sultanates, the role of guides becomes even more significant. They convey not just facts but also the cultural nuances and stories that connect the exhibits to the broader historical and cultural fabric of the region. This storytelling is essential for cultural transmission and helps ensure that heritage is not merely observed but felt and understood.

Thus, tour guides are indispensable in museums and heritage sites in their educational and managerial roles. They not only facilitate a more organised and educative visit but also play a crucial role in preserving cultural heritage by providing a controlled, engaging, and informative tour experience that respects the site's historical significance while accommodating public interest and interaction.

3.3 Chapter 3 Summary

This chapter provides a comprehensive analysis of the dynamics of heritage tourism in Indonesia, rooted in its historical evolution, philosophical underpinnings, and the contemporary challenges of navigating global recognition while safeguarding local cultural authenticity. By examining Indonesia's rich tapestry of cultural and natural heritage, exemplified by sites such as Borobudur, Prambanan, and Bali's Subak system, the chapter reveals how global frameworks, particularly UNESCO World Heritage designations, interact with indigenous values, traditions, and practices.

The chapter begins with a historical overview, tracing the development of Indonesia's cultural landscape from the influence of Hindu-Buddhist kingdoms to the spread of Islam, colonial interventions, and post-independence modernisation. This historical trajectory underscores the layered complexity of Indonesia's heritage, shaped by both internal adaptations and external forces. Colonial-era narratives, for instance, commodified Bali's cultural identity for Western audiences, laying the groundwork for enduring tensions between preservation and tourism development. Post-independence, the nation's tourism policies have sought to reconcile cultural

heritage with economic growth, often reflecting the dual imperatives of nation-building and global integration.

Building on this foundation, the chapter explores the philosophical dimensions of heritage in the Southeast Asian context, particularly Indonesia. Unlike the static preservationist approaches often associated with Western frameworks, Indonesian heritage is deeply intertwined with dynamic, living practices rooted in communal values, spirituality, and environmental harmony. The interplay between global recognition and local agency emerges as a central theme. While UNESCO designations confer prestige, enhance visibility, and generate economic benefits, they often require adherence to universal criteria that risk overshadowing or marginalising indigenous narratives and spiritual significance.

Tour guides and heritage interpreters are highlighted as pivotal actors in this contested space. Their roles extend beyond narration to safeguarding intangible heritage through storytelling that weaves folklore, spiritual insights, and communal values into visitor experiences. Case studies such as Kotagede's post-earthquake revitalisation and Lasem's community-driven preservation efforts illustrate how grassroots initiatives reclaim local narratives and align cultural preservation with economic empowerment, offering a counterbalance to the homogenising pressures of global frameworks.

The chapter also interrogates the role of digital technologies in reconfiguring heritage tourism. Tools such as augmented reality and virtual exhibitions have expanded accessibility and engagement, particularly among younger audiences, yet they remain limited in capturing the emotional and spiritual depth of heritage. Human interpreters retain an indispensable role, ensuring that heritage sites are experienced as living cultural entities rather than static attractions.

In conclusion, the chapter advocates for a paradigm that integrates global recognition with local agency, rooted in the principles of sustainability, inclusivity, and authenticity. By embracing community-driven initiatives, leveraging the strengths of digital tools alongside human intermediaries, and critically engaging with global frameworks, Indonesia can position itself as a leader in reimagining heritage tourism. This approach envisions heritage sites not only as economic assets but as dynamic spaces that honour indigenous narratives, spiritual connections, and communal identities, ensuring their relevance and resilience in the global challenges.

CHAPTER 4

METHODOLOGY

This chapter explains and justifies the research methodology and method utilised for this research project. The chapter begins by explaining the philosophical underpinnings of the research, followed by research paradigms framed within the social constructivist epistemology. The chapter then moves on to a detailed explanation of the participants' recruitment, data collection, and analysis. The research positionality was articulated to describe the author's view and position towards this chapter. The trustworthiness and the ethics of the research were explained to guarantee the quality of this research in the last sections before providing a summary of this chapter.

4.1 Research Philosophies

As outlined at the beginning of this chapter, this research is guided by a social constructivist philosophical perspective, employing interview methods to gather data, insights, and perspectives from participants. Research philosophy involves developing assumptions about the nature of knowledge, truth, and reality, which in turn shape the research approach and methods (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Understanding and articulating these assumptions is critical, as they explain why researchers choose specific methodologies and data collection techniques (Creswell, 2013).

Different researchers may interpret truth, knowledge, and reality in various ways, depending on their philosophical stance (Kuhn, 1962; Feyerabend, 1975). Feyerabend's concept of epistemological relativism posits that scientific knowledge is not absolute but is influenced by cultural and historical contexts, leading to diverse interpretations of truth. Similarly, Kuhn's theory of paradigm shifts suggests that scientific communities operate within distinct frameworks that shape their perceptions of reality, resulting in differing perspectives among researchers.

A clear philosophical stance is essential for guiding how research is conducted, influencing decisions about methodology, and the type of answers sought (Rubin and Rubin, 2011). By clarifying the philosophical assumptions underpinning the study, researchers can ensure coherence between their worldview, research methods, and the questions they seek to answer (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Lowe, 2012). This study's social constructivist approach underpins the research design, allowing for exploring participant perspectives within their specific cultural and social contexts.

Researchers are better equipped to deliberately select a research approach and critically justify their chosen methodology when they understand the ontological and epistemological assumptions that define their perspective on reality, along with the theoretical foundations that guide the research process (Crotty, 1998). Ontology concerns the nature of reality (Willis, 2007). Within this concern, the author's ontological assumption about the world is that there is no absolute truth about reality because it is multiple, as seen through many views (Creswell, 2013). While epistemology is concerned with the nature of human knowledge and how we can know reality (Willis, 2007) in other terms 'how we know the world' and a process of knowing "how we know what we know" (Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Spencer *et al.*, 2003).

The research is influenced by a subjectivist ontology that upholds the notion that experience, and meaning are deeply embedded in culture and social interaction independent of a fixed reality (Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas, 2019). Subjectivists view social phenomena as constructs derived from the perceptions and subsequent actions of the individuals who engage with and contribute to their existence. In addition, subjectivists believe that social reality exists when we experience and give meaning to it (Bryman, 2016). While the epistemology stance used in this study is social constructivism, which asserts that knowledge and truth do not arise from existing realities. However, knowledge and truth emerge through a communally produced social process (Andrews, 2012; Slater, 2017). In a social context, Crotty (1998) asserts that "the 'social' in social constructionism refers to the process of meaning-making rather than the nature of the object being interpreted." Constructivism, in this context, is described as the view that all knowledge, and therefore all meaningful reality, is contingent upon human practices, constructed through the interaction between human beings and their world, and developed and shared within a fundamentally social framework. In simpler terms, meaning is not discovered but actively constructed.

The core principle of social constructivism rests on the belief that reality is deeply intertwined with subjective experience, shaped by broader social forces and influences. Consequently, understanding individual experiences requires recognising the socially constructed concepts that define, guide, and normalise the meanings of those experiences (Slater, 2017).

In this research, the author believes that knowledge and truth are constructed by the interaction between heritage interpreter and their surroundings, particularly the visitors and the guides' trainers. Guided by a social constructivism epistemology stance, the research seeks to understand the interpreter's world and develop meanings that link to their experience, which meanings are formed through interaction with others (Creswell, 2013). Subsequently, the meaning that the interpreters produced and reproduced through social interaction and shared understandings could be understood as a social construction. Using social constructivism for this research allows the author to obtain access to the perspective and nuances that shaped the worlds of the interpreters.

4.1.1 Research Paradigm

A research paradigm is a guidance system for the researcher and illustrates the research process (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). A paradigm shapes how people look at the world and what they see and specifies how and by whom research should be carried out (Rubin and Rubin, 2011). Worldviews or paradigms can lead to specific approaches or strategies of inquiry, whether qualitative, quantitative, mixed method, deductive, or inductive (Mertens, 2007; Creswell, 2013).

In the development of social science research, positivism and constructivism are two main methodological paradigms that have influenced and structured social science research. Positivism utilises the hypothetico-deductive approach to test predefined hypotheses, often expressed in quantitative terms. This method involves establishing functional relationships between causative and explanatory factors (independent variables) and their corresponding outcomes (dependent variables). The goal of positivism is to create causal relationships that would eventually potentially lead to the prediction and control of the phenomenon being studied (Park, Konge and Artino, 2020). In contrast, constructivism is a philosophical perspective that believes that individuals create meaning in the world based on their personal experiences and interactions with others. Hence, knowledge creation is a subjective process (Creswell, 2013).

According to the constructivist perspective, knowledge is a social construct generated from social interactions or, in other words, “a construction shaped by its context” (Delanty, 1997). Constructivism embraces the notion of multiple social realities, emphasising the relativity of perspectives. It acknowledges that knowledge is co-created through the interaction between the observer and the observed, striving for an interpretive understanding of the meaning’s individuals ascribe to their experiences (Charmaz, 2003). Constructivism assumes that people construct their attitudes and behaviour together with how they interpret the world around them (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Furthermore, from the standpoint of a constructivist, an individual interpretation or construction is as 'true' as any other person's interpretation or construction, which means that their interpretation is valid and there is no single truth (Doan, 1997).

From the discussion above, social constructivism is particularly relevant for a constructed social process such as heritage interpretation, which is based on the values of the heritage interpreters, which are influenced by their view of reality. The author believes that interpreters and heritage visitors socially construct heritage interpretation where frequent encounters create a constructive dialogue that influences both individuals’ values, ideas, thoughts, and perspectives. In addition, the author also believes that the interpreters and tourists define and interpret reality based on their situation or circumstances, such as their experiences, interaction with others and evolving knowledge, which is in line with the statement from Guba and Lincoln (1994) that the inquiry informed by a constructivist philosophy aims to gain a deeper understanding and reconstruction through individual subjective interactions. The social constructivism paradigm allows the author to understand an individual construction of knowledge, truth, and reality instead of their discovery (Dwyer, Gill and Seetaram, 2012). Therefore, the study uses the paradigm of constructivism by expressing the experiences that come from reality and personal knowledge that have not yet been revealed.

4.1.2 Inductive Reasoning as the Research Approach

In social science research, inductive reasoning is a core approach for generating new theories and insights, moving from specific observations to broader generalizations. This reasoning method begins with data collection—observing particular instances, patterns, or themes—which researchers then analyse to form general conclusions or theories (Corbin and Strauss, 2008; Bryman, 2016). Inductive reasoning aligns closely with qualitative research, where the goal is to understand phenomena from the ground up, allowing findings to emerge organically

from the data rather than testing pre-existing hypotheses. This approach is particularly valuable when little is known about a topic or when existing theories do not fully capture the complexity of the phenomena being studied (Thomas, 2006).

Inductive research is rooted in constructivist or interpretivist paradigms, which hold that knowledge is socially constructed and context-dependent (Charmaz and Belgrave, 2007). Under this paradigm, researchers gather in-depth, contextually rich data, often through interviews, observations, or ethnographic studies, to gain insights directly from participants. Through this process, patterns, categories, and themes emerge, which can then be used to develop theories that are closely aligned with participants' lived experiences. For instance, in studying community attitudes towards tourism development, an inductive approach would involve gathering insights from community members, identifying recurring themes, and forming theories about how community values influence their views on tourism.

However, inductive reasoning is inherently uncertain. Unlike deductive reasoning, which starts with a general principle and tests its applicability to specific cases, inductive reasoning involves interpreting data to form probable conclusions that are open to revision (Chater *et al.*, 2011). The conclusions drawn from inductive analysis are not absolute but represent the best understanding based on the data at hand. This flexibility makes inductive reasoning especially useful in social sciences, where human behaviour is often unpredictable and context sensitive.

Inductive reasoning also allows for adaptability in research design, as researchers are not confined to rigid frameworks but can adjust their focus based on emerging data patterns (Corbin and Strauss, 2008). It encourages researchers to immerse themselves in the data, letting patterns and themes naturally arise and guiding the theory-building process. This technique ensures that the resulting theories are deeply rooted in empirical data and closely aligned with the participants' perspectives, thereby offering valuable insights into complex social phenomena.

Inductive reasoning is suitable for this research because it allows for an open-ended exploration of both knowledge acquisition processes—formal training and informal learning—and the construction of tour guides' narratives. By adopting an inductive approach, the research can delve into the varied ways guides acquire and apply knowledge without being restricted by preestablished theories or assumptions. This is crucial, as tour guiding involves a dynamic interplay of structured, formal training and unstructured, experiential knowledge, both of which

influence how guides construct culturally authentic and contextually resonant narratives. As Thomas (2006) suggests, inductive reasoning is valuable when the aim is to develop new theories based on observed patterns, making it well-suited to investigating knowledge acquisition practices in a context as diverse as Indonesia's tourism landscape. This approach allows the study to capture the organic development of guides' interpretive practices, identifying the unique contributions of informal learning, such as community engagement and lived experiences, which are often overlooked in formal training (Charmaz and Belgrave, 2007).

Furthermore, because this research examines how guides construct narratives that reflect both acquired knowledge and cultural nuances, an inductive approach enables a deeper understanding of the influences shaping these narratives. Through inductive analysis, emergent themes can be identified around the blending of formal and informal learning in narrative construction, thereby providing a holistic view of the guiding profession. This flexibility to observe and synthesise new insights from data aligns well with the goal of theory-building in an under-researched area, supporting a nuanced understanding of how knowledge is contextualised within tour guiding.

4.1.3 Adopting a Qualitative Approach

This study adopts a qualitative approach grounded in a constructivist paradigm, which prioritises understanding how individuals interpret their lived experiences and construct meaning within specific cultural and institutional contexts (Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Charmaz, 2003). Rather than seeking objective or universal truths, the research is based on the belief that knowledge is co-constructed between researcher and participant—shaped by context, culture, and interaction. This epistemological stance is especially relevant in examining interpretive work in heritage and tourism settings, where meaning-making is inherently dynamic and situated.

Qualitative research aligns well with this constructivist paradigm, offering the flexibility to explore complex, nuanced perspectives that emerge from specific socio-cultural contexts (Flick, 2009; Braun & Clarke, 2021). It relies on non-numerical, narrative data such as interviews, documents, and observations—collected in natural settings and interpreted through the lens of the researcher (Creswell, 2013). In this interpretive design, the researcher is not a neutral observer but the primary instrument of data collection and analysis. Subjectivity is acknowledged as an integral part of the process, and researcher reflexivity is essential in

navigating the interactional nature of meaning-making and accounting for positional influences (Peshkin, 1998).

In this context, transferability—rather than statistical generalisability—emerges as the appropriate marker of rigour. The aim is not to produce universal laws but to offer contextually grounded insights that may resonate across similar cultural or institutional settings. Recent qualitative scholarship highlights the importance of thick description and contextual detail to enable readers to judge the applicability of findings to other contexts (Tracy, 2010; Nowell et al., 2017; Forero et al., 2018). This approach is especially relevant in settings marked by cultural specificity and structural complexity, where meaning is shaped by localised norms, histories, and power dynamics. This is particularly important in Southeast Asian heritage and tourism contexts, where social norms, power relations, and professional practices may differ significantly from those in Western paradigms. By emphasising transferability, the study contributes conceptual and methodological insights relevant to decolonial and context-sensitive research.

Consistent with qualitative research principles, the study does not seek statistical generalisation. Instead, it aims for analytical generalisation, offering insights that illuminate broader patterns across similar contexts (Firestone, 1993; Prabhu, 2019). The focus is on depth and meaning, particularly in how tour guides negotiate their roles within layered institutional and cultural structures. This approach enables a richer understanding of interpretive practice in heritage tourism and contributes to methodological advancement in non-Western and post-colonial, collectivist settings.

A central tenet of this methodological framework is reflexivity. As a researcher positioned both within and outside the cultural context under study, my background, assumptions, and interactions inevitably shaped the research process. This insider–outsider positionality generated both opportunities—such as greater rapport with participants—and challenges, including the need for heightened ethical sensitivity and critical self-awareness. Reflexive strategies, such as memo writing and maintaining a research journal, were embedded throughout the study to support ongoing examination of interpretive decisions, role negotiation, and potential biases (Peshkin, 1998).

Ultimately, this constructivist, qualitative design enables a deep exploration of how tour guides make sense of and navigate their interpretive responsibilities. By centring participant voices

and situating their practices within broader socio-cultural and institutional frameworks, the study contributes meaningful insights to heritage and tourism research in post-colonial, collectivist contexts.

4.2 Data Collection Procedure

Data collection in qualitative research involves the use of specific techniques and tools to gather empirical evidence that addresses research questions and aligns with the study's purpose (Creswell & Miller, 2000; Denzin & Lincoln, 2008). In this study, data were collected primarily through **semi-structured interviews**, a method particularly effective for exploring complex human experiences and eliciting in-depth insights (Creswell, 2014; Given, 2008). Interviews allow participants to articulate their perspectives, elaborate on their experiences, and reflect on the meanings they construct through their work (Darlington & Scott, 2022; Kvale, 1996).

The use of semi-structured interviews was deemed appropriate for this research as it offered a flexible yet focused structure. It allowed the researcher to pose open-ended questions while remaining responsive to each participant's unique experiences through follow-up prompts and probing questions (Maxwell, 2012). A pilot study was conducted to refine the interview guide and ensure that the questions were relevant, understandable, and aligned with the research objectives.

This study involved two participant groups: tour guides and trainers. The interviews with tour guides focused on how they acquire and integrate knowledge into their professional practice, particularly the interplay between formal training and informal learning. They also explored how guides construct narratives that balance cultural authenticity with audience engagement, and the interpretive tools used to connect with diverse tourist demographics. Interviews with trainers offered insights into the design and delivery of training programmes, highlighting the underlying philosophies and competencies deemed essential for heritage interpretation.

To support the development of the interview guide and enhance contextual understanding, a range of institutional documents was reviewed. These included training modules from HPI (*Himpunan Pramuwisata Indonesia* - Indonesian Tourist Guide Association), the Ministry of Manpower of the Republic of Indonesia, various museums, and trainer-developed materials. These documents were not treated as data for analysis, but rather used to inform the design of the interview questions and to situate participants' responses within their institutional and

professional contexts. This approach aligns with qualitative research practices where documents serve a background or framing function rather than a formal data source (Bowen, 2009).

All interviews followed a semi-structured format guided by an interview guide carefully developed to address the study’s research aims (Bernard, 2006). The guide included a combination of main questions, follow-ups, and probes to encourage participants to expand on their responses and reflect on their interpretive practice (Rubin & Rubin, 2011). While the guide ensured consistency across interviews, it also allowed for flexibility in question order and language, enabling the researcher to adapt to the flow of conversation and emerging themes. This flexibility helped create a conversational atmosphere in which participants felt comfortable sharing their views. Table 4.1 presents the full set of guiding questions used in the interviews.

To complement the audio recordings, note-taking was employed during and after each interview. During the interviews, brief notes were taken to record key ideas, quotes, and cues for follow-up questions without disrupting the interaction (Halcomb & Davidson, 2006). In addition, contextual notes—such as observations of body language, tone, and setting—were recorded to enrich the data. The researcher also maintained reflexive notes, documenting personal impressions, emerging insights, and patterns observed in the field (Phillippi & Lauderdale, 2018; Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009; Mulhall, 2003). These notes served both practical and analytical purposes, aiding interpretation during coding and theme development.

Table 4.1 Interview Guide

Objective	Participant	Interview Questions
<p>To critically explore the processes through which tour guides in Indonesia acquire and integrate knowledge into their professional practice, focusing on the interplay between formal and informal learning frameworks.</p>	<p>Tour guide</p>	<p>- How do you incorporate both formal training and informal learning experiences into your practice as an interpreter?</p>
		<p>- Can you describe a specific instance where informal learning significantly influenced your professional methods or understanding?</p>
	<p>Trainer</p>	<p>- What balance do you strive for between formal curriculum and experiential learning in training programs for tour guides?</p>
		<p>- How is feedback from field experiences integrated into formal training sessions?</p>

<p>To analyse the methodologies employed by interpreters in constructing narratives that balance authenticity with audience engagement</p>	<p>Tour guide</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do you construct your narratives to ensure they are authentic to the cultural heritage yet engaging for diverse audiences? - What strategies do you use to tailor your stories to the interests and backgrounds of your audience?
	<p>Trainer</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What methodologies do you teach tour guides to help them balance authenticity with engagement in their narratives? - How do you assess an interpreter’s ability to maintain this balance during training?
<p>To investigate the effectiveness and adaptability of interpretive tools and techniques used by tour guides to enhance narrative delivery and foster meaningful connections with diverse tourist demographics.</p>	<p>Tour guide</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What interpretive tools and techniques have you found most effective in connecting with diverse audiences? - How do you adapt your approach when faced with particularly challenging or diverse groups?
	<p>Trainer</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are tour guides trained to use different tools and techniques effectively across various tourist demographics? - What ongoing support or training do tour guides receive to stay effective in their techniques?
<p>To explore the socio-cultural dynamics influencing the narrative strategies of tour guides within the context of global and local heritage discourses.</p>	<p>Tour guide</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do global heritage discourses influence the way you develop and deliver your narratives? - Can you give examples of how local socio-cultural dynamics have shaped your narrative strategies?
	<p>Trainer</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do you prepare tour guides to understand and integrate global and local cultural dynamics into their narratives? - What challenges do tour guides face when aligning their narratives with both global perceptions and local realities?

4.2.3 Selecting and Contacting the Participants

To ensure high-quality data and depth of insight from the respondents, this study carefully evaluated sample adequacy. The selection of participants was driven by their expertise and ability to reflect the study's thematic concerns comprehensively, aiming to explore diverse perspectives, ideas, and opinions on heritage interpretation (O’Reilly and Parker, 2013). The interviewing process was governed by the principle of data saturation, meaning it continued

until no new insights emerged, and responses became repetitive (Creswell, 2013; M. Patton, 2014). Interviews concluded when additional discussions ceased to yield novel information, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the topics investigated.

The study employed purposive sampling to select participants capable of providing in-depth insights into specific themes, concepts, and phenomena, thus enhancing the research's depth and breadth (Robinson, 2014). Additionally, snowball sampling was utilized to extend the reach within specific social groups or networks, effectively leveraging existing relationships to identify and recruit participants who could offer contextually significant data (Noy, 2008). This combined sampling strategy ensured the inclusion of participants whose perspectives were crucial to the research objectives. Initially, key individuals within relevant organisations were contacted; these primary contacts then facilitated connections to other potential participants who met the research criteria, proving especially effective in engaging those who held significant roles within their communities or organisations (Hibberts, Johnson, and Hudson, 2012).

The study categorised participants into two groups: tour guides and trainers, involving a total of 36 participants—25 tour guides and 11 trainers, with six holding dual roles. Each participant was selected based on their knowledge and experience relevant to the area of study, ensuring the credibility and reliability of the results roles (Ryan and Dewar, 1995; Weiler and Ham, 2002; Weiler and Walker, 2014; Yamada, 2014; Brochu and Merriman, 2015).

To maintain confidentiality and anonymity, pseudonyms replaced actual names in the findings and discussion chapters (Chapters Five and Six). All identifying information was rigorously removed from documents and interview transcripts to protect participant identities. Table 4.2 provides a summary of participant demographic data using pseudonyms to uphold anonymity.

Table 4.2 Profile of the Participants

Pseudonyms	Occupation	Age	Origin	Gender	Date of Interview
Darla	Tour guide	30 - 35	Bandung, Indonesia	Female	23-Aug-22
Karta	Tour guide	30 - 35	Bandung, Indonesia	Male	25-Aug-22
Mondo	Tour Guide/ Trainer	40 - 45	Bandung, Indonesia	Male	23-Aug-22

Dana	Tour guide	50 - 55	Bandung, Indonesia	Male	24-Aug-22
Ernie	Tour guide	56+	Bandung, Indonesia	Male	25-Aug-22
Kamil	Tour guide	50 - 55	Bandung, Indonesia	Male	25-Aug-22
Niken	Trainer	50 - 55	Bandung, Indonesia	Female	27-Aug-22
Jasmine	Tour guide	30 - 35	Bandung, Indonesia	Female	29-Aug-22
Marley	Tour guide	25 - 30	Bandung, Indonesia	Male	29-Aug-22
Fido	Tour guide	40 - 45	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	02-Sep-22
Tifa	Tour guide	40 - 45	Jakarta, Indonesia	Female	07-Sep-22
Mela	Tour guide	40 - 45	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	09-Sep-22
Jono	Tour guide	40 - 45	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	10-Sep-22
Romi	Trainer	40 - 45	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	10-Sep-22
Dennie	Tour guide	40 - 45	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	12-Sep-22
Bobby	Tour guide	40 - 45	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	13-Sep-22
Lesmana	Tour guide/ Trainer	55+	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	13-Sep-22
Sebastian	Tour guide	50 - 55	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	13-Sep-22
Ghofar	Tour guide	35 - 40	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	14-Sep-22
Archie	Tour guide	55+	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	14-Sep-22
Narsih	Tour guide	35 - 40	Jakarta, Indonesia	Female	20-Sep-22
Acil	Tour guide	50 - 55	France	Female	22-Sep-22
Sander	Tour guide/ Trainer	55+	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	24-Sep-22
Imot	Tour guide	30 - 35	Japan	Female	27-Sep-22
Devo	Tour guide	30 - 35	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	27-Sep-22
Aries	Tour guide/ Trainer	55+	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	30-Sep-22
Kay	Tour guide	50 - 55	Japan	Female	01-Oct-22
Gene	Tour guide	30 - 35	France	Female	05-Oct-22
Onad	Tour guide/ Trainer	30 - 35	Spain	Male	06-Oct-22
Coco	Tour guide/ Trainer	30 - 35	Jakarta, Indonesia	Female	18-Oct-22
Lumi	Tour guide	30 - 35	Jakarta, Indonesia	Female	18-Oct-22
Ronald	Tour guide	30 - 35	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	18-Oct-22
Geraldora	Tour guide/ Trainer	55+	Germany	Female	19-Oct-22
Miftah	Tour guide	31 - 35	Jakarta, Indonesia	Male	19-Oct-22
Juminten	Trainer	40 - 45	Yogyakarta, Indonesia	Female	26-Oct-22
Christie	Trainer	30 - 35	Yogyakarta, Indonesia	Female	26-Oct-22

Before commencing the fieldwork, the author established initial contact with some participants while still in Scotland. These participants, particularly the primary ones, served as key entry points to the organisations or communities connected to the research. WhatsApp, a widely used platform in Indonesia, was utilised to contact six participants: Niken, Fido, Tifa, John, Romi, and Dennie. These individuals were personally known to the author, which facilitated the initial approach. During this communication, the author explained the research aims and objectives, shared the informed research form and consent form and clarified why they were selected to

participate in the study. Two of these participants, Niken and Dennie, held significant roles in HPI (*Himpunan Pramuwisata Indonesia* – the Indonesia Tour Guide Association) and InterpID (*Interpretasi Indonesia* – the Indonesian Society for Interpretation), making their involvement particularly valuable. As an active member of InterpID, the author was able to reach out directly to potential participants. However, advice was sought from the organisation to ensure the selected participants met the research criteria in terms of experience and expertise. These initial conversations were informal and friendly, helping to build rapport and trust with the participants. This approach also led to valuable recommendations for other potential participants who matched the study's criteria.

Niken suggested nine participants: Mondo, Dana, Ernie, Kamil, Jasmine, Marley, Romi, Onad, and Christie. When contacting Mondo, the author asked for additional recommendations and was referred to Darla and Karta, who were also suitable for the study. When the author contacted Romi, he recommended Juminten as a potential participant. The author then contacted Juminten, who agreed to take part in the study.

While contacting other participants, it became apparent that Onad held an important role in the Indonesian Heritage Society (IHS). The author reached out to him via email to explain the research objectives. The consent form and informed research letter were attached. Following internal discussions within IHS, they agreed to participate, and seven members – Archie, Imot, Narsih, Acil, Kay, Gene, and Geraldora – joined the study. After several email exchanges, communication with Onad transitioned to WhatsApp at his request, which streamlined the process.

The participants from IHS brought a unique perspective to the research. As volunteer museum tour guides in Jakarta, they specialise in leading tours in non-Indonesian languages, including English, French, Japanese, and Korean. Their contributions added an important dimension to the study by providing insight into heritage interpretation for international audiences, which was a key focus of the research.

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Since the majority of interviews with members of the IHS took place at the *Museum Nasional Indonesia* (MNI – National Museum of Indonesia), the author also approached the museum staff for recommendations of potential participants who aligned with the study's objectives. The museum recommended four individuals: Coco, Lumi, Ronald, and Miftah. These recommendations provided the author with valuable insights into how these participants acquire and process their knowledge and craft their narratives. Comparing their approaches to those of the IHS volunteers highlighted similarities and differences in patterns of knowledge acquisition and narrative creation.

As previously mentioned, participants John and Dennie are active members of HPI and have a personal connection with the author. They suggested creating a WhatsApp group to facilitate more effective and efficient communication among the participants. Additionally, they recommended several potential participants, including Bobby, Lesmana, Sebastian, Sander, Devo, and Aries. They advised the author to reach out to these individuals through WhatsApp, ensuring that each contact was informed and agreed to be involved in the research before proceeding. Another participant personally known to the author, Ghofar, also recommended three additional individuals. However, only one of these, Mela, responded and agreed to participate in the study.

To recruit tourist participants, the author directly approached tour guides or tour guides at museums and walking tours prior to their sessions. The author explained the purpose of the research to the guides, who then introduced the author to visitors and briefly described the research intention. Visitors were then asked whether they would be willing to participate in the study. As a result, a total of 13 tourists agreed to be interviewed. Four of these participants opted to be interviewed immediately after the tour, while the remaining nine arranged for interviews at a later time and place due to scheduling conflicts. The author decided to stop

recruiting tourists for interviews at 13 participants, as it was felt that the number was sufficient and that no new information was emerging from subsequent interviews.

4.2.2 Pilot Study

A pilot study using semi-structured interviews was conducted to refine the data collection process and ensure the rigour of the research design. Pilot studies are an essential step in research, enabling researchers to test research questions, evaluate data collection tools, and identify areas for improvement prior to full-scale fieldwork (Barbour, 2008). In this study, the pilot phase allowed the researcher to assess the appropriateness of the interview questions, evaluate techniques, and confirm the optimal interview length, thereby ensuring readiness for the main study. Additionally, the pilot provided an opportunity to gain practical experience in conducting semi-structured interviews and establishing rapport with participants.

Ethical approval for the pilot study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the School of Business and Creative Industries at the University of the West of Scotland. The primary objective was to test and validate the data collection instruments and confirm internal consistency. Sekaran and Bougie (2016) highlight that pilot studies are crucial for ensuring the reliability and validity of research tools, as they help identify and address flaws that could undermine the quality of the data. This iterative refinement process strengthens the credibility of the research and lays the foundation for robust data collection.

The pilot study also served to identify broader design issues that could affect the research outcomes. Bryman (2016) emphasises the importance of piloting in enhancing the reliability and applicability of research instruments through iterative testing. Similarly, Malmqvist et al. (2019) stress that systematic piloting contributes to research robustness by enabling methodological refinements and enhancing instrument validity. Feedback from the pilot study informed critical adjustments, such as resolving ambiguities and refining data collection procedures. This process further supported the generalisability of findings and ensured the integrity of the research process.

The pilot interviews were conducted in late August 2022 in Bandung, Indonesia, following ethical approval. Two participants were purposefully selected for the pilot study based on their dual roles as tourism academics and tour guides. Both participants, aged 40–45 years with at least four years of tour guiding experience, were not included in the main study's sampling plan.

Initial contact was made using WhatsApp while the author was in Scotland, with follow-up communication arranged after arriving in Indonesia. Participants received informed consent forms, and interviews were conducted in Indonesian, using a translated interview guide to ensure clarity and accuracy. The interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed, and subsequently translated into English. As a token of appreciation, meal expenses were covered for both participants.

The pilot study identified several potential issues, including the need to reword some interview questions to improve clarity and flow. As Kim (2011) suggests, pilot studies are effective for testing research instruments and identifying areas for refinement. These adjustments included restructuring questions from general to specific, ensuring they elicited insightful responses and allowed participants to generate ideas. Warm-up questions, in particular, were refined to encourage open communication and productive dialogue. The pilot also provided insights into other practical aspects, such as verifying the intended interview duration and confirming the feasibility of the data collection procedures.

Overall, the pilot study enabled the author to address methodological challenges, enhance the reliability and clarity of the data collection tools, and prepare effectively for the main study. By identifying potential obstacles and refining research instruments, the pilot contributed to the rigour and credibility of the overall research process.

4.2.4 Entering the Fieldwork

The fieldwork for this study took place in three Indonesian cities: Jakarta, Bandung, and Yogyakarta, during the tourism high season from mid-August to the end of October 2022. These cities were intentionally selected as they represent distinct layers of Indonesia's heritage landscape and allowed for a diverse range of guiding practices and interpretive contexts. In addition to being accessible during peak season, they offered strategic variety in socio-cultural, institutional, and narrative approaches to heritage interpretation.

Jakarta, as the capital city, represents a more institutionalised and nationalistic approach to heritage. It is home to many state museums and official narratives, providing insight into how heritage is framed at the national level. Bandung is characterised by its colonial and modernist heritage, particularly its Art Deco architecture and Dutch planning legacy. Guides in this city

often grappled with the tension between colonial nostalgia and postcolonial critique, offering valuable perspectives on narrative negotiation. Yogyakarta—often referred to as the cultural heart of Java—provided deep insights into spiritual and local traditions. Here, guides often drew upon Javanese philosophy, indigenous wisdom, and spiritual legitimacy to shape their interpretations. Together, these sites allowed the author to explore a wide spectrum of interpretation styles—from formal to informal, secular to spiritual, and national to local identities. This comparative richness helped deepen the analysis and made space for different voices and tensions to emerge.

The interviews were conducted one-on-one, with locations chosen by the participants based on their availability and comfort. Most interviews took place in participants' workplaces; however, several were conducted in cafés or canteens due to factors such as lack of office space, informal settings, or after-hours timing—particularly in the case of freelancers. As with the pilot study, meal and drink expenses were covered by the author as a token of appreciation.

Although interviews ideally take place in quiet and secluded environments, this was not always feasible. In instances where background noise was unavoidable (e.g. public cafés), the author used a high-quality digital audio recorder and a voice recording app on a smartphone to ensure clarity. This dual-recording strategy aligns with qualitative research standards, as it allows the researcher to focus on listening, probing, and following up (Rosalind & Holland, 2013). A handwritten notebook was also used to record observations, impressions, and key insights shared by participants during the sessions.

A total of 36 individuals were interviewed, consisting of 30 Indonesians and 6 non-Indonesians from France, Germany, and Japan. Participants ranged in age from 22 to 60 years old, with a gender distribution of 22 males and 14 females. The sample was deliberately designed to capture diversity in age, gender, ethnicity, religion, and international background. As Allmark (2004) argues, such diversity strengthens the trustworthiness of qualitative research by ensuring that multiple perspectives are represented.

All guide and trainer participants had between 3 to 20 years of experience. Interviews typically lasted 60 to 120 minutes, with one extending to 180 minutes. In contrast, tourist interviews were shorter, typically 15–30 minutes, reflecting their limited availability and the supplementary role of their perspectives in this study.

Before each interview, participants received both an informed research form and a consent form, outlining the research objectives, their rights, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Time was provided to ask questions and discuss the relevance of their contributions. All participants gave written consent, and their data were treated with strict confidentiality. Pseudonyms were used in transcripts and reporting to protect participant identity.

Interviews with most Indonesian participants were conducted in *Bahasa Indonesia*, which allowed for greater comfort in expression. These were later translated into English for analysis. Only three Indonesian participants preferred to be interviewed in English. All non-Indonesian participants were interviewed in English.

To establish rapport, informal small talk was used before and after interviews. This helped ease participants into the conversation and fostered a relaxed yet engaged atmosphere. The interviews followed the semi-structured format, with flexibility to adjust question order or wording based on participants' responses. In some cases, questions were adapted in real time to pursue emerging themes

4.3 Data Analysis

Data analysis is often regarded as the core of any research project, where the researcher interprets and theorises to construct meaningful insights from the data (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña, 2014). It involves systematically organising and categorising the data corpus to identify and select the most relevant data set for understanding and making sense of participants' experiences (Patton, 2002; Guest, MacQueen and Namey, 2012; Gibbs, 2018). This thesis utilised qualitative thematic analysis as the primary approach to data analysis. An inductive approach played a pivotal role in directly identifying themes, codes, and categories from the data. Thematic analysis was employed to uncover patterns within the raw data and organise it into coherent themes, facilitating an interpretive, reflexive, and bottom-up analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021). The six-step process of thematic analysis—familiarisation with the data, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and writing up—was followed to analyse the interview data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis was chosen for this research as it provides a robust method for exploring individuals' views, opinions, knowledge, experiences, and values, as reflected in the qualitative data from interview

transcripts. This approach not only ensures a systematic and comprehensive analysis but also aligns with the interpretive and exploratory nature of the study.

Thematic analysis is flexible, intuitive, and very adaptable to any philosophical epistemology, hapter including the constructivist paradigm, which holds that social reality is built on human perspectives (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Constructivism maintains that people build their attitudes and behaviours, as well as how they view and construct the world around them, which is highly linked to their socio-cultural background (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Thematic analysis has also been highlighted for its adaptability and flexibility to a wide range of data formats and research aims (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Furthermore, this analysis allows the author to actively participate in discovering and interpreting themes as guided by the research questions.

This research incorporated inductive reasoning with thematic analysis and was considered for gathering rich understanding from participant narratives while ensuring findings have theoretical generalisability (Coffey and Atkinson, 1996). The thematic analysis enables the development of an inductive theory as a way of progressing from more descriptive to more latent theories (Braun and Clarke, 2006). According to Lipscomb (2012), abduction played an essential part in qualitative data analysis – theme development was directed both by the empirical content and the previously formulated theoretical point of departure (Lipscomb, 2012). This study considered adopting Braun and Clarke’s (2006) 6 steps thematic analysis tailored for inductive research guidance that excerpts from thematic analysis experts (e.g. Boyatzis, 1998; Campbell et al., 2021; Coffey & Atkinson, 1996; Jonsen et al., 2017; Hopper et al., 2021; Morse, 1994; Oliver et al., 2005; Saldaña, 2015; Taheri & Thompson, 2020; Timmermans & Tavory, 2012). The thematic analysis for this study followed Braun and Clarke’s (2006) six-step approach, emphasising both theoretical grounding and empirical discovery in interpreting qualitative data.

1. Familiarisation with the Data

The first step involved transcribing the interviews verbatim, reviewing, and thoroughly familiarising with the data to ensure accuracy. The transcription process was essential for gaining an initial understanding, as it involved interpretive thinking to derive deeper meaning. All transcriptions were reviewed multiple times, both digitally and in hard copy, to immerse

the researcher in the dataset and prepare for the coding process (Davidson, 2009; Serovich & Mason, 2005).

2. Generating Initial Codes

Coding was then conducted in two rounds, with the first round focusing on identifying raw data segments aligned with initial interpretive ideas, and the second round consolidating codes into distinct categories. NVivo 12 software was employed to facilitate coding, allowing for easy manipulation and iteration. This flexible approach enabled the researcher to revisit codes and adapt them as insights developed (Dey, 1993; Rubin & Rubin, 2005).

3. Searching for Themes

Following the coding, themes were identified by examining relationships among codes and grouping them based on shared patterns and meanings. This stage involved categorising codes that collectively represented significant phenomena within the data. Each theme was labelled with a memorable phrase that encapsulated its essence, making the thematic structure accessible for further analysis.

4. Reviewing Themes

To ensure coherence and alignment with theoretical insights, the identified themes were reviewed and refined. This stage also involved comparing datasets to observe patterns across participant cohorts, such as age or location. Adjustments were made to capture the nuances within the data, with each theme checked for its ability to reflect meaningful patterns across different groups.

5. Defining and Naming Themes

Each theme was clearly defined and named, with reference to relevant theoretical frameworks. A codebook was developed to provide structure to the coding process, including definitions, examples, and criteria for when to use or not use each code. This allowed for consistency and clarity in interpreting the themes and supported theoretical engagement with the data.

6. Producing the Report

The final stage involved compiling the findings into a coherent narrative. Each theme was presented with supporting quotations from the data and linked back to theoretical insights to underscore the significance of the empirical findings. The report included data displays to

visually represent themes, enhancing the reader's understanding of the relationships and patterns uncovered in the analysis.

4.4 Trustworthiness of the Research

The aim of trustworthiness in qualitative research is to support the argument that the research's findings are "worth paying attention to" (Lincoln & Guba, 1994). Trustworthiness needs to be upheld in research to ensure that the procedures of recruiting participants, securing their participation, and dealing with data collecting and analysis are carried out in accordance with proper research standards, with an awareness of the rights and wrongs of dealing with human participants (Patton, 2014). In order to ensure the study trustworthiness, the author establish protocols and procedures necessary for the study to be considered worth consideration by readers (Amankawa, 2016). Four Criteria outlined by Lincoln and Guba (1994) are accepted by many qualitative researchers for trustworthiness in the research, these criteria include credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. These are further explained in detail below.

- **Credibility**

Credibility shows the level of trust in the results of the study and can be obtained from the proper interpretation of information or opinions given by the participants (Korstjens and Moser, 2018). The first step to gain credibility is to familiarise with the majority of the participants to gain mutual trust. To become acquainted with the interviewees who engaged in the research, the author emailed the interviewees listed in the sampling plan. The author then described the purpose of the research and invite them to participate in the research via email or text messages such as SMS and WhatsApp with attaching the informed consent letter, participant information sheet and ethical approval letter. Following confirmation of interviewee participation, the author contacted with each interviewee to choose a mutually agreed-upon day, time, and venue for the interview. The interviewees were grouped together in time and space by city. The same procedures were applied in contacting additional potential interviewees. For the tourist participants, the author visited heritage sites and museum in Jakarta and Bandung to search for potential participants that include domestic tourists and international tourists from diverse regions.

The author was constantly reminded the respondent that they have the option to resign from the interview at any moment or when they do not feel comfortable answering the question if it is deemed inappropriate—this also increases the study credibility (Shenton, 2004). This indicates that by offering a preliminary explanation, the information given is considered to be independent of compulsion, trustworthy, and relevant for research objectives. Allowing withdrawal from an interview indicates that the information provided by the respondent is regarded safe, has been approved, and have no negative consequence other than for the goals of the research.

The data collected attained the accuracy and reliability by recording and transferring each word in transcribes transcription and notes from the data collection which accurately provide important validity for the research. The records help the author to understand the data to get the meaning. Furthermore, by documenting and transmitting each word in transcribes transcription and notes from the data collection, the data obtained achieve correctness and dependability, providing crucial validity for the research.

Once the interviews were transcribed, participants were given verbatim copies of their transcripts to review for accuracy, identify and correct any errors, and offer clarifications where necessary. The goal is to ensure that the responses obtained are trustworthy. By documenting and transmitting each word in transcribes transcription and notes from the data collection, the data obtained achieve correctness and dependability, providing crucial credibility for this research.

- Transferability

Transferability, which replaces the traditional concept of generalisability in research, involves providing sufficient contextual information from studies to understand the processes implemented (Shenton, 2004). The focus is on deeply describing a specific research context, not merely through sampling but by offering a rich narrative of the research environment. This approach allows other researchers to draw comparisons and make informed judgments about whether findings can be meaningfully applied to other settings (Seale, 1999). While outcomes and situations may differ, the contextual and relational insights generated by research can still hold relevance across different contexts (Shenton, 2004). In this study, transferability refers to

the extent to which the findings provide insights that could enhance understanding in other comparable settings.

- Dependability

To ensure the dependability of this research, the findings are structured to be replicable in future studies (Shenton, 2004). Semi-structured interviews were employed to gather and analyse data from participants, providing a systematic approach to data collection. Dependability is further supported by maintaining comprehensive research documentation, encompassing the processes of data collection, analysis, and reporting (Minichiello et al., 2008). To uphold consistency, all changes and revisions to the research protocol were meticulously recorded, with detailed logs tracking when and how adjustments were implemented.

- Conformability

Confirmability in this research was achieved by double-checking the results. Confirmability aims to ensure that the results of the interview are consistent with what the participants reported, so that the true meaning can be confirmed and not based solely on the researchers' judgment (Shenton, 2004). Confirmability is confirmed by demonstrating that the authors' results came from the data and not from the authors' predispositions. On this point, reflexivity was very important to minimize bias in relation to the researcher's own position. The goal of compliance is. The author used a reflective journal to minimize the weight of the author's own subjectivity on the research.

4.5 Reflexivity and Positionality

Reflexivity is an important aspect of qualitative research, which allows the researcher to acknowledge, disclose and reflect their selves based on their background, values and positionality in order to understand their part or influence on the research (Cohen et, al, 2011; Johnson & Duberley, 2003). Through using a reflexive approach, the author was influenced by his research process choices, knowledge, personal and professional experiences, motivation and qualifications for exploration of the field, and perspectives and theoretical foundations as the as the expression of his positionality (Holmes, 2020). Therefore, it is important to first understand that author positionality in this research.

The author was aware that his personal experiences and knowledge will influence the way he understands and expressed the social phenomena. It influenced how this research was conducted, its outcomes, and results (Rowe, 2014). This mean that a qualitative researcher always carries their own bias, no matter how objective they claim their methods and themselves to be (Wilson, 2008). For those reasons, the author thought it was necessary to express the author position with his personal background and purpose within this research (Kovach, 2009).

As a PhD student, the author acknowledges the powerful inherent aspects of his status at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) that were perceived as something impressive for some participants, although Ntsane (2001 in Wustenberg, 2008) argued that the researcher's power is negotiated, not given during the fieldwork. There were some situations in which the participants sought advice because they assumed that the author was an expert in tourism, heritage and interpretation. The author felt that it is important to state the privilege in the qualitative research, given the fact that people might participate in this research due to this factor.

As an Indonesian who is studying in Scotland, the author's position as an insider or outsider in this research was taken into consideration. In this research, the author is simultaneously both an insider and an outsider (Mohammed, 2001 in Holmes, 2020). Given the familiarity and a priori knowledge that the author possessed of his understanding of the Indonesian culture, most of the communications with the participants were using Bahasa Indonesia including colloquial language that helps the ability to build rapport better and easier for the participants to express their opinions. In addition, his background education and area of work in tourism education has benefited him to easily connected to the participants due to of the same network. Furthermore, as an 'insider,' the author have the opportunity to gained access to specific social settings that would otherwise be closed to outsiders. These advantages enhance trust and openness to the research process (Unwin, 2006; Wustenberg, 2008).

Conversely, the author encountered participants with whom they were less familiar, such as tour guides who were expatriates and international tourists, positioning the author as an outsider in these interactions. It is important to highlight that the author also felt a degree of unfamiliarity with Indonesia's economic, political, and cultural issues, considering themselves a returner (Wustenberg, 2008). Drawing on Merton's (1972, cited in Holmes, 2020) perspective, the author acknowledges that as situations involving differing values emerge, varying statuses are

activated, leading to shifts in the boundaries of separation. With this understanding, the author remains conscious of their identity within the research context and its potential influence on field interactions.

It is the author academic background, research and experience that led to this research. The author holds a bachelor's degree in tourism management from Bandung Tourism Institute in Indonesia and has experienced studying for master's degree in tourism management and planning at Bournemouth, UK. During his study, the author was captivated by heritage interpretation that was introduced through the heritage tourism course and undertook his dissertation on the topic of volunteer heritage interpreter. After completing the study, the author went back to Indonesia and work in several event organiser before becoming the lecturer in tourism. The author has worked several tourism projects with the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy of Indonesia as a tourism consultant. The author passion for heritage interpretation has co-founded InterpID , Indonesian Society for Interpretation, that aims to introduce and implement heritage interpretation as an integral part in Indonesia tourism and other related areas.

Having the privilege to experience and to be exposed to the different culture at the early age, the author was often traveling with his family to places that he never imagined that such place existed. Due to his family traveling behaviour, he often encountered tour guides, museum guides and park rangers. The author really moved by the experience on how they could “hypnotise” the audience with their fascinating stories, some of the stories could still be recalled. By witnessing their enthusiasm and passion for their role, the author started to reflect on their learning method and how do their past experience, background education, and their interaction with other people play an important role on their interpretation process and also the delivery of the interpretation to the audience. There is also countless experience of interpreter's service sometimes fails to provide quality interpretations services. They failed to play the role, unprovoked the audience to have a deep thought experience or easily sensing that the tour guides were not passionate. That is why, the author is driven to produce research results that will understand and improve those conditions.

4.6 Ethics of the Research

In terms of ethics, there are four general principles utilised by UWS through the University Ethics Committee (2020) as the cardinal ethical principle underlying research ethics is the

respect for human dignity. The principles are autonomy, veracity and informed consent, privacy and confidentiality, justice and inclusiveness, benefits (beneficence) and harms (nonmaleficence) (UWS Code of Ethics, 2020). To fulfil the ethics of the study, the four principles above are essential to be attained. The first principles, autonomy, veracity, and informed consent means that the respondent can withdraw anytime without any consequences if they feel they need to (Berg, 2007). There were informed consent letter and participant information sheet that they may review and sign before starting the interview. Their participation in this research was their own choice. For the second principle, which is privacy and confidentiality means information obtained from and about a participant should remain confidential unless otherwise agreed in advance (UWS Code of Ethics, 2020). In this research, all information about an identity that can lead to a subjective judgment were avoided. Subsequently, the research also concerns for the third principle, justice or inclusiveness, means treating the respondent with fairness and equity by treating the same respondents to each other without discussing any sensitive values (Cresswell, 2014). The fourth principles are benefits (beneficence) and harms (nonmaleficence), which aim to minimise the harm and maximise the benefits. The research ensures that there is no coercion in the interview by using proper sentences that do not vilify the respondent (Cresswell, 1994). The research also contributes to the scientific field as well as benefits to society.

Prior to data collection, the author needed to ensure that the data collection process would conform to the UWS School Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship to protect interviewees' safety and privacy. The author ensured the ethical conduct of the research by following guidelines set by the School of Business and Creative Industries (SBCI) Ethics Committee of UWS as the author were actively interacting with participants during the interviewing process, as well as through data generating from the documents information, as well as manipulating data from documents, there was an apparent need to adopt activities to address the ethical difficulties that may effect this research. The SBCI Ethics Committee ensures that potential subjects are provided with specific, understandable information about the study prior to data collection. Research protocols and instruments are reviewed and approved by the SBCI Ethics Committee. Thus, prior to the fieldwork and data collection phase, the author submitted the ethical form and received ethics approval. Based on its guidelines for ethical approval, the author developed a research-informed consent form and a participant information sheet that included the right of subjects to data collection procedures,

procedures to protect their privacy, and assurances about the confidentiality of their individual comments.

4.7 Chapter 4 Summary

This chapter has outlined the methodological approach adopted in this study, grounded in a social constructivist paradigm and executed through a qualitative research design. It detailed the philosophical underpinnings, research paradigm, and use of inductive reasoning, followed by a description of data collection procedures, participant recruitment, and fieldwork context. Thematic analysis, guided by Braun and Clarke's (2006) framework, was employed for data analysis. Rigorous measures were taken to ensure trustworthiness, including credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. The chapter concluded by discussing ethical considerations and the author's reflexive positioning. The next chapter presents the empirical findings emerging from the data.

CHAPTER 5

NAVIGATING KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION

In the next two chapters, Chapter 5 and Chapter 6, the author will discuss the findings of this study, which reveal that in Indonesia, the knowledge acquisition process for tourist guides is uniquely shaped by informal learning methods. Unlike in other contexts where formal training is predominant, Indonesian guides heavily rely on informal, experiential learning to acquire, adapt, and refine their knowledge and skills. This reliance on informal methods is not merely supplementary; it plays a central role in shaping the guides' professional development and ability to deliver culturally resonant and authentic tourist experiences. These chapters will explore the dynamics of this informal learning process, including how guides engage with local communities, peer networks, and mentorship to enhance their cultural understanding and storytelling abilities. Through this discussion, the author aims to highlight the distinct and adaptive approach that characterises Indonesian guide training, contrasting it with more standardised, formalised methods commonly found in other regions.

Chapter 5 examines the complex role of informal learning in the knowledge acquisition and professional development of tourist guides in Indonesia. While formal training programmes provide structured, foundational knowledge crucial to the profession, it is the ongoing process of informal learning—rooted in real-life contexts and community interactions—that further enriches guides' expertise. This chapter explores how informal learning complements formal education, emphasising the unique methods by which guides acquire, adapt, and refine their knowledge. Drawing on social capital and community collaboration guides not only enhances their own professional skills but also contributes to a collective pool of knowledge that supports culturally resonant and authentic tourism experiences. Through peer learning exchanges, mentorship, and engagement with local communities, these learning processes foster a deepened connection to local heritage, empowering guides to offer nuanced and meaningful narratives. The chapter also considers the limitations and challenges associated with informal

learning, such as potential biases and the complexities of maintaining trust and accuracy in community-based knowledge. Overall, this chapter illustrates how the blend of formal and informal learning enables guides to meet the diverse and evolving expectations of heritage tourism.

5.1 Tour Guide Training in Indonesia: National Standards, Cultural Curation, and the Pursuit of Authenticity

Research has demonstrated how training programmes can increase tourism practitioners' knowledge and skills (Weiler and Ham, 2002). Formal training is often considered the most conducive and structured approach to learning for tourist guides largely because it provides a consistent framework that can accommodate individuals with varying levels of pre-existing knowledge (O'Malley et al., 2013; Specht & Loreit, 2021; Weiler & Walker, 2014). This structured environment ensures that all trainees, regardless of their starting point, receive the same comprehensive education, which is critical in a profession where consistency and accuracy of information are vital to the quality of the service provided. Moreover, formal training typically involves a combination of classroom learning and practical fieldwork, which allows guides not only to acquire theoretical knowledge but also to apply this knowledge in real-world scenarios (Ong, Ryan and McIntosh, 2014).

The pathway to becoming a licensed tourist guide in Indonesia is well-structured and overseen by local tourism offices, operating within the framework of Law Number 10 of 2009 on Tourism. Candidates must complete a formal training programme followed by written, practical, and oral examinations at provincial, district, or city levels. These requirements exemplify what Foucault (1977) describes as disciplinary power, where training and assessment regulate behaviour and produce subjects who internalise bureaucratic norms. Professional identity is shaped less through free negotiation than through surveillance and assessment, embedding asymmetries of authority between the state as regulator and guides as regulated practitioners. While certification confers credibility, it also reflects what Ong, Ryan and McIntosh (2014) term "truth production," in which legitimacy is constructed through prescribed rubrics that define what counts as valid knowledge. In this way, the system privileges compliance and standardisation over creativity and situated expertise, leaving guides' legitimacy contingent on reproducing state-sanctioned narratives rather than developing reflexive or critical interpretations.

Such foundational training is vital, as noted by Lesmana, a trainer from HPI, who states:

The training programmes are essential for guides to effectively handle the complexities of real-world guiding, blending theory with hands-on practice (Lesmana, interview, 13 September 2022).

From the perspective of trainers, the system equips guides with both technical and interpersonal skills necessary for professional competence. However, participants' accounts reveal a more ambivalent experience. While the training ensures a baseline of knowledge and discipline, it also narrows interpretive possibilities, as guides are encouraged to follow prescribed scripts rather than experiment with more adaptive or critical approaches. This tension between institutional aims and lived practice becomes central to how guides negotiate their professional identity.

Positioning certification as the dominant route to legitimacy exemplifies what can be described as institutional permanence, a bureaucratic framework anchored in state regulation. Permanence secures credibility and consistency, but it risks reducing competence to technical compliance. The normalisation process noted by Ong, Ryan and McIntosh (2014) shows how such frameworks suppress flexibility, creativity, and responsiveness to audiences by privileging state-sanctioned scripts over adaptive storytelling. In this study, permanence secures the stability of professional recognition but restricts the interpretive autonomy of guides. Informal learning therefore becomes essential, as it enables guides to adapt formal competencies to specific audiences and cultural contexts.

The HPI training programme is comprehensive, designed to strengthen both technical and interpersonal skills. It covers cultural and historical knowledge, communication, and safety, while also introducing narrative construction so that guides can craft stories that connect tourists with local heritage. The training is practical, involving mock tours, guided field trips, and on-site simulations where participants rehearse delivery under the supervision of senior guides.

Although this curriculum appears holistic, its standardisation reflects a managerialist model of professionalisation. Alignment with ASEAN's Mutual Recognition Arrangement (MRA-TP) and Indonesia's SKKNI rubrics ensures consistency but privileges compliance over creativity. This exemplifies institutional permanence, where certification secures authority but limits interpretive autonomy. Humour, improvisation, and sensitivity to audiences remain undervalued because they cannot be codified into competency standards. This reflects what

Smith (2006) identifies as the Authorised Heritage Discourse (AHD), in which institutional frameworks define legitimate heritage while sidelining alternative perspectives.

At the same time, guides are not passive recipients. They adapt and reinterpret training content through lived practice, echoing Lave and Wenger's (1991) emphasis on learning as social participation. In doing so, they act as cultural brokers (Cohen, 1985; Ap & Wong, 2001; Salazar, 2012), filtering and reframing official narratives to fit local contexts. Professional identity is therefore negotiated in practice rather than mechanically reproduced.

Upon completing the required training, prospective guides must pass a competency exam facilitated by local tourism offices and administered by the *Lembaga Sertifikasi Profesi* (Professional Certification Institute, LSP), which is accredited by the *Badan Nasional Sertifikasi Profesi* (National Professional Certification Board, BNSP). The exam combines written, practical, and oral components, assessing destination knowledge, cultural and historical interpretation, communication skills, and foreign languages. Candidates also undergo a practical simulation where they guide visitors through a site, constructing narratives that highlight history, culture, or distinctive features, alongside practical considerations such as accessibility and visitor needs. An interview follows to evaluate ethics, professionalism, and commitment to the role.

This tiered system begins with *Pramuwisata Muda* (junior guide), progresses to *Pramuwisata Madya* (intermediate guide), and eventually to *tour leader*, with licences subject to periodic renewal. Such structure is presented as a guarantee of quality and credibility, aligning Indonesia's guiding profession with international standards.

However, while certification confers formal authority, its design reflects a disciplinary logic. Exams privilege standardised recall and scripted delivery over adaptive interpretation, ensuring that guides internalise bureaucratic expectations rather than experiment with more responsive practices. In this way, legitimacy is tied to demonstrating conformity to codified norms, leaving little recognition for the improvisational and relational skills that often define meaningful tourist experiences

To align with international standards and strengthen regional competitiveness, Indonesia has integrated the ASEAN Common Competency Standards for Tourism Professionals (ACCSTP) into its certification system. This initiative, developed under the ASEAN Mutual Recognition

Arrangement on Tourism Professionals (MRA-TP), facilitates labour mobility across Southeast Asia and positions Indonesian guides within a wider regional framework (ASEAN, 2013).

In the tourism sector, the *Standar Kompetensi Kerja Nasional Indonesia* (National Work Competency Standards of Indonesia, SKKNI) establishes the skills and knowledge required of professional guides. Developed by the Ministry of Manpower in collaboration with sectoral bodies, the framework sets benchmarks for training, certification, and ongoing development, positioning tour guiding as a recognised profession.

For tour guiding, SKKNI introduced a structured certification pathway in 2007, updated in 2017 to reflect global tourism demands. These revisions strengthened competencies in management, ethics, communication, and service quality, ensuring Indonesian guides remain competitive internationally (Ministry of Manpower of Indonesia, 2023). The Ministry of Manpower also produced training manuals compiled by experienced guides and academics, incorporating modules, assessment tools, and task books. These cover areas such as health and safety, destination knowledge, conflict management, tour reporting, and interpretive skills. While the manuals reflect a holistic vision, they also reinforce standardisation. The *Himpunan Pramuwisata Indonesia* (Indonesian Tourist Guide Association, HPI) actively encourages its members to pursue this certification as a marker of professionalism.

However, while SKKNI is presented as a tool for professionalisation, its competency-based structure reduces guiding to measurable outputs, overlooking the tacit and affective skills that shape authentic visitor experiences. Elements such as humour, improvisation, or the ability to navigate sensitive cultural or political conversations are difficult to codify and therefore remain invisible within the rubric. This reduction does not simply undervalue such practices; it risks reshaping guiding into a transactional service, where legitimacy is tied to ticking competency boxes rather than cultivating the interpretive sensibilities that make tours meaningful.

Indonesia's training programmes remain focused on practical guiding skills and service delivery, a pattern noted in earlier studies that found technical ability prioritised over interpretation (Ap and Wong, 2001; Mason and Christie, 2003; Black and Ham, 2005; Zhang and Chow, 2004). By contrast, the London Blue Badge model combines academic study with practical training. Its content-based lectures from subject specialists provide deeper cultural knowledge that allows guides to develop more layered interpretations and richer visitor experiences (Weiler and Black, 2015; Thomson et al., 2021).

Indonesia's system provides stability and a clear pathway into the profession. However, its reliance on codified standards reflects what I describe as institutional permanence, a bureaucratic structure that secures authority while limiting interpretive freedom. Certification signals credibility but does so by rewarding compliance with prescribed competencies rather than encouraging creativity or reflexivity. Permanence therefore strengthens professional identity on one level while simultaneously narrowing the possibilities of practice.

This emphasis on compliance aligns with global models of mission-based interpretation (Ham, 2016), which frame guiding as the neutral transmission of thematic messages. Such neutrality is never neutral. It privileges institutional priorities such as heritage promotion and national image while silencing contested or marginal perspectives. From a postcolonial perspective, this reflects what Said (1978) described as Orientalism, where dominant institutions authorise certain voices and suppress others. In Indonesia, this dynamic amplifies the narratives of bureaucrats and policymakers while the lived experiences of guides and local communities remain overlooked.

Although Indonesian law requires a guiding licence, many museums permit unlicensed individuals to lead multilingual tours because of high demand. These individuals are generally categorised as volunteer guides. Scholars argue that volunteers are central to the sustainability of museums and heritage attractions, forming a significant part of the cultural workforce (Holmes, 2003; Grenier, 2011). As noted in Chapter 4, many volunteers in Indonesia are expatriates or spouses, though the programmes also attract Indonesian participants. They are typically well educated and often have extensive international experience. As Onad explained, 'I'm a geologist, so I don't have any professional link with this world. But ... I always liked history ... I always liked museums, and I always liked things about ethnography' (Onad, interview, 6 October 2022). Similarly, Gene reflected: 'I studied international studies and Spanish literature ... I developed communication skills like speaking in public, for instance and, for tour content, I read widely because of my own interests in culture and history. I always researched the country I was moving to. (Gene, interview, 19 October 2022).

This pattern confirms Grenier's (2011) finding that many volunteer guides come from diverse educational and professional backgrounds. In Indonesia, volunteers often join organisations committed to heritage preservation, engaging in activities such as tours, language workshops, study groups, and expert lectures. Although they serve without pay, they are still required to participate in training provided by the host institution. These programmes emphasise capacity-

building and are designed to align with the institution's themes and educational aims. Grenier (2011) similarly observed that museums often adopt structured approaches to training volunteers, equipping them with specialist knowledge tailored to their institutional context.

Unlike licensed tourist guides, who typically prioritise generalist knowledge for broad audiences, museum and science-centre volunteers are expected to deliver more detailed, research-based insights. At the Museum Nasional Indonesia, for example, volunteers undergo three months of intensive training led by curators and senior mentors. The programme covers subjects including history, ethnography, textiles, bronzes, treasures, and ceramics. Training materials are produced collaboratively, with handbooks authored by senior volunteers and curators. As Geraldora emphasised:

We have fabulous, compiled handbooks or handouts, though not everything meets the highest standards. But I would say in general, if someone reads these six or seven training manuals, along with some additional catalogues.... they are able to give a fabulous tour already (Geraldora, 19 October 2022).

Upon completing the training, participants undergo assessments, including trial tours with mentor feedback. As Kay explained:

After completing the 12-week training session, you'll need to design your own tour and present a dry run to more experienced mentors for feedback. Following this, you'll conduct a maiden tour with actual visitors, accompanied by mentors who will assist if needed. These two steps are required before becoming a fully qualified guide (Kay, interview, 1 October 2022)

The intensive training provided to volunteer guides is designed to reflect the high standards expected of licensed guides, placing strong emphasis on subject-matter expertise, particularly knowledge of museum resources and collections. As Weiler and Black (2015) argue, such deep knowledge is a critical foundation for delivering high-quality interpretive experiences.

Although volunteers often demonstrate deeper subject knowledge than licensed guides, their authority remains institutionally unrecognised. This paradox exposes a blind spot within institutional permanence, where certification confers symbolic legitimacy but practice-based expertise is undervalued. At the same time, the composition of volunteer cohorts—frequently highly educated expatriates with linguistic and cultural capital—highlights how authority is unevenly distributed. In these contexts, lived experience and informal expertise may enhance interpretation but are legitimised only when aligned with institutional frameworks, leaving local voices more vulnerable to marginalisation. Professional legitimacy is therefore not a

straightforward outcome of training or certification but a socially negotiated process shaped by both bureaucratic permanence and broader hierarchies of power. This underscores the indispensable role of informal learning as a counterbalance, enabling guides to exchange and validate knowledge outside state-sanctioned channels while negotiating the asymmetries embedded within heritage institutions.

However, findings from this study suggest a significant gap between knowledge acquisition and delivery. While many volunteer guides possess adequate subject knowledge, they often lack the practical guiding skills necessary to effectively engage visitors. This includes essential skills such as group management, storytelling, and sustaining audience interest. Thus, the study highlights a tension between the theoretical emphasis on content expertise and the practical realities of interpretive performance in heritage settings. Kay summed up the challenges by each of the volunteer guides participants interviewed in this study:

It was one of the challenges to become a guide. I'd like to talk and I'd like to share information but never did guiding. So it was even a challenge for me to meet the (tour) group and talk to them, you know, in front of a certain number of groups, and especially, you know, to entertain them (Kay, interview, 1 October 2022)

While volunteer guides often possess extensive subject knowledge, a key limitation lies in guiding skills. Mastery of content does not automatically translate to effective communication or visitor engagement. Guides lacking practical skills to connect with diverse audiences, manage pacing, or handle group dynamics may struggle to create engaging, informative experiences. Weiler & Ham (2001) argue that guiding requires not only expertise but also the ability to interpret and present information interactively—an area often overlooked in content-focused training. Neill (2010) adds that while content knowledge is essential, successful educational interactions rely on assessing and adapting to audience needs. In addition, the author reveals that the training manuals for licensed guides primarily emphasise practical guiding skills, while volunteer guide manuals place greater emphasis on history and culture, tailoring content towards educational aspects. This suggests that a lack of practical guiding skills in volunteer training may limit their effectiveness in real-world scenarios.

Another concern raised by participants is that training tends to mould them into the figure of the “ideal guide,” characterised by courtesy, discipline, and compliance. This guiding style prioritises tourist satisfaction and the projection of a positive national image, rather than

encouraging meaningful engagement with cultural or historical content. As Jono explained, the principle instilled through training is that a guide stands as a cultural ambassador of the nation:

It's more about the ideal principle that a tour guide represents the country. Ideally, a guide embodies the hospitality of our nation, which we emphasise as an ethical value in training. Guides are meant to present and showcase the excellence of our cultural heritage (Jono, interview, 10 September 2022).

His reflection reflects what Ong, Ryan and McIntosh (2014) observed in Macao, where training shaped guides into submissive performers who met the expectations of a profit-driven tourism economy. In the Indonesian context, this pattern is reinforced through the state's emphasis on projecting an idealised national image. While this approach provides reassurance to tourists, it narrows interpretive possibilities, constraining guides to act as polished ambassadors rather than adaptive interpreters or ethical storytellers.

Similarly, Kay noted that 'some of the information is the same for all guides', pointing to the generic and impersonal tours produced by prescribed training (Kay, interview, 1 October 2022). Her reflection illustrates how training produces standardised outcomes that limit the relational dimensions of interpretation. As Larsen and Meged (2013) argue, such reliance results in highly staged, repetitive performances that lack vitality. Acil reinforced this point, stating 'After repeating the same tour four or five times in a row, you start to feel tired, just bored ... it's easy to keep repeating the same tour over and over, but it eventually becomes monotonous' (Acil, interview, 22 September 2022).

Acil's statement resonates with Edensor's (2000) observation that heritage performances often become staged and repetitive, and with MacCannell's (1976) claim that guides are positioned to reproduce idealised images rather than adapt responsively to diverse audiences. Monotony is therefore not accidental but symptomatic of institutional permanence, where bureaucratic authority confers stability while constraining interpretive autonomy. However, repetition also acts as a catalyst for experimentation. Faced with the fatigue of delivering scripted tours, guides turn to informal spaces where they rework content, introduce humour, and test new approaches to visitor engagement. What begins as a practical response to boredom becomes an ethical practice, as guides assume responsibility for articulating perspectives absent from official frameworks. Storytelling here is more than a communicative tool; it is a moral act that embeds empathy, critique, and lived experience into tourist encounters.

What begins as a practical response to monotony evolves into an ethical practice, as guides assume responsibility for articulating perspectives absent from official frameworks. This ethical dimension, however, is developed informally rather than through state-sanctioned training. The absence of structured preparation in visitor interaction, as Lumi noted, illustrates the limits of a system that privileges technical competence over lived practice: ‘There isn’t any specific training when it comes to interacting with visitors. It’s something that genuinely comes from our own experiences and how often we engage with people, building on that over time’ (Lumi, interview, 18 October 2022).

Lumi’s reflection illustrates how guides reposition themselves as ethical actors despite institutional constraints. Informal narratives, whether humour, co-stories, or political jokes, draw on lived experiences of neighbourhood struggles, corruption, floods, traffic, and daily survival. These narratives are not merely entertaining anecdotes but ethical interventions that humanise heritage and foster empathy for communities excluded from official frameworks. At the same time, they function as acts of resistance, unsettling the state’s sanitised image of Indonesia and exposing how dominant institutions decide which stories can be told and which must remain silent. This dynamic resonates with postcolonial critiques of heritage interpretation, showing that neutrality is never truly neutral but always embedded in power relations.

By embedding lived realities into their tours, guides assume the role of custodians of memory, treating interpretation as an act of care for the communities they represent. In this sense, storytelling is simultaneously political and ethical—an exercise in truth-telling and empathy-building. It moves beyond MacCannell’s (1976) notion of staged authenticity and Urry’s (1990) tourist gaze, demonstrating that Indonesian guides use informal learning not to reproduce but to destabilise state-sanctioned scripts. What emerges is a different source of professional authority: one negotiated through peer recognition and community trust, rather than conferred solely through bureaucratic certification.

For some guides, informal learning also enabled the inclusion of themes entirely absent from official curricula. Narsih deliberately introduced Pancasila into her tours:

I want to show visitors what Indonesia truly is. I’ve started talking about Pancasila because it’s often overlooked, and no one really discusses it. I believe international visitors should understand what this ideology stands for, so I always make sure to

include it. Additionally, I aim to showcase our country's incredible diversity and richness (Narsih, interview, 20 September 2022).

Such interventions exemplify how guides reclaim interpretive agency, embedding marginalised or overlooked narratives into practice and constituting new forms of professional legitimacy. This reflects Reisinger and Steiner's (2006) critique of objectivist authenticity, which rejects the idea that guiding should transmit fixed truths and instead frames authenticity as something negotiated and co-created in practice. By drawing on overlooked themes such as Pancasila, neighbourhood struggles, or political humour, guides move beyond state-sanctioned scripts to generate new layers of meaning for their audiences. Similarly, Reijnders (2011) highlights how storytelling produces a sense of place by weaving together personal and collective memory. In the Indonesian context, this resonates strongly: guides' informal learning enables them to anchor heritage interpretation in lived experiences that are absent from official curricula. Hitchcock, King, and Parnwell (2010) further remind us that heritage interpretation in Southeast Asia is never politically neutral but shaped by tensions between state agendas and community voices. The findings here extend this insight by showing how guides, through informal networks, reposition themselves not as passive transmitters but as brokers of contested narratives, a role Ap and Wong (2001) conceptualise as central to the guide's professional identity. Echoing Cohen's (1985, 1986) recognition of guides as mediators of meaning, the Indonesian case demonstrates that legitimacy is increasingly derived not from certification alone but from the capacity to ethically integrate community knowledge, everyday struggles, and overlooked ideologies into the visitor experience.

Collectively, these practices demonstrate that informal learning does not merely complement or compensate for the shortcomings of formal training but can be constitutive, generating new authority rooted in lived experience and peer validation. In doing so, guides challenge what Smith (2006) terms the AHD, pushing professionalisation beyond state-sanctioned models. This aligns with Lugosi and Bray's (2008) observation that research often overlooks the cultural contexts of learning, and supports Dahles' (2002) critique that globalised tourism models simplify local traditions. Albrecht, Moscardo and Dwyer (2022) similarly argue that over-standardisation erases guides' unique voices, while Kohl (2013) suggests that guides in developing countries must evolve from show-and-tell performers into facilitators and brokers. The present findings confirm and extend these insights, showing that such evolution is already underway in Indonesia through informal, community-driven learning.

Another concern raised by guide participants is that training moulds them into the ideal guide where courteous, disciplined, and compliant, prioritising tourist satisfaction over critical engagement with content. This observation echoes Ong, Ryan and McIntosh's (2014) study in Macao, which found that guide training often produces submissive figures designed to serve the expectations of global tourism economies. Jono reflected on this ideal when he explained:

It's more about the principle that a Tourist guide represents the country—as a cultural ambassador. Ideally, a guide embodies the hospitality of our nation, that's an ethical value we emphasise in training. Tourist guides are meant to present and showcase the excellence of our cultural heritage (Jono, interview, 10 September 2022).

Jono explained how state authorities have intervened in training content, recalling the case of the 'Jakarta Hidden Tour' which was banned for being seen as tarnishing the country's image. Jono further noted that HPI's code of ethics prohibits any negative remarks about Indonesia, a rule he traced back to national conventions in the 1980s, reflecting the regulatory legacy of the New Order era. Sebastian reinforced this perspective, framing his role as part of a patriotic duty:

Apart from sharing the beauty of this country, I'm always promoting Indonesia. I think, as a citizen, if not me, then who else? Through my learning process, I've realised it's important to give good information in a positive way (Sebastian, interview, 13 September 2022).

These reflections reveal how professional identity is closely tied to nationalist narratives. Training does more than provide technical competence; it embeds an ideological dimension in which guides are positioned as custodians of a polished national image. This illustrates how institutional permanence operates as a political technology, regulating not only professional skills but also the interpretive boundaries of heritage discourse.

The author argues that this emphasis on controlling tourism narratives reflects institutional permanence as ideological continuity. Ethical codes and training scripts, still influenced by New Order directives of the 1980s, discipline guides into producing polished, positive portrayals of Indonesia. As Dahles (2002) observes, tourism narratives were historically crafted to serve state goals of national identity, political stability, and economic growth. Decades later, these legacies remain embedded in HPI's ethical codes, which prohibit guides from voicing critical or nuanced interpretations. Within the revised framework, permanence is therefore double-edged: while it provides stability and authority, it also restricts interpretive autonomy, reducing guides to cultural ambassadors who transmit state-sanctioned images rather than reflexive mediators of complex heritage. This ideological continuity underscores the necessity of informal learning,

where guides find space to negotiate, contest, and reframe dominant narratives in ways that restore authenticity and critical depth.

The influence of Urry's (1976) concept of the tourist gaze and MacCannell's (1990) theory of staged authenticity is evident in Indonesian guide training, where destinations are often framed through marketable images shaped by UNESCO recognition, media visibility, or tourist demand. Such framing privileges spectacle over context and risks commodifying local traditions into consumable products, echoing concerns that culture is reduced to transaction rather than lived practice (du Cros and McKercher, 2020). Training manuals and competency rubrics further reinforce this tendency by prescribing scripts that privilege uniformity, thereby narrowing interpretive autonomy.

However, this study shows that guides are not passive recipients of institutional frameworks. Through political commentary and everyday stories, they reintroduce perspectives excluded from official curricula and transform state-approved performances into spaces of negotiation. In doing so, they destabilise idealised images and reconfigure professional legitimacy so that it rests on lived experience and peer recognition rather than bureaucratic certification. From a postcolonial perspective, this dynamic challenges what Said (1978) describes as Orientalist regimes of representation and what Smith (2006) AHD, both of which privilege institutional voices while sidelining others.

The analysis of formal training demonstrates that institutional permanence provides professional stability and bureaucratic legitimacy while narrowing interpretive identity by emphasising uniformity and compliance. Guides may be recognised as competent representatives of state-sanctioned narratives, but the substance of their practice is constrained by the silences and omissions embedded in official frameworks. The findings also show that guides reclaim interpretive agency through informal learning, positioning themselves as cultural actors whose legitimacy is derived from peer validation, lived experience, and community knowledge. This reconfiguration is not only practical but also ethical, since guides take on the responsibility of telling stories that formal curricula neglect. By embedding critique and marginalised perspectives into their tours, they contest assumptions of neutral interpretation and construct a situated postcolonial professional identity rooted in resistance and ethical care. The following section explores this process of informal learning in greater detail, focusing on how guides use peer networks, lived experience, and community ties to negotiate legitimacy beyond the constraints of formal training.

5.2 The Role of Informal learning in Knowledge Acquisition of Tour Guide

Informal learning should not be understood as a peripheral supplement to formal training but as a structural process through which guides acquire, legitimise, and adapt their professional identity. Its importance is increasingly recognised in tourism studies (Grenier, 2011; McLeod, 2020; Albrecht, Moscardo and Dwyer, 2022), though research specifically on tour guiding remains limited (Kodom-Wiredu et al., 2022). This study shows that informal learning is integral to professionalisation, operating in three interrelated ways. It is complementary, softening the rigidity of state-sanctioned curricula by embedding relational and context-sensitive practices. It is compensatory, addressing the gaps left by competency frameworks, particularly in areas such as visitor interaction and narrative adaptation. It is also constitutive, generating new forms of authority and authenticity that stand outside bureaucratic permanence.

The role of informal learning is pivotal because certification alone cannot capture the skills that make guiding effective. Studies emphasise that while formal training provides a foundation of technical competence, professional identity is actively negotiated through peer networks, community exchanges, and everyday practices (Leask, 2009; Richter et al., 2020). Grenier (2011) observed that it is through informal learning that guides gradually develop confidence and adaptability. Similarly, Lugosi and Bray (2008) argue that the most essential skills for guiding such as handling diverse audiences and improvising narratives—emerge outside formal training environments. Eraut (2004) adds that informal learning is often more effective than classroom education because it is embedded in real-life contexts and shaped by immediate needs. Cohen (1986) and Holloway (1981) underline that information is the guide's primary currency, which explains why guides are continually seeking new knowledge to enrich their narratives and engage visitors more effectively (Rihova and Alexander, 2024).

Participants consistently described peers as vital resources, providing skills, experiences, and insights that extended beyond the limits of formal training. Such reliance highlights that professional competence is not delivered solely by formal institutions but is sustained through the collective expertise of peer networks. Geraldora emphasised that knowledge sharing among fellow guides deepened her understanding and broadened her perspective, allowing her to access cultural and historical insights not found in official manuals:

I think everyone has a specific topic of expertise, like Abdul, who is very much into history and is a (traditional) weapons expert. Mita, on the other hand, is a geophysicist with deep knowledge of geology and volcanology. So if there are some questions, we

will always ask him, if it is about Buddhism or Hinduism, they always ask me (Geraldora, 19 October 2022).

Such exchanges illustrate how informal learning operates in a compensatory role: it fills gaps left by formal programmes that often prioritise uniformity over depth, ensuring guides remain responsive to the diverse demands of their profession. Beyond a technical function, these exchanges also carry an ethical weight where they allow guides to refine stories that restore voices excluded from official curricula, embedding humour, critique, and community struggles as acts of truth-telling and empathy-building. These findings align with Lugosi and Bray's (2013) and El-Sharkawy's (2007) argument that the most important sources of information for guides emerge not from manuals but from direct experience and exchanges with colleagues who hold first-hand knowledge of places. Albrecht, Moscardo and Dwyer (2022) similarly highlights how such experiences shape the substance of guided narratives. The present study suggests that these dynamics go beyond knowledge transfer. Peer interactions also create a shared professional identity, forged through the exchange of perspectives and stories. This demonstrates that professional growth is collectively negotiated rather than individually acquired, complicating dominant views of professionalisation as a linear process delivered exclusively by training institutions. While peer exchange compensates for the limits of formal training, its impact extends further. These interactions do not merely fill curricular gaps but actively generate new forms of authority and authenticity. In this sense, informal learning becomes constitutive of professional identity, enabling guides to construct legitimacy rooted in lived practice and collective recognition rather than bureaucratic certification.

Building on the role of peer exchange, participants also described more structured forms of collective learning. Karta explained how group reading sessions at his museum encouraged deeper engagement with complex subjects and allowed guides to refine their interpretations through discussion: 'We conduct group readings of *The Bandung Connection*. If any sections are challenging to understand, we collectively discuss and resolve them. This collaborative reading is part of our routine preparation for fieldwork' (Karta, interview, 25 August 2022). Mela offered a similar reflection: 'Every Friday we meet with guides and educators for themed discussions such as the Bandung Conference, colonialism, and so on—and we also learn a lot from visitors such as lecturers and historians' (Darla, interview 23 August 2022).

These examples show that collective learning extends well beyond memorisation. It becomes a process of negotiating meaning, pooling perspectives, and co-producing interpretive authority.

Such practices thrive on trust, which enables guides to share knowledge without fear of judgement (Chen & Hung, 2010). As trust deepens, social capital emerges, allowing knowledge to circulate more effectively and equipping participants with skills that may be absent from formal curricula (Yang, 2007). This reflects a social constructivist view of learning (Vygotsky, 1978), where knowledge is co-created through participation.

While group discussions and collaborative readings expand knowledge and strengthen trust, they are not equally accessible. Guides with greater disciplinary expertise or stronger linguistic skills often dominate these exchanges, leaving others to contribute more peripherally (Boud & Middleton, 2003). Informal learning therefore operates in a dual way. It is compensatory, filling gaps left by formal programmes and sustaining professional growth, but it is also stratified, reproducing hierarchies within the guiding community. These tensions show that peer learning is not a neutral process but one marked by uneven access to authority and recognition.

Crucially, these practices extend beyond knowledge-sharing and into the realm of critique. By re-reading and reinterpreting prescribed materials together, guides decentre official frameworks and produce counter-narratives that unsettle Orientalist and bureaucratic representations (Said, 1978). Authority does not rest on certification but is socially negotiated through collaborative labour. In this way, guides are positioned not as passive transmitters of state-sanctioned scripts but as active cultural agents who reframe heritage, embedding local perspectives, critique, and lived realities into their narratives.

Another form of collective learning highlighted by participants is mentorship. Research shows that mentorship strengthens novice guides by linking them directly to experienced practitioners and enabling the emulation of expert practices (Hirsch et al., 2020; Carmody, 2013). Gene illustrated this dynamic:

The senior fellows have been crucial in my guiding development and advising me with their experience and expertise. What I really appreciate is how each mentor has their own style and perspective. It's not just one way of learning—you get a range of insights, which really enriches the experience. Their different approaches help you see things from multiple angles, and that variety makes a big impact on how you learn and grow (Gene, interview, 5 October 2022).

Mentorship enables experienced guides to share the practical, on-the-job knowledge they have acquired over years of guiding, including local insights, storytelling skills, and strategies for handling unpredictable situations. This finding is mirrored in findings presented by Mok (2011),

who highlight that mentoring is utilised to share expertise, and learners are more likely to observe and emulate their pattern. Chang (2006) and Grenier (2011) further note that effective mentorship accelerates learning by combining practical guidance with encouragement and recognition, enabling novices to internalise confidence alongside skill. In this way, mentorship bridges the persistent gap between abstract training curricula and the lived realities of guiding.

Without a formal leader to take on the mentoring role, as discussed by Yang (2007), these opportunities are unevenly distributed. Organisationally embedded guides often benefit from structured mentorship, while freelance or self-employed guides rarely have such support. For them, professional growth depends on informal relationships with senior peers or leaders in associations such as HPI. Freelance guides like Fido, Dana, Tifa and Christie described drawing on these networks as alternative forms of mentorship, accessing advice and solidarity in the absence of formal structures. This shows that mentorship, like other forms of informal learning, is both a compensatory and a stratified resource. It sustains growth but also reflects wider inequalities in access, since not all guides are equally positioned to cultivate such relationships.

Participants also emphasised that formal spaces such as conferences and workshops play an important role in sustaining professional growth. These events expose guides to new theories and practices while simultaneously building networks that extend beyond local associations. Lesmana reflected on his experience at hosting the World Federation of Tourist Guide Associations (WFTGA) brought interpretation into view for his cohort:

At the time, HPI was the host for the WFTGA (World Federation of Tourist Guide Associations), with Rosaline Newland from Scotland as the chairperson. One of the workshops was on interpretation by Sam Ham, and that was actually the first time we started hearing about it... After the session, I approached him and talked about how we could apply interpretation, and he really opened my eyes. He recommended his book to me [...] After that, me and other guides started to see how to approach it—how to guide properly, the techniques, the SOPs, how to manage things in the field, storytelling techniques, and the soft skills, like how to deliver a story the right way (Lesmana, interview, 13 September 2022).

This example illustrates how participation in global networks fosters what Putnam (2000) terms bridging social capital, enabling guides to import new perspectives and adapt them to local contexts. Such encounters create opportunities for innovation that move beyond the confines of nationally prescribed training, positioning guides as agents who translate global expertise into situated practice.

Exchanging knowledge and resources between organisations and associations is common in the tourism industry (Kodom-Wiredu et al., 2022). This dynamic is reflected in Mondo's account, which highlights how collaborations with national and international institutions expand access to resources:

We work with ANRI (the National Archives of the Republic of Indonesia), the National Library, and the National Museum. We also collaborate with foreign archives, such as the Non-Aligned Movement collection in Serbia. Exhibitions are different from papers, you need physical collections, two or three-dimensional objects. In academic writing, quotations may suffice; in a museum you need actual artefacts (Mondo, interview, 23 August 2022).

Through these networks, Mondo gains access to rare archival materials that enrich exhibitions while situating Indonesian narratives within broader global histories. This supports Putnam's (2000) view that bridging ties open pathways to knowledge and resources otherwise unattainable, while also reflecting Coleman's (1988) conception of social capital as an infrastructure that enables individuals to pursue professional goals through shared support. Crucially, Mondo's experience highlights the reciprocal nature of such collaborations, showing that partnerships with international institutions are not extractive but mutually enriching, with expertise and resources circulating in multiple directions.

A key feature of informal learning is its resistance to structured organisation or fixed location. Rather than occurring in classrooms or workshops, learning often emerges in unconventional settings that foster openness and reciprocity (Ehrmann, 2005). These spaces provide opportunities for guides to share practices, update one another on current issues, and collaboratively refine their narratives.

In the Indonesian context, guides frequently described *nongkrong*—the practice of casual meetups in coffee shops or *warung*—as central to their professional development. These gatherings encourage humour, storytelling, and spontaneous discussion, creating spaces where guides exchange insights in conversational rather than didactic ways. Unlike formal workshops, *nongkrong* cultivates reciprocity and mutual reflection, enabling guides to adapt content more responsively to visitor needs. At the same time, these spaces act as counter-publics where guides critique official narratives and experiment with alternative representations of Indonesia. In this sense, *nongkrong* strengthens solidarity while simultaneously disrupting the boundaries of formal authority by legitimising lived experience as a source of interpretive credibility (Smith,

2006). Authority here is grounded not in certification but in peer recognition and community trust, underscoring that professional legitimacy is socially negotiated.

Nongkrong therefore illustrates the *complementary* role of informal learning. It does not replace the authority of formal training but humanises it, embedding relational and contextual dimensions into guiding practice. This dynamic resonates with Sutopo's (2019) work on music subcultures, where *nongkrong* operate as sites of socialised learning based on reciprocity. Romi reflected on gaps in training and reciprocal learning:

Most tourist guides are not really trained in methodology; they mainly receive basic guiding skills. When I started, I had little formal preparation, academically or practically. Ken, a Balinese tour guide, taught me guiding, and I taught him methodology (Romi, interview, 10 September 2022).

Here, learning is not hierarchical but co-created, demonstrating how skills are collectively built through exchange. Beyond competence, *nongkrong* fosters solidarity and belonging, producing a sense of collective identity within the guiding community. This echoes Sutopo and Lukisworo's (2020) findings on music scenes, where *nongkrong* cultivate camaraderie and shared identity through reciprocal practices. It also aligns with Bourdieu's (1986) concept of social capital, as frequent participation builds trust and opens access to knowledge and networks that might otherwise remain closed.

However, the benefits of *nongkrong* are not evenly distributed. Drawing on Fuller and Unwin's (2004) framework of expansive–restrictive learning environments, *nongkrong* can also be restrictive, privileging those who are socially embedded while marginalising newcomers, or less-connected guides. In this way, *nongkrong* operates ambivalently: it complements formal training by restoring flexibility and authenticity but also reproduces boundaries of inclusion and exclusion within the profession.

These tensions are not confined to *nongkrong* alone but also reflect a broader pattern in which knowledge is unevenly distributed and authority negotiated. Informal learning does not only occur among peers but also within the encounters between guides and tourists, where the dynamics of teaching and learning continue to unfold. Tour guiding is frequently compared to teaching, as guides often highlight the importance of sharing knowledge in their role (Holloway, 1981). In this capacity, they are often viewed as both pathfinders and mentors (Cohen, 1985). These roles can create an asymmetrical relationship between guides and tourists, often seen as instrumental, commodified, and power-laden (Smith, 2006). However, this study reveals that

the interaction between guides and tourists is far more fluid and relational, functioning as a process of co-learning in which both parties influence one another. Many guides in the study view these interactions as opportunities to give the stage to the tourists, acknowledging the value of temporary autonomy in enhancing visitor experience. Rather than undermining authority, this reciprocity expands the interpretive space by allowing tourists' expertise to enrich the narrative. Sander illustrates this dynamic:

Just because we are guides does not mean every guide is knowledgeable, it is relative to their expertise. A professor could visit the museum, and some guides might feel uneasy, thinking, 'Oh, this is challenging.' However, I find joy in such situations; it is an opportunity to learn (Sander, interview, 24 September 2022)

Sander's quote illustrates how authority is not diminished but repositioned, as guides recognise visitors as collaborators in meaning-making. Acil similarly explained how she incorporated visitors' contributions into her practice:

Sometimes my audience is very knowledgeable—they know more than I do. For example, once I was telling the story of how Ganesha got his elephant head, and there was an Indian visitor who already knew the story. In the end, she said, 'Yes, you told it mostly right, but actually, there's a deeper reason. Ganesha was supposed to guard Parvati's door while she was bathing.' I was like, 'Oh!' It was great because she didn't judge me; instead, she added to my knowledge in a helpful way, which was really valuable (Acil, interview, 22 September 2022).

Karta's experience also highlights this process of co-learning:

At that time, I had a visitor who was a professor from the USA, an African-American who was very supportive of equality issues, and the information he shared was incredibly new to me. It enriched my understanding of the Asia-Africa Conference, and I believe his insights were credible, as my discussion was directly with a professor whose expertise is in international relations (Karta, interview, 25 August 2022).

Taken together, these examples demonstrate that authority in guiding is not a fixed attribute conferred through certification but a relational practice continually negotiated in real time. They reinforce Rihova and Alexander's (2023) observation that guides often value and acknowledge visitors' superior knowledge. In this sense, knowledgeable visitors, much like peers in informal networks, act as co-creators of meaning, transforming tours into collaborative learning encounters. This dynamic aligns with Weiler and Walker's (2014) view that guiding increasingly involves co-creation, while challenging earlier claims that guides fear being overshadowed by expert tourists (Larsen & Meged, 2013; Murdy et al., 2016). The findings suggest that informal learning is not confined to back-stage spaces but emerges in the

immediacy of tourist encounters, where humility, adaptability, and shared expertise reframe interpretation as a dialogical and ethical practice.

This dialogical reframing also brings authenticity into sharper focus. If authority is co-created through relational encounters, then authenticity becomes less about reproducing official facts and more about negotiating lived experiences, emotional connections, and local knowledges. In this sense, authenticity is not a static quality embedded in heritage objects but a dynamic process shaped through interaction, often revealing tensions between community voices and the commodifying pressures of global tourism. While Wang (1999) argues that authenticity is shaped by visitors' perceptions within their social world, the desire for authentic experiences remains a key motivator for heritage tourists (Ahns, 2023; MacCannell, 2008; Poria et al., 2009). The findings in this study reinforce this perspective, as many guides emphasised the importance of offering visitors experiences that are both authentic and reflective of local culture. As Juminten explained:

For us, the soul of the programme is interaction. It is not only about the physical activities—[gamelan], [batik]—but about our team engaging with local residents. Guests sometimes wander the *kampung* on their own, explore, and strike up conversations. That is what many visitors seek, and it becomes a form of cultural exchange for us as well (Juminten, 26 October 2022).

Juminten's reflection frames authenticity as an individual responsibility, where guides enrich their narratives by sharing local stories that are often absent from official accounts and published literature. While this emphasis highlights the creative agency of guides, it also risks reducing authenticity to personal style, leaving unaddressed the structural silences embedded in heritage discourse. The findings of this study show that authenticity is not only crafted through individual storytelling but also collectively negotiated. Guides collaborate with elders and local communities to recover, preserve, and co-create narratives that would otherwise remain hidden, ensuring that authenticity reflects a broader constellation of voices rather than a single perspective.

Collaboration with local communities emerged as a crucial dimension of guiding practice in this study. Rather than positioning themselves as sole interpreters, guides often draw on community knowledge to enrich and legitimise their narratives. This is particularly evident in their engagement with elders, whose oral histories and lived experience provide insights absent from formal training or published texts. As Kamil, a trainer from Bandung, explained, 'In our organisation, guides meet with local elders and ask about the old days. We do not rely only on

textbooks; we build tours from the lived memories of people who have been here for generations' (Kamil, interview, 25 August 2022). Extending this point, Niken described how such work deepens her own knowledge while contributing to cultural preservation: 'One of my most memorable moments was sitting with a respected elder in Bayan, Lombok. I listened to his stories and wrote them down so we can keep them for future generations. That is one way we safeguard these cultural narratives' (Niken, interview, 27 August 2022).

These practices highlight how informal learning with local communities anchors heritage interpretation in lived experience, addressing concerns that official frameworks risk overlooking the realities of place (Bajec, 2016; Hsieh et al., 2017; Frenzel and Blakeman, 2015). Building from individual encounters, Niken also employs more structured participatory methods that extend collaboration from one-to-one exchanges to collective processes. Drawing on Kohl's (2013) participatory-interpretative framework in Labuan Bajo and Penyengat Island, she explained:

We adopt a participatory-interpretative approach in which community members are actively involved in the process; we work together to co-create narratives that reflect their collective identity and heritage. It is about enabling them to share their own experiences and culture (Niken, interview, 27 August 2022).

This practice disrupts the AHD (Smith, 2006) by shifting interpretive authority away from experts and enabling local stakeholders to define what aspects of their heritage matter most. In doing so, it resonates with broader calls to re-centre local heritage as deeply personal and community-embedded, rather than subordinated to the demands of global tourism (Apaydin, 2018; Smith & Akagawa, 2009; Waterton, 2005). Dines (2016) and Smith (2006) further suggest that local heritage often carries deeply personal meanings for host communities. Recognising heritage in this way allows communities to reclaim their narratives, fostering a more inclusive and intimate approach to interpretation.

Taken together, these findings suggest that collaboration with host communities is not peripheral but constitutive of heritage guiding. Informal engagements with elders ensure the survival of overlooked stories, while participatory frameworks institutionalise community voice within interpretive practice. Both approaches empower communities to reclaim their narratives and invite tourists to engage with heritage in more intimate and plural ways. At the same time, they expose the political stakes of interpretation, challenging top-down models of

heritage that silence local perspectives and reinforcing the ethical responsibility of guides as mediators of community voice.

While collaboration with host communities enriches authenticity and strengthens heritage interpretation, it also exposes the vulnerabilities of informal learning. Informal learning, though highly beneficial, presents challenges that can affect its effectiveness and integrity, particularly in a diverse society such as Indonesia, where multiple ethnic groups create complex cultural dynamics. Building and maintaining networks with local communities and experts is essential for accessing valuable knowledge. However, these relationships are not always seamless. Social barriers, including language differences, cultural misunderstandings, and mistrust between communities and external actors, can impede knowledge-sharing and weaken opportunities for meaningful collaboration (Putnam, 2000).

Moreover, the main sources that make informal learning distinctive such as oral histories, community knowledge, and local expertise, are shaped by the partiality of memory and cultural interpretation. Personal perceptions and selective recall may lead to the omission of certain experiences, while community biases can privilege dominant voices at the expense of marginalised ones. Barton and Hamilton (1998) caution that while the situated nature of informal learning enriches understanding by grounding knowledge in lived contexts, it can also distort interpretation if not critically examined. Ensuring inclusivity therefore requires careful navigation, balancing the immediacy of lived testimony with the recognition that no single account can capture the full complexity of heritage.

In this study, guides reflected on these tensions by emphasising the central role of trust and social capital. Bourdieu (1986) reminds us that networks provide access to resources and knowledge, but they also risk reinforcing existing assumptions if left unchallenged. Wenger's (1998) theory of communities of practice similarly shows that while such communities foster learning through participation, they also require mechanisms to validate knowledge to prevent the uncritical circulation of errors or biases. These concerns were echoed by several guides when asked how they ensured the reliability of knowledge derived from informal learning.

Fido, for example, explained that he places particular trust in the accounts of long-term residents and native community members:

Using the perspective of people who have lived there for a long time or are natives of the area is considered more valid. This means that the information can be trusted because it comes directly from those who have experienced daily life there for an extended period, including those born there (Fido, interview 2 September 2022).

Fido's response highlights the value placed on local authority and embedded experience as safeguards for reliability. His emphasis resonates with Albrecht, Moscardo and Dwyer's (2022) conclusion that host community narratives provide authentic and culturally embedded knowledge, offering depth and nuance often absent from formal training or educational materials. However, privileging such sources is not without risks. Reliance on long-term residents or elders may reproduce hierarchies within the community itself, silencing younger or less powerful voices, or overlooking alternative perspectives shaped by gender, class, or ethnicity. In this sense, authenticity and reliability are themselves contested, continually negotiated within the politics of community life.

While Fido emphasised the authority of long-term residents as the most trustworthy source of information, other guides adopted a more systematic strategy to address the same concern of reliability. Rather than privileging a single perspective, they sought to cross-check and corroborate information from multiple sources. Jono explained:

We always cross-check what we hear. If a local guide shares a detail, we verify it against books or reliable online sources, and we tell visitors where it comes from. For example, at the Kraton Yogyakarta museum we might hear a story from an *abdi dalem* (royal servant); later, on the bus, we add context from H. J. de Graaf's *Kejayaan Mataram* (The Glory of the Mataram Kingdom) (Jono, interview, 10 September 2022).

Jono's method illustrates how triangulation strengthens credibility in informal learning environments. By weaving together oral testimony, lived experience, and written sources, guides not only enhance the richness of their narratives but also model a form of critical reflexivity. This practice reflects Abdelhamid's (2020) observation that triangulating knowledge promotes deeper understanding by situating local accounts within broader historical and scholarly contexts. In doing so, guides signal to tourists that heritage interpretation is neither singular nor static but layered, contingent, and always open to revision. The value of this approach becomes clearer when set against the risks of relying solely on oral histories. As Fido emphasised, long-term residents and elders are often seen as the most authoritative sources. While such testimony provides invaluable cultural depth, it can also be shaped by selective memory, nostalgia, or the desire to present communities favourably. Vansina (1985) reminds us that oral traditions, though crucial, must be read critically, while Barton and

Hamilton (1998) caution that informal learning may distort as much as it clarifies if narratives are accepted uncritically.

However, triangulation is not a straightforward corrective. The very act of validating oral accounts through academic texts risks reasserting the hierarchies embedded in AHD (Smith, 2006). In this sense, triangulation is double-edged. It enhances the credibility of narratives by grounding them in multiple sources, but it also privileges written authority as the benchmark of truth, potentially diminishing the interpretive weight of lived perspectives. What appears to resolve the limitations of oral testimony may simultaneously reinforce the exclusions it seeks to address.

The findings therefore illustrate that the challenge is not choosing between oral tradition and textual authority, but negotiating the tension between them. Both forms of knowledge are partial and situated, when held together they create richer, more layered accounts of heritage. This balancing act echoes Clifford's (1988) notion of partial truths, where cultural representation is never definitive but always contested and provisional. For guides, this negotiation is both methodological and ethical: it requires deciding how to honour community voices while maintaining credibility, positioning them as mediators who continually navigate the line between validation and marginalisation.

This section has shown that informal learning is not an auxiliary addition to training but a structural mechanism that enables guides to negotiate, contest, and extend their professional legitimacy. Through peer exchange, mentorship, collective reading groups, *nongkrong*, conferences, visitor interactions, and collaboration with communities, guides cultivate knowledge and practices that humanise and expand the rigidities of formal curricula. These dynamics demonstrate that professional identity is not secured through certification alone but is socially negotiated in everyday practice, drawing authority from lived experience, community ties, and dialogical engagement with tourists.

At the same time, informal learning is neither universally accessible nor free from hierarchy. It operates within boundaries shaped by linguistic capital, social embeddedness, and institutional expectations. While these practices often enrich authenticity and preserve overlooked narratives, they can also reproduce exclusions and reinforce dominant voices. This ambivalence underscores the need to view informal learning not as a uniformly emancipatory process but as one marked by power relations, contestation, and selective inclusion.

The contribution of this study lies in demonstrating that informal learning is simultaneously complementary, compensatory, and constitutive. It complements formal curricula by embedding relational and contextual practices; it compensates for the gaps left by competency frameworks, especially in areas such as visitor interaction; and it constitutes alternative sources of authority that challenge institutional permanence and state-sanctioned narratives. By foregrounding this tripartite role, the findings extend current theories of heritage interpretation and professionalisation, showing that guides are not passive recipients of official training but cultural agents who reshape legitimacy through every day, situated practice.

This conclusion provides the basis for the following section, which compares how these dynamics unfold differently in Jakarta, Bandung, and Yogyakarta. The comparative reflection demonstrates that informal learning interacts with national training frameworks in uneven ways, shaped by the historical, political, and cultural specificities of each city.

5.3 Comparative Reflection on Training and Informal Learning

The purpose of this section is to reflect comparatively on how these domains interact across Jakarta, Bandung, and Yogyakarta. A comparative perspective is important because the same national framework does not produce uniform outcomes. Instead, each city demonstrates a distinct balance between institutional structures and informal practices, shaped by its cultural, political, and historical context.

The analysis considers how formal and informal domains interact in practice, whether as complementary, compensatory, or constitutive forces, and how these interactions influence the ways in which guides acquire skills, sustain knowledge, and legitimise their professional identity. In Jakarta, where training is continuous and highly institutionalised, informal learning plays a complementary role by softening the rigidity of formal curricula. In Bandung, where training is episodic and fragmented, informal networks compensate for gaps and ensure continuity. In Yogyakarta, where legitimacy is closely tied to heritage institutions, informal learning is constitutive, forming the very foundation of authority and identity.

This comparative reflection not only clarifies the differences across the three contexts but also highlights the politics of professionalisation. Authority in Jakarta is projected through bureaucratic stability, in Bandung it is sustained through peer resilience, and in Yogyakarta it

is anchored in cultural custodianship. The following subsections examine each city in detail before drawing the analysis together in a comparative summary.

Jakarta represent the most institutionalised training environment for tourist guides in Indonesia. The city is home to the headquarters of HPI as well as the P4EKRAF training centre, where training programmes are continuous, highly formalised, and assessed under SKKNI rubrics by accredited LSPs. This infrastructure reflects bureaucratic permanence: professionalisation is embedded within state routines and policy frameworks, with certification signalling competence to employers and tourists.

This permanence, however, comes with costs. Guides repeatedly describe the monotony of repeating tours that follow identical scripts. Examinations and structured assessments encourage accuracy and compliance but leave little space for creativity or adaptation to audience needs. As a result, guides risk being positioned less as independent interpreters and more as carriers of state-sanctioned messages. Professional identity in Jakarta is therefore stable, but often constrained, disciplined by rules that reward uniformity and penalise deviation.

Against this rigidity, informal learning provides a counterbalance. Outside the classroom and examination hall, guides gather in cafés, meetings, or community events to test stories and exchange feedback. In these peer spaces, they find the freedom to insert critique or everyday stories about life in Jakarta where perspectives absent from official training materials. These exchanges give guides a different form of legitimacy, one grounded in the approval of colleagues and the lived realities of audiences rather than in certificates.

Jakarta therefore reflects a dual dynamic. On one side, formal training offers authority and stability; on the other, informal practices restore relevance and vitality. Guides do not simply submit to bureaucratic permanence but actively reinterpret it, using informal learning as a space for adaptation and subtle resistance. Professional identity here is constantly negotiated, caught between the authority of the state and the recognition of peers and audiences.

Bandung's guiding landscape stands in contrast to Jakarta. Training here is not permanent but episodic, often linked to short-term projects or city branding initiatives. Guides may benefit from well-funded programmes when they appear, but these are irregular and rarely sustained. Once projects end, formal opportunities vanish, leaving long gaps that weaken continuity.

In this fragmented environment, guides rely on informal learning to sustain themselves. Storytelling circles, community museums, and peer gatherings provide a platform to exchange knowledge and refine skills. These networks act as the backbone of professionalisation, filling the void left by inconsistent training. Peer groups not only keep knowledge alive but also allow guides to experiment with new content that reflects Bandung's identity as a creative city.

This creativity, however, is always shadowed by the city's colonial heritage. Bandung's architecture and urban design remain dominated by Dutch legacies, which continue to frame many tourist itineraries. Guides must decide whether to reproduce these familiar colonial stories for visitors or to reinterpret them through a local perspective. Informal exchanges become vital here, offering safe spaces to test new ways of presenting Bandung, sometimes ironic, sometimes critical that complicate the image of colonial grandeur.

Bandung therefore illustrates how informal learning is more than a stopgap for missing training. It sustains professional identity in precarious conditions while also creating room for postcolonial negotiation. Professionalisation here is not secured by the state but maintained by solidarity, creativity, and the willingness of guides to challenge inherited narratives.

Yogyakarta represents a very different model again. While formal training exists, it is not the main source of legitimacy. Certification may be valued, but guides consistently describe their authority as rooted in the *Keraton*, palaces, and heritage institutions that define Yogyakarta as the cultural heart of Java.

For Yogyakarta guides, guiding is not simply a job but a lifelong vocation tied to custodianship. Learning happens through mentorship and intergenerational storytelling, where knowledge is passed down from elders and embedded in community traditions. Authority flows not from certificates but from recognition within these cultural networks.

This embeddedness gives guides authenticity and depth. Tours are enriched with cultural memory, ritual, and lived experience, and storytelling is framed as a moral responsibility to preserve and transmit heritage. Guiding in Yogyakarta is therefore both professional and ethical — a duty of care for cultural continuity.

At the same time, this strength creates limits. Authority tied so closely to local institutions can be difficult to translate into broader markets where flexibility and entertainment are valued.

Yogyakarta's model provides deep cultural legitimacy but narrows the scope of practice beyond its immediate heritage context.

Professionalisation here is therefore constitutive rather than supplementary. Informal learning is the foundation of legitimacy, shaping guides' authority through custodianship and community recognition. To be a guide in Yogyakarta is to be a custodian of memory, where professional identity is inseparable from ethical responsibility to heritage.

The comparison across Jakarta, Bandung, and Yogyakarta shows that informal learning plays different roles depending on how training is structured locally. Jakarta illustrates how bureaucratic permanence offers stability and state recognition, but leaves little space for creativity. Here, informal practices complement the rigidity of formal training, restoring relevance by allowing guides to adapt and personalise their narratives.

Bandung presents the opposite challenge. With no continuous system, professional development is fragmented and dependent on short-term projects. In this setting, informal learning compensates for the absence of sustained provision, becoming the backbone of knowledge-sharing and a platform for negotiating the city's colonial heritage.

Yogyakarta highlights a third model, where legitimacy is anchored in heritage institutions and custodianship rather than in certification. Informal learning here is constitutive, forming the foundation of professional identity and embedding guiding within intergenerational mentorship and cultural responsibility.

The three cases collectively demonstrate that professionalisation in Indonesia cannot be reduced to national frameworks alone. It is shaped by how guides negotiate between state structures, local contexts, and peer practices. Table 5.1 summarises these differences by outlining the dominant training models, the roles played by informal learning, and the ways in which professional identity is constructed and sustained in each context.

Table 5.1 Comparative Configurations of Formal Training and Informal Learning in Jakarta, Bandung and Yogyakarta

City	Training Model	Role of Informal Learning	Professional Identity
Jakarta	Bureaucratic permanence – continuous, state-led, compliance-focused	Complementary – softens rigidity of formal curricula	Negotiated between state recognition and peer validation
Bandung	Episodic provision – project-based, fragmented, irregular	Compensatory – sustains skills and continuity between training gaps	Sustained through solidarity, creativity, and postcolonial reinterpretation
Yogyakarta	Heritage embeddedness – rooted in cultural institutions and custodianship	Constitutive – foundation of legitimacy and professional identity	Defined by custodianship, intergenerational mentorship, and moral responsibility

Source: Author's fieldwork, 2022

This comparison highlights that informal learning cannot be treated as a secondary or residual activity. In Jakarta it complements state-led permanence, in Bandung it compensates for fragmented provision, and in Yogyakarta it constitutes the foundation of professional legitimacy. What emerges is a picture of professionalisation as a negotiated process, where authority is not conferred solely by certificates or state frameworks but is continually reshaped through peer practices, cultural custodianship, and community recognition. The table therefore underlines the central claim of this chapter: that informal learning is integral to the making of professional identity in Indonesian guiding.

5.4 Chapter 5 Summary

Chapter 5 has examined how tourist guide training and informal learning are experienced and negotiated across three Indonesian cities. Section 5.1 showed that formal training, grounded in national law and competency-based frameworks, provides stability and bureaucratic legitimacy but often at the cost of creativity, reflexivity, and interpretive autonomy. Training privileges uniformity and compliance, positioning guides as ambassadors of state-sanctioned narratives and reinforcing asymmetries between the state as regulator and guides as regulated practitioners.

Section 5.2 revealed that informal learning is not merely an add-on to formal training but a central mechanism of professionalisation. Through peer exchanges, storytelling, and community interactions, guides create spaces that operate as both ethical and resistant practices.

By weaving humour, co-stories, and everyday struggles into their tours, they disrupt authorised discourses, humanise heritage, and foreground perspectives that state curricula neglect. This positions informal learning as a postcolonial practice of truth-telling and empathy-building, highlighting guides' role as ethical actors rather than passive service providers.

Section 5.3 demonstrated how these dynamics play out differently in Jakarta, Bandung, and Yogyakarta. In Jakarta, informal practices complement bureaucratic permanence, softening rigidity while sustaining relevance. In Bandung, they compensate for fragmented and project-based training, keeping professional identity alive through solidarity and creative reinterpretation of colonial legacies. In Yogyakarta, informal learning is constitutive, forming the foundation of legitimacy through custodianship and intergenerational mentorship. The comparative analysis therefore challenges the notion of a uniform, nationally defined model of professionalisation, showing instead that guiding identities are continually negotiated in relation to state authority, peer recognition, and cultural responsibility.

The contribution of this chapter lies in reframing informal learning as central to the making of professional identity in Indonesian guiding. Rather than treating it as a secondary or residual activity, the analysis demonstrates that informal learning operates simultaneously as a complement, a compensation, and a constitutive force, depending on local conditions. It also advances debates on professionalisation by foregrounding ethical responsibility and postcolonial resistance as integral to how guides legitimise their practice. In doing so, the chapter moves beyond descriptions of training systems to argue that Indonesian guides are active cultural agents who reshape professional authority through everyday acts of negotiation, adaptation, and care.

Building on these insights, the next chapter turns to the narratives that guides construct in their daily practice. If Chapter 5 demonstrated how professional identity is shaped by the interplay of training and informal learning, Chapter 6 explores how this identity is enacted through storytelling. Here, the analysis examines how guides select, frame, and adapt narratives to construct authenticity, embedding ethical responsibility into the way they represent Indonesian culture. By blending informal learning with lived experience, guides move beyond official scripts to create accounts that challenge stereotypes, reveal overlooked aspects of everyday life, and foster deeper connections between visitors and communities. This focus on narrative practice shows how authenticity is not only a technical goal but also an ethical commitment, positioning guides as both interpreters of culture and custodians of memory.

CHAPTER 6

CONSTRUCTING AUTHENTIC NARRATIVES

This chapter explores how Indonesian tour guides construct authentic narratives through a blend of informal learning and lived cultural experiences, presenting tourists with a nuanced view that challenges conventional portrayals of Indonesian destinations. Unlike traditional narratives shaped by the “tourist gaze” and media representations, the narratives crafted by these guides aim to dispel misconceptions and foster a more profound understanding of Indonesian culture. Through immersion in local traditions and engagement with their communities, guides develop insights into the motivations behind cultural practices, allowing them to create narratives that address both celebrated and often-overlooked aspects of Indonesian identity. This chapter examines how guides carefully select, frame, and negotiate these narratives to reveal Indonesia’s multifaceted culture. Additionally, by employing universal themes and interpretation tools, guides enhance visitors' emotional connection to Indonesia, ultimately positioning themselves as agents of cultural representation and active shapers of societal perception.

6.1 Redefining Indonesian Tourism Narratives: The Power of Informal Knowledge and Cultural Insight

In interpretive tour guiding, narrative construction is a critical process that shapes the visitor's experience and understanding. This section delves into the complexities of narrative construction, emphasising the integral role played by various sources and the profound influence of guides' personal and professional experiences. By integrating a multitude of formal and informal knowledge, guides are able to construct narratives that are not only informative and engaging but also rich in authenticity and depth.

The role of tourist guides as cultural mediators is increasingly crucial due to the dynamic interplay between local traditions and global influences. According to Hampton and Clifton (2016), the representation of tourist destinations in media often shapes global perceptions,

which guides must navigate to present a more nuanced view. The tourist gaze, as a social construct, is not always positive and often involves asymmetrical power relations (Bunten, 2014, Larson, 2014). Although it has been recognised that the tourism industry is largely built on meeting these visitor expectations, this often places pressure on locals to conform to the gaze, overshadowing authentic cultural expression (Mannheimer, 2024). As Indonesia becomes more integrated into the global community through enhanced tourism and media exposure, traditional narratives are continuously adapted and redefined. Tourist guides are at the forefront of this process, tasked with translating and adapting local narratives in a way that is both understandable and engaging for an international audience, while also preserving the authenticity that makes these narratives uniquely Indonesian.

By examining tour guides' lived experiences, this study explores how they navigate the expectations of the tourist gaze while educating visitors about the local realities. These lived experiences are invaluable in shaping how guides interpret and convey information, creating a richer, more authentic experience for tourists. Bruner's theories (1990) on narrative construction illustrate how narratives can be structured to enhance understanding and engagement by linking personal experiences with broader historical and cultural contexts such as guide's familiarity with local ceremonies or customs enables them to share insights that transcend textbook knowledge. This informal understanding, rooted in personal experiences, family traditions, community involvement and even acquired through peer learning, enriches their storytelling, allowing them to present a multi-dimensional view that reflects both historical context and living culture. Each guide's unique perspectives add depth to the narratives they craft, influencing how historical events and cultural practices are portrayed and understood. This approach is particularly valuable in regions with diverse ethnic and cultural backgrounds, such as Indonesia. Utilising this informal knowledge adds authenticity to their storytelling, helping tourists to appreciate the complexities of the culture in a way that standardised which formal training may not achieve.

Many participants in this study noted that their lived experiences significantly shaped their interpretative narratives. By weaving personal experiences into the broader context of heritage interpretation, guides add a layer of relatability that mere facts or descriptions may lack. These lived experiences are portrayed as valuable tools in the interpretative process, not just stories, but strategic elements that enrich the narrative by providing real-life examples of how historical or cultural concepts manifest in everyday life. Guides see their role as an opportunity to correct

misconceptions and present an accurate reality of the sites they represent. This commitment is seen as essential not only for ensuring visitors leave with a truthful understanding of the destination but also for preserving the cultural integrity of the sites themselves. Fido, one of the guides, exemplifies this: ‘They don't understand what life is like for us in Jakarta, with all the harsh realities that we face. So, for them (tourists), there were like ‘wow’ (Fido, interview, 22 September 2022). Guides draw on their lived experiences to address misconceptions and alter tourists’ perspective, particularly when it comes to portraying the realities of social life. Through these narratives, they provide explanations—especially for foreign tourists who may have a limited understanding of local social dynamics. Fido’s choice of bringing his lived experience to the tour narrative supported by Sebastian who testified how his experience as a Jakarta native is crucial in challenging and reshaping tourists' preconceived notions about life in the city that allow him to present a more nuanced view that goes beyond stereotypes, helping visitors to see Jakarta from an authentic perspective:

In Indonesia, you’ll often see people by the roadside during the day. This can raise questions, like ‘Does this mean poverty is high here?’ or ‘What percentage of people are unemployed?... I often explained, ‘Here in Indonesia, we work in shifts – morning, afternoon, evening. Maybe they work in factories with rotating shifts, or perhaps they enjoy outdoor meals. So, people bring food from home and gather outside to relax for a bit. Indonesians work at a comfortable pace, but we work longer hours.’ This kind of explanation can subtly change their perspective, making them realise, ‘Oh, Indonesia isn’t quite what I thought....’ I find more respectful ways to explain it, as we’re talking about our country here. And sometimes, that can change their perceptions of Indonesia or its people (Sebastian, interview, 13 September 2022).

Sebastian further continued his by explaining how he demystifies unfamiliar cultural practices for his audience. By spotlighting tourists’ encounters with the everyday lives of the local community, Sebastian brings clarity to cultural practices that might otherwise seem foreign or perplexing. Through this approach, Sebastian bridges cultural divides, making the unfamiliar more accessible:

When I guided groups of Spaniards on Fridays, (we encountered) local people that want to perform Friday prayers in West Java, everyone wears sarongs. One person asked me, why are these people wearing skirts?’ I explained that it's not a skirt, it's a sarong (Sebastian, interview, 13 September 2022).

Sebastian's explanations serve as a cultural bridge between his Spanish tour group and the local customs, illustrating the vital role of tourist guides as intermediaries. Weiler and Black (2015) argued that bridging cultural gaps is central to a guide's role, helping tourists from diverse backgrounds connect with and appreciate the cultural nuances of the places they visit. An inquiry from a tour group member about *sarong* being similar to "skirt" highlights typical cross-

cultural misunderstandings, underscoring the importance of a guide's role in addressing and correcting such misconceptions. Sebastian's effective clarification fosters respectful interactions between visitors and locals, reshaping preconceived notions about cultural symbols and practices. Most of the walking tour guides in this study emphasise that spontaneous interactions with the local community are among tourists' favourite experiences. Through these interactions, tourists not only gain an authentic experience but also gaining informal knowledge and learn the values from the locals, as exemplified by Juminten:

Interacting with locals and observing everyday street life is a big part of the experience here. For instance, there are many men in this area who enjoy keeping birds; it's a local tradition, and there's a whole trade around bird cages. You'll often see birds in cages lined up along the alleyways. Visitors find it fascinating—they stop to take photos and ask, 'Why are there so many birds here?' It's simply part of the local lifestyle. Recently, even more people have started keeping birds, partly because there's a belief that they serve as a warning of impending disaster. These kinds of stories add layers of meaning (Juminten, interview, 26 October 2022).

By engaging with locals and observing everyday life, tourists gain a unique perspective on the cultural essence of a destination. These interactions enrich the tourist experience by providing insights that often go beyond traditional or global narratives, offering context and depth to cultural practices. For example, the local custom of birdkeeping, combined with the belief that birds signal impending disaster, reflects a worldview deeply rooted in the community's beliefs. By incorporating these insights into tour narratives, guides enable tourists to navigate cultural complexities, promoting meaningful engagement and empowering local communities by affirming their traditions and knowledge. These organic exchanges create a mutual learning environment, where both locals and tourists gain knowledge and respect. Guides like Sebastian and Jojo exemplify this, using personal insights to make local narratives accessible and bridging gaps between tourist expectations and authentic culture (Richards & Wilson, 2019; Smith, 2018).

Some guides draw on their personal experiences to challenge existing biases and introduce different perspectives through thoughtful narrative selection and framing. This strategy proves especially impactful when tourists are exposed to unfamiliar cultures. Lesmana, a devout Muslim, exemplifies this approach in addressing prejudice:

When I take tourists to visit Istiqlal Mosque, I often address how Muslims are portrayed in the media, especially the persistent stereotype linking Islam to terrorism. However, when visitors experience it firsthand—through Q&A sessions and direct interactions—they see a completely different reality. They're warmly welcomed; people are laughing, and taking photos (Lesmana, interview, 13 September 2022).

Furthermore, by sharing their own reflections and interpretations, guides can present an overarching portrayal of Indonesia, offering tourists a well-rounded understanding that topics often overlooked :

The narrative is often told about how well-organised everything was, with a pavilion, a prison, and a mosque, and then there's always talk about the market and the cinema, with people mentioning the excitement of movie screenings. But I see it differently. I see what used to be there—a cinema divided into two sections, with Europeans on one side, where they could clearly see the screen properly. Meanwhile, our people were on the other side, watching a reversed image because the screen was made of translucent fabric. It had been divided into European and local sections, and this is something that's rarely discussed. But I believe it's important to raise this awareness, to recognise how we were treated (Dana, interview, 24 August 2022)

Similar to Dana, another guide, Kamil, reinterprets his walking tour in Bandung. Rather than simply glorifying the city's Art Deco architecture, he provides thought-provoking insights into the disparity between colonialism and the challenges faced by the city's native residents. Another example to incorporate darker historical themes to their tours, Ghofar, who experienced Indonesia's reformation period and the fall of Suharto, weaves his experiences into his narratives. As a walking tour guide, Ghofar not only strives to distinguish himself from competitors offering similar tours of Jakarta, but he also believes it is crucial to highlight Indonesia's turbulent history. This approach helps visitors understand that the country's political struggles are recent and continue to shape its identity.

It's about being more aware of the state of the country—understanding what's really going on, what's right, and what's wrong. In reality, it's not about right or wrong, but about what is actually happening. We still have a lot of unresolved issues from the past, like human rights, for instance, or recognising that the country isn't in an entirely good place right now (Ghofar, interview, 14 September 2022).

Ethical considerations are crucial for guides tasked with interpreting sensitive historical and cultural topics, such as colonialism, political turmoil and ethnic conflicts. Ensuring factual accuracy and inclusivity while delivering information is crucial. This responsibility includes maintaining neutrality, crucial in fostering an environment where all perspectives are valued, thereby enriching the educational aspect of tours. The findings in this study also explore how guides address controversial topics and how they negotiate these sensitive subjects in their narratives. This approach involves carefully selecting stories that educate and encourage critical thinking and dialogue among visitors, broadening their perspectives and fostering a deeper understanding of complex issues.

The following quote from Lesmana illustrates how he deliberately crafts controversial topics to spark discussions that will engage and challenge his audience, encouraging them to think critically and engage in meaningful dialogue about complex issues:

In (Jakarta) Chinatown, we would discuss “why, as a minority, they are successful in the economy? This goes against the common perception – it's controversial. When we go to Sunda Kelapa, we create controversial topics like the issue of flooding surrounded by plastic waste. Why do people choose to live here despite the floods? (Lesmana, interview, 13 September 2022).

Lesmana’s insights underscore the importance of cultural sensitivity in addressing potentially sensitive topics. Tour guides, by carefully navigating these subjects, show respect for both tourists’ and locals’ values, enhancing the destination's identity while preserving cultural and educational integrity. Such direct engagement with difficult topics, as Cohen and Cooper (2019) suggest, provokes thoughtful discussion and reflection among tourists, enhancing their understanding of the socio-economic and cultural dynamics of the areas they visit. This sensitivity allows for the recognition of cultural narratives' significance without compromising factual accuracy. Mannheimer (2024) affirms that tour guides’ need have a careful consideration to negotiate and present the sensitive narrative but also maintain respectful to the resident. As noted by Saville (2022) and Kafy (2021), respecting local voices in tourism value lived experiences. By carefully addressing sensitive topics and acknowledging diverse perspectives, tour guides can enhance the educational value of their tours while fostering a deeper appreciation for the cultural significance of the places they represent.

Another participant, Tifa, shared her experiences of how she carefully narrates sensitive subjects:

Not everyone is familiar with every item we encounter on our tours. For instance, sea cucumbers, commonly consumed in Chinese cuisine, might be unknown to some. We take the opportunity to explain such items. When we come across vendors offering exotic foods like frogs, escargots, or soft-shell turtles, we provide context, perhaps comparing escargots to their revered status in France, introducing visitors to diverse culinary traditions. Yet, we're careful about sensitive topics, such as turtle butcheries in Glodok, discussing them only when deemed appropriate (Tifa, interview, 7 September 2022).

She added:

Our guiding narrative enriches the experience by weaving intriguing local insights and culinary discoveries into the main tour, which is particularly beneficial for foreign tourists seeking a deeper connection with local culture and traditions. We aim to make these insights accessible to all, recognising that even locals might not be familiar with every aspect discussed (Tifa, interview, 7 September 2022).

Tifa's reflections on the importance of cultural sensitivity highlight how guides can either reinforce or challenge moral disengagement through their narratives and interactions with

tourists. According to Sharma (2024), moral disengagement occurs when individuals rationalise or justify unethical behaviour, allowing them to distance themselves from the moral implications of their actions. This can manifest when guides choose to sensationalise sensitive subjects, such as the consumption of exotic foods or local practices that may be viewed as controversial. Tifa's approach to explaining culinary items, such as sea cucumbers and escargots, demonstrates an effort to educate tourists while respecting local traditions. By providing context and comparisons, guides can foster a deeper understanding of cultural practices, thereby mitigating the potential for moral disengagement. However, the careful handling of sensitive topics, such as turtle butcheries, underscores the need for guides to exercise discretion and ethical judgment. This means recognising the potential impact of narratives on both tourists and local communities and striving to present information that honours cultural integrity while remaining factual.

Moreover, guides use their unique position to mediate tourists' experiences, selecting and framing narratives that challenge existing prejudices and foster new perspectives, particularly in settings with unfamiliar cultures or controversial issues. The guide's role as an intermediary, as discussed by Weiler and Black (2015), facilitates cultural understanding and empathy, making the learning experience more personal and memorable. By influencing tourist attitudes through compelling content, guides ensure that tourists and locals feel comfortable and respected, emphasising the transformative potential of storytelling in heritage interpretation. This strategy educates and inspires, bridging the gap between different cultural perspectives and enhancing the overall tourist experience.

The narratives crafted by tour guides, grounded in their lived experiences, foster a sense of belonging and connection to national identity. The emotional bonds that guides establish with their audiences can significantly shape visitors' perceptions of this shared identity. (Wang et al. (2024) found that positive emotional experiences at tourism sites enhance national pride and identity among visitors. A practical example of this narrative approach is seen in the way guides discuss Pancasila, Indonesia's foundational ideology. Many guides thoughtfully infuse Pancasila's principles into their tours, highlighting its significance as a symbol of national identity. This approach reflects a broader commitment to vividly convey Indonesia's essence, ensuring that both local and international visitors appreciate the deep-rooted values of unity and diversity embodied by Pancasila. For instance, Narsih, speaks passionately about her approach

to integrating Pancasila into her tours. She recognises that, while often overlooked or assumed to be understood, Pancasila's deeper significance deserves exploration.

My objective is to portray Indonesia's essence to my audience vividly. Recently, during my tours, I have incorporated discussions about Pancasila, an overlooked topic. Many tend to disregard it, assuming it is inherently understood. However, as a local guide, I feel compelled to delve into Pancasila because it is not merely an ideology but a fundamental part of who we are. Non-local visitors must comprehend its significance and grasp the principles it represents, emphasising our unity in diversity. In essence, I aim to unveil the true essence of Indonesia through my perspective. It is not merely about showing off the physical richness and diversity but also conveying the intangible richness embedded in our culture and heritage." (Narsih, interview, 20 September 2022)

Even non-Indonesian tour guides recognise Pancasila as an important and foundational concept to present to visitors, as they learn from the lived experiences of their Indonesian colleagues that Pancasila is deeply ingrained in Indonesian identity. The strategies employed by participants in this study reflect the findings of Albrecht, Moscardo and Dwyer (2022) where non-native tour guides compensate for their lack of cultural authenticity by drawing on the knowledge of native guides. This approach ensures accuracy and cultural sensitivity in the information they share with visitors. Onad summarised the perspectives described by each participant interviewed in this study:

I spend more time in Pancasila, explaining the Garuda, the Sutasoma..... I see myself there, people who haven't been in Indonesia before. They don't know anything about the size of the country, the diversity that is in this country (Onad, interview, 6 October 2022).

These examples' emphasis on nationhood, and the strategic use of Pancasila in their narratives, align with MacDonald (2022) and Bhandari (2019), who underscore the complexity and fluidity of national identity and cultural heritage and argue that tourist guides actively construct and communicate national identity through lived experience. This dynamic role of guides in narrative construction is echoed by other participants in the study, who share a deep sense of nationhood and pride in their cultural identity, influencing how they craft and deliver narratives to their audiences. For example, Mondo reflects, 'At least when they (visitors) leave the museum, they have a sense of pride in their nation' (Mondo, interview, 23 August 2022). This statement highlights the role of tour guides in fostering a sense of national pride among visitors, especially through the guides' own lived experiences and connection to national identity. When tour guides share stories, symbols, and values deeply rooted in their cultural background, they invite visitors to experience the same pride and connection they feel. By presenting narratives

that underscore the uniqueness and diversity of the nation, tour guides aim to ensure that visitors leave with a deeper understanding and appreciation of the country's identity.

However, there is a debate about having neutral narratives in tour guiding because guide's personal interests, values, and experiences can influence how they emphasise and frame certain aspects of a narrative, potentially creating biases in how information is interpreted and presented. This approach brings challenges, as discussed by Cohen (1985), who highlights the potential for personal narratives to create biases. Cohen argues that while infusing personal values can make tours more engaging and thought-provoking, it requires careful management to ensure that it does not alienate or mislead tourists. As we discussed above, tour guides, as intermediaries between tourists and the local community, often infuse their personal perspectives, beliefs, and experiences into the narratives they present. This bias can manifest in various ways, influencing how information is framed, what stories are prioritised, and how local customs and practices are interpreted. One of the primary ways personal bias affects tour guiding narratives is through the selection of content. Guides may choose to emphasise certain aspects of a topic that resonate with their own experiences or beliefs, potentially leading to a skewed information. Ghofar presents a perspective by questioning the extent to which personalisation or individual expression should influence guided tours. He raises important considerations about the balance between a guide's personal touch and the need to maintain professionalism and accuracy in delivering factual information. This viewpoint stimulates a discussion on how much a guide's personal experiences and opinions should be integrated into their narratives without overshadowing the historical and cultural contexts they aim to convey:

They taught us in (training) class, 'You have to narrate neutrally; even if tourists ask about controversial things, your answer should also be neutral, neutralise it.' But I don't think I can do that, I can't. But there are tour guides who adhere to those standards, just telling the usual neutral stories. But for me, my mission, my message is more like political matters, human rights and such (Ghofar, interview, 14 September 2022).

Ghofar's approach exemplifies the ongoing debate about the extent to which personal values should influence professional narratives in the field. While standard training often underscores the importance of neutrality to ensure a consistent and broadly acceptable tour experience, Ghofar's decision to infuse personal and politically charged themes into his tours represents a significant departure from these norms. This reflects a broader trend identified by scholars like Weiler and Black (2020), who discuss the delicate balance tour guides must strike between delivering standardised content and incorporating personal insights that may enhance visitor engagement and understanding. Moreover, Pine and Gilmore (1999), in "The Experience

Economy," suggest that personalising experiences by incorporating the guide's unique perspectives can transform ordinary tours into memorable and impactful experiences. This perspective supports the idea that by sharing personal values, guides like Ghofar are not merely informers but also educators and advocates, potentially deepening tourists' connections to the cultural and historical contexts they explore.

The lived experiences of tour guides are invaluable in shaping narratives that bridge local culture with tourists' expectations. This approach aligns with Lugosi and Bray's (2011) observation that guides are increasingly encouraged to infuse their narratives with their lived experience. By doing so, guides move beyond standardised information, creating a more personalised and engaging experience that can positively influence tourists' attitudes. This study further reveals that guides possess the agency to reinterpret and reframe heritage narratives, helping visitors gain a nuanced understanding of Indonesia's complex social fabric.

In this role, tour guides become active agents in shaping how their society wants to be perceived by visitors (Mannheimer et al., 2022). This influence empowers them to challenge stereotypes and reshape tourists' preconceived notions, fostering empathy and dismantling misconceptions. Weiler and Black (2015) emphasise that guides mediate cultural exchange by crafting immersive narratives that encourage visitors to look beyond superficial assumptions. This role aligns with research highlighting guides as cultural ambassadors who contribute to intercultural understanding and, ultimately, positive social change (Reisinger & Steiner, 2006). Furthermore, this study mirrored in findings presented by Albrecht, Moscardo and Dwyer (2022) that highlight that guides' lived experiences are crucial to their effectiveness, providing a depth that formal training cannot replicate. By drawing on their upbringing, cultural context, and personal history, guides enrich storytelling with authentic insights into everyday life, offering visitors a more profound connection to the culture they encounter.

6.2 Enhancing Narrative Engagement in Interpretive Tour Guiding

In the field of interpretative tour guiding, enhancing narrative engagement is crucial in creating memorable and impactful experiences for visitors. This section examines various strategies employed by guides to enhance audience engagement. These methods include personalising historical events to make them more relatable, emphasising universal themes that resonate across cultures, and simplifying complex ideas through analogies and metaphors. By tailoring these approaches to the specific audience, guides create deeper connections with the material,

ensuring that both the emotional and intellectual aspects of the narrative are accessible and engaging to a diverse range of visitors. Additionally, interactive engagement techniques such as experiential and immersive activities help to solidify the visitor's connection to the content. Lastly, the section will discuss the role of contextual visualisation through visual aids and digital tools, which are instrumental in making abstract concepts tangible. Each of these strategies plays a crucial role in enriching the tour experience, making historical and cultural narratives both accessible and engaging for diverse audiences.

6.2.1 Universal Themes

Ham (1992, pp. 12–15) argues that interpretation is most effective when it is structured around universal themes—ideas such as love, conflict, justice, or belonging—that transcend cultural boundaries and enable audiences to relate personally to unfamiliar contexts. The findings demonstrates that Indonesian guides frequently employ this strategy, embedding local narratives within broader human experiences that resonate with diverse visitors. By anchoring culturally specific narratives in these universal themes, guides act as cultural mediators who preserve the authenticity of heritage while ensuring its accessibility to international audiences. This interpretive practice highlights that the effectiveness of guiding lies not only in factual accuracy, but in the ability to transform local heritage into globally recognisable human experiences.

One way guides realise these universal themes in practice is through the use of analogy and metaphor, which render complex cultural or historical information accessible and engaging to visitors (Ham, 1992, p. 14). Aries demonstrates this approach vividly in his interpretation of Borobudur. To explain the symbolism of the temple's clockwise circumambulation, he draws on a metaphor of imperfection and self-improvement that resonates across cultures. He notes that the ritual begins on the left, a side that in many Asian traditions is associated with imperfection. "Starting from the left," he says, "is like admitting, 'I'm not perfect.' In Buddhism, recognising one's flaws is the first step in self-improvement" (Aries, interview, 30 September 2022). As visitors progress through each level, they move from left to right, which Aries frames as a journey from imperfection to goodness, culminating in enlightenment. Each completed circuit, marked by exiting on the right, represents a step forward, yet each new ascent on the left signals that there is always more to learn. As he explains, "you've gone through a whole journey of self-reflection and growth, embodying the path to enlightenment"

(Aries, interview, 30 September 2022). By framing Borobudur's architectural design within the universal theme of moral and spiritual evolution, Aries enables tourists from diverse backgrounds to find personal relevance in their visit. This supports Salazar's (2008, pp. 12–13) observation that guides frequently employ analogy to make the ingenuity of Borobudur intelligible to international audiences by connecting it to widely recognisable symbolic frames.

By framing the story of Borobudur's construction and its intricate stone carvings within broad, universally resonant themes, tourist guides facilitate a profound connection for visitors from diverse cultural backgrounds. This approach enriches the educational aspect of the tours by making the historical and spiritual significance of the monument accessible and relevant to a global audience.

Moreover, by linking these personal stories to universal themes such as sacrifice, resilience, and ambition, guides make these narratives relevant to a diverse audience. Visitors from different backgrounds can see reflections of their struggles and triumphs in these stories, which deepens their engagement with the narrative. This method of narrative construction helps create a more comprehensive and relatable historical discourse that effectively bridges the gap between past and present, making history a vibrant part of contemporary cultural understanding.

Personalising historical events is a powerful interpretative strategy that enhances the relatability and impact of narratives presented by tour guides. This approach transforms potentially abstract and distant concepts into intimate and engaging stories that resonate with visitors on a personal level. By focusing on individual experiences and stories, guides bring history to life, making it more tangible and accessible. The theoretical foundations of this approach are grounded in the scholarly work of Falk and Dierking (2012), who emphasise the importance of connecting content to visitors' lives to enhance the memorability and impact of museum experiences.

In personalising historical narratives, guides enhance storytelling by exploring the emotional and personal sacrifices of key figures in Indonesia's struggle for independence. Mondo, for example, vividly recounts the stories of leaders such as Amir Syarifuddin and Mohammad Hatta at the museum. He illuminates the complex pressures and decisions these leaders faced, providing a deeper understanding of their profound commitments and the personal costs they endured. As Mondo explained, 'Amir Syarifuddin, despite being a communist, served as head

of the government at that time. In his position, one might also feel conflicted or uncertain about the Renville Agreement” (Mondo, interview, 23 August 2022). He further highlighted that Amir Syarifuddin’s leadership during the Renville Agreement reveals the weight of steering Indonesia through critical negotiations, while Mohammad Hatta’s role in accruing national debt to secure sovereignty illustrates the immense burden of his decisions at both personal and national levels. These narratives not only recount historical events but also forge an emotional connection, transforming visitors’ engagement from factual absorption to empathetic understanding. This approach brings historical figures to life, making their sacrifices relatable and deepening visitors’ appreciation of the complexities of Indonesia’s path to independence.

An interesting finding in this study is how guides at a heritage observatory—where most of the content is scientific—use universal themes (Ham, 1992, p. 14) to bring historical figures to life by emphasising passion and dedication. Marley, for example, introduces visitors to the founder of the observatory, Karel Albert Rudolf Bosscha (Marley, interview, 29 August 2022). Rather than recounting only factual details about the observatory’s creation, she highlights his personal motivations and background. In doing so, she portrays Bosscha as a dynamic individual whose passion and dedication were central to the establishment of the observatory:

Before delving into astronomy stories, we set the stage with the motivation behind establishing this significant place, shedding light on its founders and the driving force behind its creation. What distinguishes Bosscha Observatory is the unique spirit of individual generosity that pervades its history. Unlike institutions funded by the government or scientific organisations, Bosscha Observatory owes its existence to individuals, notably Mr. Karel Albert Rudolf Bosscha. His passion for astronomy, fuelled by a bequest from his grandfather upon his arrival in the Dutch East Indies, led him to establish an observatory community.....Such stories of individual dedication and generosity form an integral part of our narrative about the Bosscha Observatory, illustrating how personal passion and commitment can shape the trajectory of scientific endeavours (Marley, interview, 29 August 2022).

Using this universal theme not only humanises historical figures but also inspires visitors by connecting them to the passion and dedication driving the scientific endeavour. It transforms abstract concepts and events into relatable stories, allowing visitors to engage with the human aspects behind the achievements. Marley’s method highlights the critical role of storytelling in making scientific content more accessible and engaging to visitors. By focusing on the heritage and personal stories associated with the observatory’s establishment, the narrative gains a richness and relevance that extend beyond traditional scientific exposition. The narrative demonstrates the profound impact of individual passion and dedication in the pursuit of

knowledge, transforming the observatory tour into a compelling experience that resonates with visitors on both an intellectual and emotional level.

These examples of using universal themes in their narratives demonstrate that guides do not strictly adhere to a standardised, fact-based historical narrative as described by Salazar (2005). Instead, they employ creative approaches to reinterpret history, making it more accessible and relatable for visitors. This flexibility aligns with research by Ham and Weiler (2002), who highlight the importance of "thematic interpretation" in heritage tourism, where guides use universal themes to bridge cultural and temporal gaps between historical figures and modern audiences. By incorporating these themes, guides not only convey facts but also evoke emotions, enabling visitors to form a more personal connection to the story. Larsen and Meged (2013) also note that interpretive freedom allows guides to infuse their narratives with elements that resonate with diverse audiences, moving beyond rigid historical accounts. This approach enriches the visitor experience by adding depth and relatability to the narrative, demonstrating that heritage guides play an active role as cultural interpreters, creatively reimagining history to foster understanding and engagement.

6.2.2 Sensory Participation

Engaging visitors interactively is a crucial strategy for enhancing the tour experience and deepening the educational impact. This approach transforms passive spectators into active participants, providing them with hands-on experiences that foster a more profound connection with the local culture. The discussion on interactive engagement is pivotal within the broader context of interpretation tools and techniques, which transcend traditional guided tours by weaving in elements like role-playing, interactive demonstrations, and hands-on activities. This multifaceted approach allows participants to engage more intimately with the cultural, historical, or environmental facets of the tour site, fostering a richer understanding and appreciation, and rendering the experience both informative and memorable. This comprehensive strategy of employing interactive and immersive methods, as highlighted by scholars such as Ham (1992) and Beck and Cable (2011), underscores the effectiveness of experiential learning techniques. These methods, which promote active participation and sensory engagement, are crucial for deepening visitors' understanding and appreciation of the sites they visit, transforming passive observation into an engaging and enriching encounter with the destination's cultural heritage.

Indonesia's rich culture, with its deep-rooted traditions, art, and heritage, can be further enhanced through interpretative tools that engage human sensory perception. By using tactile elements, sounds, scents, and even tastes, guides create immersive experiences that allow visitors to physically connect with cultural content. This sensory-based, immersive approach helps transform cultural and historical narratives into vivid experiences, making Indonesia's heritage not only accessible but also unforgettable for diverse audiences. Each of these strategies enriches the tour experience, presenting Indonesia's cultural heritage in ways that resonate emotionally and intellectually, offering a multifaceted, sensory-engaged journey through the archipelago's history and traditions. For example, Bobby underscores the significance of incorporating active participation into tours to enhance visitor retention and understanding. He particularly highlights the Wudu' or Islamic ablution process, explaining, "Upon arriving at the Luar Batang Mosque, rather than solely explaining the ablution process, we invite visitors to perform it themselves, engaging all five senses to fully absorb the experience" (Bobby, interview, 13 September 2022). This hands-on method significantly enriches the learning experience by fostering a direct, sensory connection with the cultural practice, making it more vivid and memorable.

Echoing Bobby's experiential approach, Sebastian, a seasoned tour guide, utilizes interactive techniques to connect tourists with local customs. He facilitates participation in traditional activities such as rice harvesting, where tourists touch the grains and learn about the labour involved. Sebastian notes, "It's crucial to let them feel and even try for themselves, like experiencing the texture and taste of durian or participating in rice harvesting" (Sebastian, interview, 13 September 2022). These immersive interactions provide tourists with a tangible appreciation of the intricacies of local life and the labour behind agricultural practices, enhancing their understanding of cultural and economic contexts.

Similarly, Christie enhances interpretative activities by incorporating gamified elements into her tours, making them not only educational but also entertaining. Her approach transforms learning into an adventure, engaging tourists in scavenger hunts and interactive games that deepen their engagement with cultural and historical contexts. Reflecting on this approach, she explained: "When we designed Jawa Trail, the idea was how to make participants directly involved with the site through games. We create clues with a theme and participants must explore different places based on those clues, which then leads to a group discussion at the end. The aim is always two-way interaction" (Christie, interview, 22 October 2022). This illustrates

how guides move beyond transmitting factual information by embedding learning within interactive experiences that resonate emotionally and intellectually, reinforcing the broader argument of this study that effective interpretation is rooted in participation and shared meaning-making.

In addition to gamification, Christie also highlighted the importance of visual aids in simplifying complex topics, particularly for younger audiences. As she noted: “By using the media we choose, such as photos, we can reduce complexity and weight of these issues to a level that children and teenagers can understand through those photos” (Christie, interview, 22 October 2022). She recalled how visual media prompted a young participant to reflect: “Oh, so culture isn’t solely about dances, right? Because at school, that’s often the main association with culture” (Christie, interview, 22 October 2022). Such moments demonstrate how photographs can expand perspectives by showing culture as a lived reality encompassing traditions, challenges, and ways of life, rather than being reduced to performance. This reinforces Brochu and Merriman’s (2010) argument that visual aids are indispensable tools for interpreters seeking to bridge complex knowledge with public understanding.

While Christie’s experiences illustrate how visual tools can open up cultural interpretation for younger audiences, Jasmine applies similar techniques in the scientific domain. At the heritage observatory, she explained: ‘Using images of astronomical objects is an easy and powerful way to dive into our narrative. We often use photographs and pictures of celestial objects and representations of the sky to start discussions’ (Jasmine, interview, 29 August 2022). These visual prompts encouraged participants to ask questions such as “What are we seeing here?” and “Why does it appear this way?”, which became entry points for critical thinking and deeper exploration. This process highlights how visual imagery can simplify complex astronomical phenomena, sparking initial attraction and curiosity while also supporting analytical engagement. It echoes Wong and Wang’s (2009) argument that visual materials stimulate curiosity, Bowie and Chang’s (2005) emphasis on exploratory learning, and Tsaur and Teng’s (2017) observation that visual examples make intricate concepts more accessible.

Most participants also recognised that photographs are invaluable in visually allowing the audience to compare the past and present. For instance, Ghofar consistently uses historical photographs during his walking tours to vividly demonstrate the dramatic changes that heritage buildings have undergone:

This building is often a wow factor for tourists because it did not look like that before. There are actual photos from the past, and I find that showing those photos is a way to create an "Oohh" response. It shows them what it used to look like, how it changed, and how it functioned in the past. And then, in the end, I hold back one surprising fact." (Ghofar, interview, 14 September 2022).

Ghofar's quote highlights the physical transformations and the shifts in function and symbolism that the building has undergone over time. He utilises historical photographs to elicit an "Oohh" response from tourists as a technique to create emotional engagement. This method involves presenting photos while strategically delaying a surprising fact until the end, thus maintaining narrative suspense and keeping the audience interested throughout the tour. This approach not only enhances engagement but also makes the experience more memorable. Additionally, allowing visitors to compare historical and present images visually deepens their appreciation for the building's historical and cultural significance. This strategy supports Weiler and Black's (2015) assertion that using photographs to compare past and present conditions enhances understanding and appreciation of a site.

Another visual aid that emerges throughout the discussion is maps, which serve as another vital interpretative tool that enriches the visitor. Guides experienced in leading international visitors frequently emphasise that maps are foundational to their tours. According to museum guides such as Lumi and Kay, maps are indispensable for helping international visitors understand the geographical layout of Indonesia, a country known for its sprawling archipelago. Lumi stated, 'Starting with a map is essential for foreign visitors who are often not familiar with the concept of Indonesia, including the different regions shown on the map' (Lumi, interview, 18 October 2022), Kay also have the similar opinion, 'Visitors are not always familiar with the names of the islands, so having a map to refer back to is crucial, even though we explain the map of the whole of Indonesia at the beginning of the tour' (Kay, interview, 1 October 2022). Both quotes highlight the significant role of maps in addressing the challenges international visitors encounter when navigating the complex geography of Indonesia's many islands. Maps serve not only as aids for wayfinding but also as essential tools for enhancing the learning and retention of geographical data during museum tours and other educational activities. By incorporating maps into these settings, guides foster a spatial understanding, helping visitors overcome their initial unfamiliarity with the area. This approach aligns with MacEachren's (1995) arguments, which discuss the power of maps to convey complex spatial relationships and historical data effectively. By integrating a nuanced interpretation of maps, interpretive guides and guides help tourists grasp the intricacies of geographical narratives and their

historical implications, a concept that is also supported by Wood's (1992) "The Power of Maps," which discusses how maps communicate and shape our understanding of the world around us.

Furthermore, maps encourage interactive engagement by allowing visitors to track discussed locations visually. This interactivity enriches the learning process and enhances the overall tour experience, making it more enjoyable and participatory. While much of the existing research focuses on maps primarily as tools for navigating tourist destinations and attractions (Chang, 2015; McIlwraith, 2018; Lee et al., 2017), their potential to provide interpretative insights and enhance geographical familiarity is often overlooked. These findings highlight the importance of recognising maps as crucial tools in guided tours, especially for addressing visitors' unfamiliarity with a country's geographical context. This suggests that emphasising the uses of maps beyond simple navigation can improve the interpretative experience for tourists.

Some participants enhance their presentations by integrating maps and photos as concrete references for the discussed objects. This combination helps visually anchor the information, making it easier for the audience to understand and relate to the presented subjects. exemplifies this integration:

"I have to print the map of Indonesia; I carry it in my bag just to show where we are. For example, when I show the Ikat from Sumba, I should show it on the map of Indonesia, where Sumba is. So, I need more props, maybe a photo of how Ikat is made. When I explained the technique of making Ikat, I did not explain it so well. So, I should have photos to show people. Props are here to explain better something I cannot say in words." (Acil, interview, 22 September 2022).

Acil's quote highlights visual aids' critical role in transforming abstract concepts into tangible understanding. Acil points out the difficulties inherent in verbally explaining the intricate process of making Ikat textiles and identifies photographs as a powerful solution to provide clarity. These findings underscore the limitations of relying solely on verbal communication to convey complex processes and illustrate the profound capability of visual storytelling to surmount these challenges. Acknowledging the necessity for effective communication, it becomes evident that visual aids are essential complements to verbal explanations, not replacements. They effectively reinforce and clarify concepts that might remain elusive when expressed only through words.

The discussion with participants also explored how visual aids have evolved through the integration of digital devices. These devices enable interpretive guides to utilise multimedia elements like digital pictures and photographs, videos, interactive maps, and augmented reality,

thus making heritage and cultural concepts more accessible and engaging for audiences. For instance, Acil provides a compelling example of this integration during her tours. She uses her iPad to demonstrate the practical applications of the museum's collections to the visitors. By connecting items displayed in the museum with their real-world uses, digital media enriches the visitor experience, deepening their understanding and appreciation of the exhibits:

To enhance my UNESCO-themed tour, I incorporated digital elements to showcase Indonesian culture vividly. I intend to play Gamelan music on my phone for an immersive auditory experience for the Gamelan segment. Furthermore, using my iPad, I will integrate *Wayang Kulit* into my tour by displaying a 20-22-second clip of a *Wayang Kulit* performance on stage. This video serves as a demonstration and a vital tool to bring museum exhibits, often perceived as static or "dead objects," to life. It acknowledges the limitations of verbal descriptions alone and leverages technology to provide a more engaging and dynamic interpretation of cultural heritage (Acil, interview, 22 September 2022).

To show a film of *Wayang Kulit* on stage, Acil allows visitors to experience dynamic aspects of the culture that static displays or verbal descriptions alone might not fully convey, offering a more immersive learning experience (Huang, Weiler and Assaker, 2015). By acknowledging the limitations of verbal descriptions in capturing the essence of cultural practices like “*Gamelan*” and “*Wayang Kulit*”, the use of digital visual aids is recognised as a strategy to enhance the narrative, providing a more nuanced and engaging portrayal of cultural heritage through visual storytelling (Yu, Weiler and Ham, 2002; Black and Ham, 2005). Furthermore, the use of accessible technology for educational purposes aligns with a theme of accessibility and inclusivity, aiming to make cultural heritage more accessible to a broader audience, including those who may not have the opportunity to experience these cultural practices firsthand (Hughes, 1991).

Throughout the discussions with participants, various examples were provided of how digital tools enhance guided tours. Tifa's quote highlights the significance of digital visual aids in illustrating the transformation of places and objects over time in an immersive manner: ‘....., I keep aerial videos and photos on hand, providing a comprehensive view that words alone might not achieve, thus capturing the area’s picturesque quality from a bird’s-eye perspective.’(Tifa, 7 September 2022)

Tifa’s quote emphasises the effectiveness of digital visual aids, such as images and videos, in communicating certain aspects of cultural heritage, including architectural beauty and historical changes, which might not be as effectively conveyed through words alone. Utilising aerial

photos and videos to provide a comprehensive view of locations such as the Kali Besar offers a spatial understanding that surpasses maps alone. This aerial perspective grants visitors a unique vantage point, enhancing their appreciation of the site's layout and aesthetic similarities to European settings. The interactive element of displaying videos and photos on demand creates an engaging learning environment. This method brings history to life and enriches the overall tour experience by forging a dynamic connection between historical contexts and their relevance today.

In another interview, Lumi, took this discussion further by highlighting their use of digital device as a means to explain historical narratives:

Tablets can effectively explain historical narratives, offering dynamic visual aids that enhance the learning experience. For example, they can be used to display images that illustrate the shape and culinary uses of spices like cloves, which were highly sought after by Europeans. These digital displays can help visitors visualise and understand the historical significance of such commodities in global trade.

Additionally, tablets enable guides to present detailed visuals of prominent landmarks that may not be physically present in the museum. For instance, despite only having a Buddha's head from Borobudur in the museum, a tablet can be used to show detailed images or videos of the entire temple complex. This approach helps overcome the physical limitations of the exhibits by providing a more comprehensive understanding of the monument's architectural grandeur and historical context. This method not only enhances the storytelling but also brings to life the rich cultural heritage that might otherwise be constrained by the physical limitations of the museum's collection (Lumi, , interview, 18 October 2022).

Lumi emphasises the pivotal role of technological tools in providing cultural and historical context within museums. By illustrating the spread of Hindu-Buddhist influences from India or the historical European demand for spices, these tools help contextualise artefacts beyond their aesthetic appeal, enhancing visitors' understanding of their broader historical narratives. Visual aids such as images of cloves or landmarks like Borobudur are crucial in storytelling, especially when physical displays cannot fully represent the original sites or objects. These aids allow the interpretive guides to overcome the limitations of their physical exhibits and enable a more comprehensive representation of cultural heritage.

The integration of digital devices such as tablets in museums plays a pivotal role in enhancing visitor experiences, particularly through the use of visual aids that deepen understanding and appreciation of historical and cultural artefacts. These technologies enable guides to provide engaging narratives that are both informative and interactive, catering to a diverse audience's informational needs and preferences. By showcasing detailed visuals and videos, such devices

can compensate for the physical limitations of museum collections, offering a comprehensive view of significant landmarks and historical contexts. Falk and Dierking (2013) highlight the significant role of these visual aids in enriching the museum experience, particularly by facilitating a deeper learning context. This approach benefits visitors who prefer to explore independently and enhances guided tours, making them more dynamic and immersive. The adoption of multimedia in guided tours transforms the standard presentation into an interactive exploration that resonates more profoundly with visitors.

Furthermore, the integration of these technologies into the training of tourist guides and interpretive guides is increasingly advocated to adapt to modern technological advancements. Weiler and Black (2020) emphasise that this strategic incorporation of digital tools into tour guiding can greatly enhance the interpretative capabilities of guides, thereby enriching the overall visitor experience. This approach ensures that guides and interpretive guides are equipped to meet today's global tourists' varied needs and preferences, making heritage attractions more accessible and engaging.

6.3 Chapter 6 Summary

This chapter has examined the distinctive role of informal learning and lived experiences in shaping Indonesian tour guides' narratives, allowing them to deliver authentic and culturally resonant experiences that go beyond the traditional "tourist gaze." Through data analysis, this chapter demonstrates how guides construct narratives that challenge the often oversimplified or idealised portrayals of destinations in media. These narratives actively address and dispel misconceptions, offering tourists a more nuanced understanding of Indonesian culture and heritage. By drawing on their immersion in local culture, guides not only convey the visible aspects of cultural practices but also explain the underlying reasons, fostering a deeper appreciation and changing visitor perspectives.

A significant finding of this chapter is the way these narratives allow guides to highlight overlooked topics and enrich discussions around such as national identity. By tapping into lived experiences, guides can bring forward culturally significant yet underrepresented elements, presenting a fuller picture of Indonesian identity. This process of narrative crafting involves careful selection, framing, and negotiation, as described by MacCannell's concept of staged authenticity (1999), where guides present both the celebrated and controversial aspects of their

culture. In doing so, guides become agents of cultural representation, actively shaping how visitors perceive their society.

The chapter also reveals how guides employ universal themes as a narrative technique, using shared human experiences to connect tourists with local culture on an emotional level. Interpretation tools further enhance these narratives, immersing visitors more deeply in Indonesian culture by making the stories relatable and personally meaningful. Ultimately, this chapter concludes that through informal learning and lived experiences, Indonesian tour guides not only enrich the tourism experience but also contribute to a more complex and accurate portrayal of their society, embodying a unique role as cultural interpreters and agents of social narrative.

CHAPTER 7

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter outlines the conclusions and recommendations based on the findings and discussions from Chapters 5 and 6. The conclusions section highlights the study's main findings, raises additional questions stemming from these insights, and discusses implications for scholarly knowledge and research in heritage interpretation. Practical applications and recommendations tailored for Indonesian tourist guides are also presented, followed by an overview of study limitations and directions for future research.

The section on scholarly implications and knowledge creation addresses the study's contributions to heritage interpretation literature. Practical recommendations for Indonesian tourist guides discuss how and where the findings can be applied in the field. Study limitations are outlined, with particular emphasis on methodological and data analysis challenges encountered. Lastly, the recommendations for future research propose areas for further investigation and suggest ways to refine the methodologies used in this study.

7.1 Concluding Synthesis: Informal Learning and Narrative Construction

The focus of this study has been to examine the complexities of knowledge acquisition and narrative crafting among tourist guides in Indonesia. There is a notable lack of research focusing on the informal learning processes of tour guides, particularly regarding how informal interactions shape narrative construction in Indonesia. The lived experiences of tourist guides emerge as one of the most significant factors in creating authentic narratives that deeply connect visitors with the cultural and historical contexts of a site (Albrecht, 2023; Black & Weiler, 2013; Lugosi & Bray, 2013; Weiler & Ham, 2001). This study thus offers new insights into how

informal learning and informal knowledge can be effectively integrated into narrative construction, contributing to ecotourism development.

This study employs a qualitative approach, using semi-structured interviews and thematic analysis to address two key questions introduced in the opening chapter: how tourist guides in Indonesia acquire knowledge and how they use that knowledge to shape their tour narratives. Regarding the first question, findings reveal that Indonesian tourist guides predominantly rely on informal learning to acquire knowledge. This preference arises because formal training often has limitations in capturing the cultural richness and diversity of Indonesia. The formal training provided typically lacks the depth and local specificity that informal learning can offer, especially in a country as culturally diverse as Indonesia, where many aspects of heritage, tradition, and local knowledge are passed down through community practices and personal interactions rather than through formal education. Driven by the knowledge that they get from this informal learning and the guides' own lived experiences form the foundation of their narrative construction. These informal learning processes allow guides to incorporate culturally resonant stories, local insights, and unique perspectives into their tours, creating narratives that are authentic and deeply connected to the local environment and cultural context.

7.2 Revisiting the Aim and Objectives

In this section, the author revisits the research objectives to assess how effectively they have been achieved and to what extent. Additionally, by reflecting on these objectives, the author uncovers insights that emerged during the study, offering a deeper understanding of the core themes. This reflection not only highlights the success in addressing the initial aims but also uncovers areas of unexpected discovery that contribute to a more nuanced perspective on the research topic.

These insights offer a basis for discussing both the practical implications of the findings and potential directions for future research. The objectives of the research, as established in Chapter one, were as follows:

- To critically explore the processes through which tour guides in Indonesia acquire and integrate knowledge into their professional practice, focusing on the interplay between formal and informal learning frameworks.
- To analyse the methodologies employed by tour guides in constructing narratives that balance authenticity with audience engagement.

- To investigate the effectiveness and adaptability of interpretive tools and techniques used by tour guides to enhance narrative delivery and foster meaningful connections with diverse tourist demographics.
- To explore the socio-cultural dynamics influencing the narrative strategies of tour guides within the context of global and local heritage discourses.

7.2.1 To Critically Explore the Processes through which Tour Guides in Indonesia Acquire and Integrate Knowledge into their Professional Practice, Focusing on the Interplay Between Formal and Informal Learning Frameworks

This objective has been addressed by identifying and critically examining the process guides used to acquire knowledge. Many studies explore this knowledge acquisition process focusing on formal training (Weiler & Ham, 2002; Ap & Wong, 2001; Christie & Mason, 2003), while only a few focus on informal learning (Lugosi & Bray, 2008; Albrecht et al., 2022; McLeod, 2020). However, most of the research focuses only partially on aspects of peer learning, learning from visitors, and engaging with the local community (Salazar, 2008; Black & Weiler, 2015; Kodom-Wiredu et al., 2022). Therefore, rather than focusing on how they acquire knowledge only in one of the aspects of knowledge acquisition, the author offered the opportunity to explore both formal training and formulate peer learning, learning from visitors and engaging with the local community as a whole as an informal learning, particularly in the context of Indonesia.

The research emphasises that while formal training programmes provide foundational knowledge, they often fall short in addressing the full complexity of Indonesia's cultural and historical diversity. As a result, informal learning—including peer learning, community engagement, lived experience, and direct interactions with tourists—emerges as an essential complement to formal education, enabling guides to develop more authentic, personalised narratives that resonate deeply with visitors.

Formal training in Indonesia provides foundational knowledge and skills required for certification, which are heavily structured and geared toward standardising guiding practices through a framework of certification and competency assessments. This formal programme, managed by local tourism offices and aligned with the ASEAN Common Competency Standards for Tourism Professionals, focus on foundational skills like communication, ethics, historical knowledge, and basic guiding techniques. However, they often lack the specificity

and adaptability required to engage with Indonesia's intricate, varied cultures. This standardised approach may lead guides to rely on prescribed narratives, limiting their flexibility and often resulting in repetitive, impersonal tours.

To overcome these limitations, many Indonesian tourist guides turn to informal learning, which is found to be more effective in capturing the rich, localised knowledge that formal training overlooks. Informal learning avenues include mentorship from senior guides, interactions within guiding communities, and engagement in non-traditional learning spaces like “*nongkrong*” (casual gatherings in local cafes or food stalls). These informal interactions foster a supportive environment where guides can freely exchange insights, discuss challenges, and refine their guiding techniques. For example, guides often draw upon peers' experiences with specific expertise, allowing them to expand their knowledge of diverse topics such as geology, traditional crafts, or local folklore. This peer-to-peer learning nurtures a collective knowledgesharing culture that enriches both individual guides and the broader guiding community.

Lived experiences and direct interactions with tourists further enhance the narrative skills of guides, enabling them to adapt their stories to reflect personal insights and cultural authenticity. Many guides incorporate local myths, unique historical anecdotes, and lesser-known community narratives gathered through interviews with elders or interactions with knowledgeable visitors. This approach allows guides to bridge the gap between formal historical knowledge and the lived cultural heritage of local communities. The study notes that guides view tourists not just as audiences but as collaborators who can contribute valuable knowledge, often leading to the co-creation of enriched tour content. For example, when encountering a tourist with expertise in a specific cultural topic, guides may integrate the tourist's insights into future narratives, thus continually refining their storytelling approach.

The study also highlights the political and ideological constraints embedded in the formal training framework, which often prioritises the projection of an ideal or positive national image over critical engagement with Indonesia's complex history and social issues. This results in guides adhering to a form of “staged authenticity,” where they are encouraged to showcase only idealised aspects of Indonesian culture, potentially limiting the authenticity and depth of the visitor experience. These constraints are compounded by the Indonesian government's influence over training content, which reflects broader national narratives and may discourage guides from presenting culturally or politically sensitive information. The study suggests that

while formal training standardises skills, it may inadvertently restrict guides' ability to provide a full, balanced perspective on Indonesian heritage.

To address these limitations, the research advocates for the integration of informal learning methods into formal training frameworks to enhance the adaptability and cultural resonance of tour narratives. By leveraging informal knowledge sources such as lived experiences, local community insights, and co-creative efforts with local stakeholders, guides can present more nuanced and multidimensional portrayals of Indonesian culture. This co-creation approach encourages guides to work alongside local communities to develop narratives that honour local perspectives, fostering a sense of pride and ownership among community members while providing tourists with a richer, more grounded understanding of Indonesian heritage.

Challenges in relying on informal learning are acknowledged, particularly in navigating cultural biases and ensuring the reliability of information gained through informal sources. Some guides address this by cross-referencing information with academic or published sources, ensuring a balanced narrative that blends informal insights with verified historical facts. However, the study underscores that despite these challenges, the value of informal learning lies in its flexibility and its alignment with the dynamic, interactive nature of tour guiding.

In conclusion, this study reveals that Indonesian tourist guides operate within a complex knowledge ecosystem where formal training, though foundational, is often supplemented by informal learning to capture the full depth of Indonesia's cultural landscape. This blend of formal and informal knowledge acquisition empowers guides to serve as cultural mediators rather than mere transmitters of information, bridging the gap between tourists and the local environment. The study's findings suggest that fostering informal learning opportunities within the guiding profession can significantly enhance the authenticity and quality of tourism experiences, creating a more engaging, empathetic connection between visitors and Indonesian culture.

7.2.2 To Analyse the Methodologies Employed by Tour Guides in Constructing Narratives that Balance Authenticity with Audience Engagement

This objective explores how Indonesian tourist guides construct their narratives, focusing on the interplay between formal training, informal learning, and lived experiences. It addresses the

limitations of formal training, which is often standardised and unable to fully encompass the vast cultural diversity of Indonesia. As a result, tourist guides in Indonesia rely heavily on informal knowledge gained through interactions with local communities, peer learning, and personal lived experiences to bring depth, authenticity, and cultural resonance to their narrative. This study underscores that such informal learning processes are crucial in creating narratives that reflect the local context, making the guides' stories engaging and memorable for tourists.

One of the key findings is that informal learning, defined by experiences outside traditional education settings, provides guides with a "tacit knowledge" that enables them to add nuance and relatability to their narratives. For instance, tourist guides who grew up in the local area or maintain close community ties can incorporate local legends, folklore, and everyday customs that go beyond formal historical accounts, offering tourists an insider's view of Indonesia. This approach is particularly valuable in countries as culturally diverse as Indonesia, where each region has its unique traditions and history. Such personalised narrative helps guides act as cultural mediators, allowing tourists to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the local culture.

Clearly, many guides use their lived experiences to challenge stereotypes and reshape tourists' perspectives on Indonesian culture. For example, one guide addresses foreign tourists' misconceptions about poverty by explaining Indonesia's unique social dynamics, like people's preference for gathering outdoors during work breaks, which may be misunderstood by tourists. Another guide clarifies religious practices, such as Friday prayers, to offer tourists a respectful understanding of local customs. This adaptability to address biases and foster new perspectives is essential, particularly when dealing with foreign visitors who may lack a full understanding of Indonesia's cultural or social realities.

Guides' narratives often reflect their role as cultural advocates, balancing their personal values with the need for accuracy and respect for local traditions. This aligns with Cohen's (1985) theories on tour guiding, which suggest that guides must carefully navigate between neutrality and personal expression. Some guides, consciously incorporate politically charged or culturally sensitive topics, such as human rights, to educate tourists on aspects of Indonesia's history that may otherwise be overlooked. Furthermore, guides who personalise their narratives by infusing unique perspectives can transform ordinary tours into impactful experiences (Weiler & Black, 2020). Through these narratives, guides become more than just informers; they serve as

educators who encourage critical engagement, offering tourists a multifaceted understanding of the country's cultural and historical contexts.

The "tourist gaze," shaped by media and tourism marketing, often pressures guides to conform a curated image of Indonesia, overshadowing local authenticity. However, many guides strive to balance these expectations by sharing genuine insights drawn from their lived experiences, thereby challenging stereotypes and offering a counter-narrative to mainstream media depictions. For example, some guides use their personal backgrounds to provide nuanced interpretations of Indonesia's colonial past, highlighting aspects like social inequality and local resistance that are often underrepresented in traditional narratives.

Additionally, the research identifies the ethical challenges that guides face in interpreting sensitive cultural and historical topics, such as colonialism, economic disparity, and religious diversity. Guides must balance factual accuracy with cultural sensitivity, ensuring that their narratives are inclusive and respectful. Ethical considerations require guides to carefully select and frame stories that promote understanding without distressing local or international visitors when delivering controversial or sensitive topics by providing context and respectful explanations, allowing tourists to gain insight without reinforcing stereotypes or misconceptions.

Finally, by weaving elements of Indonesia's foundational ideology, Pancasila, into their narratives, guides reinforce national values of unity and diversity. This approach, as highlighted by Wang et al. (2023), contributes to a sense of national pride among both local and foreign tourists. Guides like Narsih and Onad integrate discussions of Pancasila to present a comprehensive portrayal of Indonesia, emphasising not only the tangible beauty of the country but also its intangible cultural values. This approach helps tourists appreciate the principles that underpin Indonesian society, making the experience both educational and emotionally resonant.

7.2.3 To Investigate the Effectiveness and Adaptability of Interpretive Tools and Techniques Used by Tour Guides to Enhance Narrative Delivery and Foster Meaningful Connections with Diverse Tourist Demographics

The research objective of exploring how these interpretive tools and techniques shape narrative construction highlights the number of ways guides enrich their narrative to foster meaningful connections with Indonesia's cultural heritage. This analysis uncovers a variety of approaches,

from personalising historical events to integrating sensory engagement and digital media, all of which contribute to a comprehensive and impactful experience for visitors.

The study reveals how the personalisation of historical events allows guides to convey Indonesian heritage in a way that feels intimate and relatable to visitors. Rather than presenting historical information solely as a series of factual events, guides transform history into a vibrant story by focusing on the lives and sacrifices of key figures in Indonesian history. This personalised approach brings historical figures to life, creating narratives that resonate on a deeply human level. For example, guides like Mondo share the sacrifices of independence leaders like Mohammad Hatta, highlighting the personal costs of their political commitments. This approach, which aligns with theories by Falk and Dierking (1992) on connecting content to visitors' lives, facilitates an emotional connection that enhances visitors' understanding of Indonesia's complex cultural journey. By highlighting these personal stories, guides do not merely recount facts; they create an immersive experience that fosters empathy and emotional engagement, transforming history from a distant subject into a shared human experience.

A related technique employed by guides is the incorporation of universal themes into their narratives. By drawing on fundamental concepts such as love, resilience, sacrifice, and self-improvement, guides are able to bridge cultural divides and make the stories of Indonesian heritage accessible to a global audience. These themes allow tourists from diverse backgrounds to find personal relevance in Indonesian culture, as they see reflections of their own struggles and achievements mirrored in the narratives. For example, guides often use analogies and metaphors to make complex or region-specific cultural elements more accessible. Aries, a guide at Borobudur, explains the temple's clockwise circumambulation in terms of self-improvement, describing the journey from left (imperfection) to right (goodness) as a path toward enlightenment. This use of universal themes aligns with Salazar's (2008) findings on guiding, which suggest that relatable comparisons enable visitors to appreciate complex cultural or spiritual concepts.

Sensory engagement emerges as another critical strategy for deepening the tourist experience. By involving tourists directly in cultural practices, guides foster active participation that enhances the educational impact of their narratives. This sensory-based approach aligns with experiential learning theories by scholars such as Ham (1992) and Beck and Cable (2011), who emphasise the role of hands-on experiences in transforming passive spectators into engaged participants. Guides like Bobby and Sebastian engage tourists in activities such as performing

Islamic ablution or participating in rice harvesting, fostering a physical and emotional connection to Indonesian customs. These immersive experiences encourage tourists to explore Indonesian culture not only through observation but through active participation, touching, tasting, and feeling elements of local life. By inviting tourists to perform activities themselves, guides help them develop a deeper understanding of the cultural values embedded in these practices, creating a powerful, sensory-rich experience that is both educational and memorable.

In addition to personal and sensory elements, visual aids and digital tools are central to enhancing the narrative construction of Indonesian tour guides. Visual aids such as maps, photographs, diagrams, and physical artefacts help clarify complex information, making Indonesia's cultural diversity and historical intricacies more accessible. Digital devices, including tablets, are used to present dynamic content like videos, music, and historical photos, allowing guides to create a more vivid representation of cultural practices. For instance, Acil uses an iPad to play *Gamelan music* and show *Wayang Kulit* performances, breathing life into static museum displays and enriching tourists' understanding of these cultural artefacts. Maps are also invaluable, particularly for international tourists unfamiliar with Indonesia's vast archipelago. This integration of multimedia helps overcome the limitations of physical exhibits and makes intangible cultural elements more tangible and accessible for tourists. Aerial videos and interactive maps also offer a comprehensive perspective, particularly useful in conveying the spatial and historical context of significant sites. For instance, Tifa uses aerial footage to give tourists a bird's-eye view of locations such as the Kali Besar, allowing them to appreciate its architectural beauty and historical significance in ways that go beyond conventional narrative techniques. This multimedia approach aligns with Falk and Dierking's (2013) emphasis on the role of visual aids in enhancing the museum experience and supports the notion that visual storytelling can engage audiences in ways that words alone cannot achieve.

7.2.4 To Explore the Socio-Cultural Dynamics Influencing the Narrative Strategies of Tour Guides within the Context of Global and Local Heritage Discourses

The socio-cultural dynamics influencing the narrative strategies of Indonesian tour guides are intricately tied to their roles as cultural mediators, balancing local traditions, informal learning, and global tourism demands. For instance, tour guides at prominent sites like Borobudur and Prambanan integrate philosophical and spiritual dimensions into their narratives, revealing the interconnectedness of tangible and intangible heritage to create deeper emotional resonance with visitors (Salazar, 2008; UNESCO, 2003). These personalised narratives often stem from

informal learning processes such as peer mentorship, community engagement, and personal lived experiences. This approach enables guides to draw on the deep knowledge of local communities, regarded as more authentic and reliable due to its grounding in lived realities. By incorporating insights from long-term residents and community elders, guides ensure their narratives resonate with cultural authenticity while fostering trust among tourists. As participant Fido noted, leveraging the knowledge of locals who have spent a lifetime in these areas lends unparalleled validity to the stories told to visitors (Marsick & Watkins, 2001).

Tour guides also navigate the challenge of presenting heritage authentically while addressing global expectations for standardised tourist experiences. For example, guides enhance their storytelling by combining their own experiences with meticulously verified historical sources. This triangulation of information, involving cross-referencing local narratives with academic texts and digital resources, allows guides to construct well-rounded and credible narratives that maintain cultural integrity. For example, Jono described how guides verify and expand upon the stories they hear from local informants, ensuring that their narratives are robust and transparent when shared with tourists (Tilden, 1957;). Such practices align with the principles of heritage interpretation, which emphasise the importance of provoking curiosity and fostering emotional connections beyond the mere presentation of factual information (Beck & Cable, 2011; Ham, 1992).

Addressing stereotypes and misconceptions about Indonesian culture further illustrates the socio-cultural complexities faced by guides. For instance, Lesmana explained how tourists often misinterpret scenes of workers gathering outdoors during breaks as evidence of poverty. He clarified to visitors that such practices reflect Indonesia's communal lifestyle and flexible working arrangements rather than economic hardship. Similarly, Sebastian shared how he corrected a tourist who mistook a sarong worn during Friday prayers for a skirt. He explained the sarong's cultural and religious importance, fostering greater respect for Indonesian traditions. These examples highlight how guides challenge reductive narratives by weaving together historical facts, cultural insights, and lived experiences to provide a more nuanced and respectful understanding of Indonesia's diverse heritage.

These examples demonstrate how informal learning, cultural sensitivity, and innovative interpretation empower Indonesian tour guides to craft narratives that authentically represent the country's diverse heritage. By bridging the gap between local realities and global expectations, guides play a pivotal role in fostering cultural preservation and delivering

enriching tourist experiences. This dual approach, rooted in community insights and rigorous knowledge validation, ensures that tourists gain a comprehensive and meaningful understanding of Indonesia's heritage landscape.

7.3 Contributions to Knowledge

This thesis contributes new and original insights to the study of heritage interpretation and tour guiding, particularly by foregrounding the role of informal learning in shaping the construction of heritage narratives. Within the broader field of tourism studies, the processes through which guides acquire, share, and perform knowledge have often been examined through the lens of formal, institutionalised training. As a result, the informal and community-based learning that underpins much of guiding practice has remained largely underexplored (Lugosi & Bray, 2008; Black & Weiler, 2015; Albrecht et al., 2022). By investigating how Indonesian tour guides learn and construct meaning through everyday social interaction, peer exchange, and lived experience, this study expands theoretical understanding of how interpretive authority is developed, negotiated, and enacted in practice.

Through a qualitative, constructivist approach, the thesis illuminates the socially embedded and culturally grounded nature of knowledge production in guiding. It reveals that guides' learning extends far beyond the boundaries of formal training and certification frameworks and that their interpretive competence often depends on informal networks and collective social capital within guiding communities. In doing so, the study challenges the persistent assumption that professional expertise derives primarily from institutional instruction and technical mastery. Instead, it conceptualises knowledge as relational, experiential, and continuously co-produced through community engagement and shared practice.

This thesis makes a clear and original theoretical contribution to the study of heritage interpretation and tour guiding by establishing informal learning as the core mechanism through which interpretive authority is constructed, shared, and sustained. It advances the field beyond its dominant emphasis on formal, institution-based training models (Weiler & Ham, 2002; Black & Weiler, 2015), showing instead that professional expertise emerges from the social, cultural, and ethical relationships that guides cultivate within their communities. Whereas much of the heritage interpretation literature has explored how visitors learn informally (Falk & Storksdieck, 2010; McClain & Zimmerman, 2020; Greaves, 2023), this thesis reframes the conversation by demonstrating that guides themselves are informal learners and knowledge

producers, continuously constructing meaning through lived experience, community engagement, and interpersonal dialogue.

The study positions social capital theory (Bourdieu, 1986) as a central conceptual frame rather than a supporting tool. Through this lens, it reconceptualises informal learning as a form of socially embedded knowledge production, where interpretive competence depends on networks of trust, reciprocity, and belonging. These social relationships form the foundation of guiding practice, determining how knowledge circulates, whose voices are amplified, and how professional legitimacy is conferred within the guiding community. In doing so, the thesis extends social capital theory into the domain of tourism interpretation, demonstrating how cultural capital—in the form of local wisdom, historical familiarity, and ethical responsibility—is mobilised through social relationships to generate interpretive authority.

By framing knowledge as a collective rather than an individual asset, the study challenges linear or technocratic models of professional development and positions guiding as a relational practice deeply tied to community well-being. Informal knowledge sharing—through *nongkrong* gatherings, peer mentorship, and collaborative storytelling—is shown to be not simply a functional response to limited formal training but a culturally ingrained mode of learning that reproduces solidarity and moral accountability within the profession. This reconceptualisation of learning through social capital provides a robust theoretical explanation for how guiding communities maintain resilience and coherence despite institutional fragmentation.

The thesis also makes a significant contribution to postcolonial and constructivist theory by repositioning guides as active cultural agents who both navigate and contest dominant narratives. Extending Smith's (2006) AHD and Said's (1978) *Orientalism*, the findings demonstrate that Indonesian guides reinterpret official histories through ethically reflexive and emotionally grounded storytelling. Their use of humour, empathy, and spiritual reference constitutes an act of subtle resistance that deconstructs Western-centric and state-sanctioned portrayals of culture. In this way, the research advances theoretical understanding of how interpretive authority operates under postcolonial conditions, revealing it as a dynamic negotiation between institutional power, community voice, and global expectation.

In addition, by integrating experiential and interpretive learning theories (Ham, 1992; Beck & Cable, 2011) with social capital, the thesis expands the conceptualisation of interpretation from a transmission model to a transformative process. It provides empirical evidence that sensory

participation, affective storytelling, and participatory co-creation with communities not only deepen visitor engagement but also cultivate intercultural empathy and ethical awareness. This supports Reisinger and Steiner's (2006) vision of guides as cultural advocates while extending it by foregrounding the emotional and moral dimensions of their interpretive labour.

Collectively, these theoretical contributions position informal learning as the foundation of interpretive practice and establish social capital as the mechanism through which such learning is generated, legitimised, and sustained. They also advance understanding of interpretive agency in postcolonial contexts, showing that authenticity is not fixed or institutional but relational, negotiated, and situated. Importantly, the theoretical insights developed through the Indonesian case have analytical transferability to other heritage destinations across the Global South and beyond. In contexts where tourism professionals operate within constrained institutional systems or contested cultural narratives, the concept of informal, socially embedded learning offers a universal framework for understanding how guides, curators, or cultural mediators produce meaning.

Thus, the thesis not only extends social capital theory into a new empirical field but also advances a relational theory of interpretive legitimacy, illustrating how professional authority in heritage interpretation emerges from the moral, emotional, and social ties that bind guiding communities. This relational perspective provides a conceptual bridge between learning, narrative construction, and heritage communication, offering a globally transferable model for analysing interpretation as a socially grounded, ethically charged, and transformative practice.

7.4 Implication and Practical Recommendation

Indonesia's training programme must evolve beyond a focus on practical skills and standardised content delivery to foster a truly authentic approach to tour guiding. Authenticity in guiding necessitates a deeper engagement with the material, encouraging guides to explore the rich cultural and historical narratives that make their destinations unique. By incorporating immersive, interactive learning experiences, training can inspire guides to research and form meaningful connections with the cultural and historical dimensions of tour sites, ultimately enabling them to offer tourists a more nuanced, enriching, and genuinely authentic experience. As Indonesia seeks to strengthen its position within the global tourism landscape, re-evaluating and updating its tour guide training programme is essential. This process should embrace a collaborative approach, engaging stakeholders across government bodies, educational institutions, and the tourism industry to build comprehensive programme that not only adhere

to regulatory standards but also promote authentic cultural representation and critical engagement with Indonesia's heritage.

Incorporating direct feedback from active tourist guides into curriculum development could yield practical insights into the real-world challenges faced in the field. Establishing a feedback loop between guides and programme developers would help to create a responsive framework, adapting to the evolving needs of both guides and tourists. As tourism trends continue to shift, Indonesia's training programme must be adaptable, ensuring guides are well-equipped with the skills, knowledge, and confidence required to provide engaging, authentic experiences that leave a lasting impact on visitors.

Furthermore, strengthening the connections between universities, the research community, and the tour-guiding industry would open up valuable pathways for exploring Indonesia's intangible cultural heritage—local wisdom, myths, legends, and unique cultural practices—in ways that offer tourists fresh and insightful perspectives. Equipping guides with enhanced heritage interpretation skills can make tours more memorable and meaningful, giving visitors a richer understanding of the stories and sites they encounter. Additionally, fostering these interpretive skills within local and Indigenous communities can empower community members to serve as guides, benefiting economically from tourism while actively preserving and celebrating their own cultural heritage.

In light of the study's findings, which underscore the value of informal learning for professional growth, these recommendations highlight the potential for tourist guides to reflect on and integrate their own informal learning experiences into their guiding practices. Emphasising this approach in training may also inspire guides to reconnect with their cultural heritage and identity, fostering both personal and professional enrichment.

7.5 Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

This research has several limitations, particularly related to researcher subjectivity, which can be both an advantage and a limitation. All qualitative research involves some level of researcher bias, shaped by personal worldviews and values. In this study, the author brings an insider's perspective as a guide, offering unique insights into the world of Indonesian tour guides. However, this dual role of insider and outsider can impact the study, especially during data collection. As an insider, familiarity with the community could lead to assumptions, potentially affecting objectivity and leading to selective interpretation of data. Conversely, as an outsider,

the author may lack access to certain cultural nuances, risking misinterpretation of culturally embedded practices. Additionally, this dual perspective may have influenced participant perceptions: some may have viewed me as an outsider, leading to guarded responses, while others may have assumed shared knowledge, leaving some insights unspoken. Balancing these roles can blur boundaries, making it challenging to maintain complete neutrality, as there may be an unconscious tendency to favour one perspective over the other.

Second, the sample in this research can be considered extensive, as it includes participants from three key groups: tour guides, trainers, and a small number of tourists. However, given Indonesia's vastness with over 17,000 islands, five main islands, and a population that ranks fourth globally the sample size may appear limited. Indonesia has approximately 20,000 licensed tour guides, though the actual number of active guides is likely higher, with most tour activities concentrated in Bali. This research sample, covering only three major cities—Jakarta, Bandung, and Yogyakarta—is nonetheless considered sufficient and representative for the study's purposes.

Third, although several English-speaking guides were interviewed, most of them were volunteer museum guides, many of whom are expatriates residing temporarily in Indonesia. This introduces a clear bias, as the research primarily contrasts these guides with Indonesian guides who work as permanent museum staff, official tour guides, and walking tour guides.

Fourth, although this research includes three participant groups, it primarily focuses on tourist guides and trainers, with tourists playing a smaller role. While tourist perspectives were incorporated, their contribution is less prominent and primarily supports data triangulation. Future research could explore tourists' perceptions of informal knowledge and practices in tour guiding, particularly in heritage tourism, to provide additional insights into the overall tour experience. Interviews with tourists in this study revealed their appreciation and interest in learning more about informal knowledge practices. This suggests an opportunity for further research on how tour guides' narratives may influence tourists' attitudes and perspectives.

Since training is fundamental to equipping guides with essential knowledge and skills, future research could also assess the effectiveness of Indonesia's tour guiding training programme. Evaluating how well these programmes integrate heritage interpretation, informal learning, and localised cultural content could provide insights into how training can better prepare guides to

offer authentic and meaningful experiences for tourists, ultimately fostering a more sustainable approach to heritage tourism.

Some guides in this study have recognised and applied heritage interpretation in their tours, even though this concept is relatively new in the field of tour guiding in Indonesia. Future research could further explore how heritage interpretation can reconceptualise the tour guide's communicative role in enhancing the tour experience. Given Indonesia's many islands and rich cultural diversity, there is also an opportunity to investigate how heritage interpretation might support the preservation of both natural and cultural heritage across the country. Additionally, since Indonesia's communal culture is rooted in strong social capital, research could examine how these social networks could be leveraged to reinforce heritage preservation efforts through interpretation.

7.6 Final Thoughts

At the beginning of this research journey, I set out to explore the largely uncharted territory of informal learning and narrative construction among Indonesian tour guides. Along the way, I encountered unforeseen challenges, from the disruptions of the global pandemic to technical setbacks that reminded me of the unpredictability inherent in research. These obstacles tested my resolve, enriching my understanding and reinforcing that the path to knowledge is seldom linear. In many ways, these experiences mirrored the essence of my research: the intricate blend of formal and informal learning, the resilience of local voices, and the strength in adapting to one's surroundings.

This study not only bridged gaps in academic knowledge but also reshaped my own understanding of narrative and heritage interpretation. By engaging deeply with the guides' experiences, I learned that tour guiding is more than mere storytelling; it is a craft, a vehicle for cultural empathy, and a means of reconnecting with one's heritage. This PhD journey has, indeed, been transformative, both personally and academically. As I conclude this chapter, I carry forward a renewed belief in the power of informal learning and heritage tourism to foster deeper connections and understanding. This journey leaves me inspired by the potential for research to create an impact, and I am grateful for the opportunity to share the insights and stories of those who make Indonesia's heritage resonate with visitors from all over the world.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Participation Information Sheet

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Name of School : Business and Creative Industries

Name of Degree : Doctor of Philosophy

Title of Project : Examining the Communication Process of Interpreters that Affects the Attitudes and Behaviour of Heritage Visitors.

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it involves. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Please feel free to ask questions if anything you read is not clear or would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you want to take part.

Thank you for reading this.

My Name is Khrisnamurti, I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. As for my research project I have chosen to research the communication process of interpreters that affects the attitudes and behaviour of heritage visitors. The University of the West of Scotland School of Business and Creative Industries is supporting me to undertake this project.

What is the purpose of this investigation?

The purpose of this research is to explore the communication process between the interpreter that affects the attitudes and behaviour of heritage sites. It seeks to understand how interpreters or tour guides acquire knowledge and how their narration influences visitors' attitudes and behaviour at the heritage sites in Indonesia.

Research Objectives

The study will address the following objectives:

- To examine the sources of knowledge and their acquisition process by heritage interpreters.
- To investigate interpretation tools used by heritage interpreters in enhancing heritage communication.
- To examine the narrative that interpreters applied to influence the visitors' attitudes and behaviours.

Do you have to take part?

Participation in this study is voluntary. This information sheet will describe the study to you. I will then ask you to sign a consent form to show you agree to take part. At any time, you are free to withdraw without giving a reason. This will not affect the standard of care you receive.

What will you do in the project?

You will be interviewed for approximately 60 to 90 minutes. You will be asked to answer some questions in relation to the studied subject.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been chosen because as an interpreter or a tourist or an interpreter trainer, you might have experience that is related with the research. You may have an idea about how do the interpreters acquire knowledge and how their narration influences visitors' attitudes and behaviour at the heritage sites. Your experience may help us to develop a better understanding about the communication process between interpreters and heritage visitors.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort.

What happens to the information in the project?

Any data collected as part of this research will be stored securely for 3 years following the publication of the results. Only the primary researcher and the supervision team will have access to participants' information (identities, audio records) and the data collected will be anonymised and be on a secure server (UWS) one-drive password protected.

The data controller ensures that the only research team are authorized to access the data with the understanding that all the information of the participants will remain protected from unauthorized persons. All data will be stored on UWS secure systems.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office who implements the Data Protection Act 1998. All personal data on participants will be processed in accordance with the provisions of the Data Protection Act 1998.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in this project, please sign the consent form to confirm this. If you do not wish to be involved, thank you very much for your time.

If desired, a feedback report can be sent once the investigation is complete.

This investigation was granted ethical approval by the University of the West of Scotland, School of Business and Creative Industries ethics committee.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or from whom further information may be sought please contact:

School Ethics Committee

School of Business and Creative Industries

Paisley Campus

University of the West of Scotland,

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Researcher Details:

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Appendix 2: Participant Consent Form

School of Business and Creative Industries

Informed Consent

Title of the study: “Examining the Communication Process of the Interpreters that Affects the Attitudes and Behaviours of Heritage Visitors”

Dear Participants,

I am **Khrisnamurti**, a PhD researcher at the University of the West of Scotland, at the School of Business and Creative Industries.

I am carrying out this study as part of my PhD research. The purpose of this research is to explore the communication process of the heritage interpreters that influence the change of attitudes and behaviour.

My main participants in this study will be Indonesia interpreters, tourists and interpreter trainers.

I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.

1. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
2. I understand that I am going to:
 - a. Pilot study (about 45 mins)
 - b. Participate in an interview (approx.60-90 mins).
 - c. Be audio-recorded during the interview.
3. I understand that any information recorded in the data collection process will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
4. I consent to being a participant in the project.

Name of the participant:

Date

Signature

.....

.....

Name of the researcher: Khrisnamurti

Date

Signature

Appendix 3: Ethical Approval

17/05/2022

Dear Khrisnamurti .,

Your application 18010: Examining the Communication Process of the Interpreters that Affects the Attitudes and Behaviours of Heritage Visitors, submission 15232, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

Appendix 4: Codes and Themes

Theme	Description	Codes
Formal Training and Certification	This theme refers to Indonesia's structured approach to tourist guide training, highlighting formal programs, certification processes, and alignment with ASEAN standards for professional development.	"Structured training", "certification process", "professional standards", "curriculum design", "regulatory compliance", "skills development", "assessment and evaluation", "trainer qualifications",
Informal Learning Dynamics	This theme refers to the role of informal learning methods in complementing formal training, emphasising real-life experiences, peer networks, and community engagement as essential to guides' professional and cultural development.	"Experiential learning", "peer networks", "community engagement", "cultural authenticity", "professional development", "mentorship", "personal observations", "local knowledge integration", "adaptive learning", "contextual learning"
Integration of Learning Methods	This theme refers to analysing how informal learning integrates with formal education to provide a comprehensive knowledge base, allowing guides to deliver authentic cultural experiences.	"Integration of methods", "blended learning strategies", "practical and theoretical balance", "continuous improvement"
Challenges of Learning Methods	This theme refers to the challenges and limitations of both formal and informal learning methods, including biases, maintenance of accuracy, complexities of standardisation, and other external factors impacting learning efficacy.	"Training challenges", "bias and accuracy", "standardisation issues", "external influences", "methodological limitations"

<p>Community and Cultural Engagement</p>	<p>This theme refers to how tourist guides in Indonesia interact with and learn from local communities to acquire authentic cultural knowledge. This engagement enriches guiding practices and enhances the tourist experience with culturally resonant narratives.</p>	<p>"Experiential learning", "cultural narratives", "community collaboration", "authenticity in guiding", "cultural insight sharing", "impact on professional practice", "local expertise utilisation",</p>
<p>Role of Social Capital in Informal Learning</p>	<p>This theme refers to how social networks and relationships enhance the learning processes among tourist guides. It highlights the importance of peer interactions, mentorship, community integration, and the exchange of knowledge and skills through various social mechanisms that enhance professional and cultural competence.</p>	<p>"Peer collaboration", "mentorship impact", "community ties", "trust building", "knowledge sharing mechanisms", "professional networking", "cultural insight exchange", "adaptive learning practices"</p>
<p>Redefining Indonesian Tourism Narratives</p>	<p>This theme refers to how Indonesian tour guides use informal learning and cultural insights to reshape the conventional narratives about Indonesia. They counteract simplistic and often stereotypical views, offering more nuanced and authentic portrayals of Indonesian destinations.</p>	<p>"Countering stereotypes", "authentic portrayal", "cultural insights", "informal learning impact", "narrative complexity", "visitor perspective shift"</p>
<p>Role of Tourist Guides as Cultural Intermediaries</p>	<p>This theme refers to guides acting as cultural intermediaries who use their deep knowledge and lived experiences to bridge the gap between local cultures and tourist perceptions. They meticulously select and present cultural details to ensure narratives are both accurate and engaging, helping tourists appreciate the complexity of Indonesian culture.</p>	<p>"Cultural bridging", "narrative accuracy", "deep cultural engagement", "lived experiences", "interpretative flexibility", "educational outreach"</p>

<p>Enhancing Engagement Through Narrative Techniques</p>	<p>This theme refers to the advanced narrative techniques used by guides to make historical and cultural information engaging. These include storytelling that personalises historical events, the use of metaphors and analogies to simplify complex ideas, and the deployment of interactive elements to deepen tourists' connection to the narrative.</p>	<p>"storytelling", "metaphors and analogies", "interactive engagement", "personalised history"</p>
<p>Challenging Misconceptions and Expanding Perspectives</p>	<p>This theme refers to guides who challenge existing misconceptions and broaden tourists' perspectives by integrating their own experiences and observations into the narratives. They provide deeper insights into Indonesia's social, cultural, and economic realities.</p>	<p>"Expanding perspectives", "social insights", "realities", "cultural complexities", "historical context", "interactive discussions", "myth debunking"</p>
<p>Enhancing Visitor Engagement through Interpretive and Sensory Tools</p>	<p>This theme refers to the consolidation of the use of interpretive tools and interactive techniques to engage multiple senses. It includes the employment of digital media, physical props, and sensory activities that immerse tourists more deeply into the local environment and cultural practices.</p>	<p>"Digital tools", "physical props", "visual aids", "sensory engagement", "interactive techniques", "multisensory experiences", "immersive storytelling"</p>